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Abstract

Task 2.3 focused on assessing the potential for scaling up promising business and innovation models identified in previous tasks. One key aspect of this assessment involved investigating acceptance of these business models among potential buyers and sellers. Several partners conducted valuation studies in representative contexts to examine the willingness-to-pay for improvements in ecosystem services or certification and understand their interactions. Another important focus was on adoption studies among farmers and land managers. This involved identifying relevant drivers that influence the adoption of selected business models. Furthermore, the task sought to estimate the potential market value and by this the hypothetical societal value that could be created through the scaling up of the selected business models. For categorising the different business models, the work in this task built on results from T2.2.

Summary

Deliverable 2.3 of the NOVASOIL project assesses the upscaling potential of promising business and innovation models for soil health. Building on earlier tasks, the work evaluates farmer and consumer perspectives through a set of discrete choice experiments (DCEs) and other surveys conducted in multiple European countries. The central aim was to explore the willingness-to-pay (WTP) for soil-related ecosystem services and certification schemes, the willingness-to-accept (WTA) compensation for adopting soil-friendly practices, and the societal benefits of scaling up such models.

The findings highlight substantial heterogeneity in preferences across contexts. Farmers generally favoured familiar and less risky models, particularly agri-environmental climate schemes (AECS), which provide relatively secure payments and shorter contract durations. In contrast, carbon farming initiatives often faced scepticism due to their long-term commitments, result-based monitoring, and uncertainty around certificate prices. Value chain approaches, such as certification schemes and eco-labels, proved more attractive in scenarios with flexible conditions and short-term obligations.

From the consumer side, the type of business model was less relevant than its design. Consumers preferred shorter payment commitments and valued guarantees of measurable environmental outcomes. Although many expressed willingness to support soil-friendly products or offset carbon emissions, price sensitivity and reluctance to engage in long-term contracts limited their commitment.

Overall, the results suggest that while significant market interest exists, large-scale adoption depends on designing business models that combine economic feasibility, flexibility for farmers, credible environmental outcomes, and consumer trust. The societal benefits of successful upscaling include enhanced carbon sequestration, biodiversity preservation, and more resilient food systems, yet these gains require coordinated policy support, effective monitoring frameworks, and stable market incentives.

1. Introduction

Healthy soils are essential for producing nutritious food, preserving biodiversity, and enabling a circular economy. They are critical to preventing land degradation and desertification and are key to achieving climate neutrality (European Commission 2025a). However, around 60% of European soils are currently in poor condition due to unsustainable practices such as intensive farming, pollution, and soil compaction (European Commission 2025a). The resulting loss of vital ecosystem services, such as food and feed production, water regulation, pest control, and carbon sequestration, leads to annual costs of at least €50 billion (European Commission 2025a).

To address this, the EU introduced the Soil Monitoring Law in July 2023, aimed at promoting sustainable land use and restoring soil health (European Commission 2023). Priority actions include reducing erosion, salinization, and contamination, with particular emphasis on conserving soil organic matter – an essential measure to meet the EU Green Deal's goal of climate neutrality by 2050 (European Commission 2025b).

Increasing soil organic carbon (SOC) is a proven method of removing CO₂ from the atmosphere and storing it in soils (McDonald et al. 2021). Effective SOC-enhancing practices include improved crop rotation (especially legumes), intercropping, conversion of arable land to grassland, reduced tillage, and organic farming (McDonald et al. 2021; Lahmar 2010; Casagrande et al. 2016). In addition to climate benefits, these practices improve soil structure, water retention, erosion resistance, and nutrient availability (Dumbrell et al. 2016). Despite these advantages, adoption can be hindered by short-term opportunity costs, for example, reduced profits from diverse rotations or high upfront investment in specialized equipment like flotation tires (Sattler and Nagel 2010).

Research shows that financial incentives, both public (Schaub et al. 2023; Schulze et al. 2024) and private (Buck and Palumbo-Compton 2022; Mamine et al. 2020; Weituschat et al. 2023), can play a key role in encouraging farmers to adopt soil health practices. A study by McDonald et al. (2021), commissioned by the Committee on the Environment, Public Health and Food Safety (ENVI), identified four distinct models for supporting soil health friendly practices. While the models differ in the payment mechanism and the parties involved, they all result in farmers being paid for an extra effort that increases the SOC content and thus sequesters CO₂.

First, in land management practice payments, central funders provide financial rewards for climate-friendly, carbon-sequestering farming practices. A prominent example is the agri-environmental climate schemes (AECS) under the Common Agricultural Policy's (CAP) second pillar.

Second, in value chain engagement, farmers produce according to standards that promote soil health, with agri-food companies paying farmers directly through their supply chains. Consumers can recognize these efforts via labels on food products.

In the third and fourth business models, greenhouse gas (GHG) certificates are generated through increased SOC and subsequent CO₂ storage. These certificates are either sold to buyers through an intermediary (third model) or directly exchanged between farmers and purchasers (fourth model).

While some of these are already well-established business models, there are also many business models that currently fill regional niches. In the value chain approach, for example, tourism can also be included as a source of income. Private markets can trade not only in CO₂ certificates, but also in other sustainability services. Depending on the regional and, above all, agricultural context, business models can differ in terms of customer segments, value propositions, key activities, resources or sources of income.

The research described in this deliverable aimed to assess the upscaling potential of promising business and innovation models for sustainable land use. It includes investigations into consumer acceptance and willingness to pay (WTP) for improvements in ecosystem services and certification schemes, as well as their interactions. Furthermore, it examines adoption potential among farmers and land managers by identifying key drivers for large-scale adoption.

2. Conceptual framework – acceptance of soil health promoting business models

The decision-making process behind the acceptance of **soil health promoting business models** can be informed by the extensive literature on farmer participation in agri-environmental climate schemes (AECS). Drawing from this body of work, the factors influencing adoption can be grouped into two overarching categories: **business model factors** and **farm-specific factors**.

Business Model Factors

These factors refer to the design, structure, and delivery attributes of the soil health promoting business model. Inspired by AECS literature (Brotherton, 1989, 1991; Ruto & Garrod, 2009; Raina et al., 2021), these can be categorized into five key dimensions:

- **General Attributes:** Include structural aspects such as the duration of the business model contract, size and scale of implementation, and the availability of consultation or technical support. These elements influence the perceived feasibility and attractiveness of the model.
- **Monetary Attributes:** Encompass all financial incentives, revenue-sharing mechanisms, cost coverage, and risk mitigation tools associated with participation. Monetary considerations are often the most decisive factors (Kuhfuss et al., 2016; Latacz-Lohmann & Breustedt, 2019).
- **Flexibility Attributes:** Refer to the extent to which the business model allows for adaptive implementation. Models that accommodate unexpected weather conditions, market shifts, or changes in farming operations are likely to be more acceptable to farmers.
- **Prescription Attributes:** Involve the degree of control, monitoring, and compliance required. Overly rigid or bureaucratic systems may reduce acceptance, while transparent and supportive governance can enhance trust and participation.
- **Purpose Attributes:** Reflect the environmental or agronomic objectives of the business model, such as increasing soil organic matter, reducing erosion, or enhancing microbial biodiversity. A strong alignment between the purpose of the model and the farmer's values or goals can positively influence uptake.

Farm-Specific Factors

These include characteristics intrinsic to the farm or farmer that shape how a given business model is perceived and adopted. Consistent with the AECS literature (Ruto & Garrod, 2009; Dessart et al., 2019), these can be divided into:

- **Farm characteristics:** Such as farm size, cultivation practices, main production branch, full-time or part-time farms or regional growing conditions.
- **Socio-Demographic Characteristics:** Such as age, education level, farm size, tenure, and income dependency. These factors often moderate risk perception and investment decisions.
- **Behavioural Characteristics:** These are further broken down into:
 - **Cognitive Factors:** Include farmers' knowledge and understanding of soil health benefits, perceived risks of the new model, and cost-benefit assessments.
 - **Dispositional Factors:** Refer to attitudes toward innovation, environmental concern, and risk tolerance. Farmers with a proactive or conservation-oriented mindset are more likely to adopt SHPBMs.
 - **Social Factors:** Highlight the influence of peer networks, advisory services, and community norms. Farmers often look to their peers or trusted advisors for signals on the viability and legitimacy of new practices.

Understanding these diverse influences is critical for the design of business models that not only promote soil health but are also aligned with farmers' operational realities and motivations. Just as in the AECS context, effective soil health strategies must be co-developed with stakeholders, consider behavioural nuances, and provide tangible, flexible, and economically viable pathways for sustainable farming.

Consumer behaviour in this context can be conceptualized along three main categories: **awareness and values, perceived product attributes,** and **external influences and constraints.** Together, these elements shape whether and how consumers support soil health initiatives through their purchasing choices or broader market engagement.

Awareness and Values (Grunert et al., 2014; Thøgersen, 2010; Vermeir & Verbeke, 2006).

- **Environmental Awareness:** Consumers who are aware of the links between agricultural practices and environmental outcomes (e.g., soil degradation, carbon sequestration, biodiversity) are more likely to value soil health as a criterion in their food purchasing decisions.
- **Sustainability Values:** Ethical consumption patterns, such as support for regenerative agriculture, organic products, or climate-resilient farming, are often rooted in broader pro-environmental and health-related values.
- **Trust and Belief in Impact:** Consumers are more inclined to support soil-friendly products if they believe their choices lead to real environmental benefits. Clear and credible information about impact can therefore build trust and increase engagement.

Perceived Product Attributes (Hughner et al., 2007; Janssen & Hamm, 2012)

- **Labelling and Certification:** Eco-labels, sustainability certifications, or QR-code traceability systems influence consumer willingness to pay by signalling soil-friendly production methods. However, the effectiveness depends on recognition, clarity, and credibility of the label.
- **Quality and Health Perceptions:** Products grown under soil health-promoting practices may be perceived as healthier, fresher, or more “natural.” These perceptions can drive purchasing behaviour, particularly in high-value markets (e.g., organic, local, premium).
- **Price Sensitivity:** While many consumers express willingness to support sustainable products, actual behaviour is often price-sensitive. The perceived value of soil health practices must outweigh any cost premium.

External Influences and Constraints (Aertsens et al., 2009; Hartmann & Siegrist, 2017; Lindenberg & Steg, 2007)

- **Social Norms and Identity:** Consumer behaviour is influenced by societal expectations, peer influence, and identity alignment (e.g., “green consumer”). Messaging and branding that resonate with consumer identity can enhance engagement.

- **Information Availability:** Accessibility of information through media, point-of-sale communication, or digital platforms influences awareness and decision-making. Confusing or overwhelming messages can backfire.
- **Policy and Retail Structures:** Availability of sustainable products, retailer prioritization (e.g., shelf placement, promotions), and public campaigns also shape consumer access and choice.

3. Methodological approach – Discrete Choice Experiments

To estimate the potential of soil health promoting business models, different methods can be used to determine either farmers' or consumers' preferences for these models. As discrete choice experiments (DCE) are frequently used to measure farmers' preferences for all kinds of sustainable practices, e.g., the conversion of arable land to grassland or the reduction of pesticide use, the DCE approach seems to be a suitable method to estimate soil health incentive preferences. As it was frequently used within the case studies analysed here, this section provides an overview of the underlying theory.

The DCE approach is based on two key economic theories: Lancaster's Theory, which states that the utility of a good is derived from its attributes (Lancaster, 1966; Vass et al., 2017) and Random Utility Theory (McFadden, 1973), which assumes that respondents will maximize their utility (U). Participants are asked to choose among a finite set of alternatives, called a choice set (Hasler et al., 2019). In each choice situation, levels of the attributes are combined differently, creating trade-offs between options.

In a choice situation t , participant n will select one alternative i over other alternatives j if $U_{it} > U_{jt}$, $j \neq i$. The total value, thus the utility, of an alternative i , is the sum of all attributes' values (deterministic component) and a random or stochastic component ε_{nit} :

$$U_{nit} = \beta X_{nit} + \varepsilon_{nit} \quad (1)$$

where β reflects the individual preference for each attribute and X_{nit} is the vector of attributes of the contract i , chosen by participant n on choice card t . ε_{nit} is assumed to be independent and identically distributed (IID) following a Gumble distribution. The probability of participant n choosing alternative i in choice t follows a conditional logit model (CL):

$$P(\text{choice}_{nt} = i) = \frac{\exp(\beta' X_{nit})}{\sum_{j=1}^J \exp(\beta' X_{nit})} \quad (2)$$

The conditional logit model implies that the standard deviation of unobserved utility is the same for all participants, meaning there is no preference heterogeneity (Scarpa & Alberini, 2005; Train & Weeks, 2005; Vaissière et al., 2018). It also implies independence of irrelevant alternatives (IIA), an assumption that can be tested using the Hausman test. It compares estimations of the full CL model with partial models each time one alternative is dropped (Vaissière et al., 2018). If the assumption of IIA does not hold, or heterogeneous preferences need to be assumed, the Mixed Logit Model (MXL) accounts for individual variation, allowing for unobserved heterogeneity

in estimated parameters (Canessa et al., 2023). The probability of participant n choosing alternative i in choice t , conditional on the individual coefficient vector β_n is:

$$P(\text{choice}_{nt} = i/\beta_n) = \frac{\exp(\beta_n' X_{nit})}{\sum_{j=1}^J \exp(\beta_n' X_{nit})} \quad (3)$$

To calculate the marginal willingness to pay/accept (WTP/WTA) of consumers or farmers for different contract attributes, coefficients of the Logit Model are used:

$$WTP = -\frac{\beta_{\text{attribute}}}{\beta_{\text{payment}}} \quad (4)$$

where $\beta_{\text{attribute}}$ is the parameter associated with attribute x and β_{payment} is associated with the payment attribute. WTP (or WTA, respectively) is the ratio of the attribute and the price coefficient.

4. Results – Country-specific analyses

4.1 Germany: Carbon Farming (TUM)

4.1.1 Introduction

As previously described McDonald et al. (2021), four distinct models for supporting soil health friendly practices. This first study in Germany, focuses on the first three approaches, i.e., an AECS type business model, a value chain model and a GHG certificate model involving payments for practices that enhance SOC, with the associated certificates being sold via an intermediary.

Farmers voluntarily participate in these business models, making their acceptance one of the most important success factors. Therefore, numerous other studies, in addition to McDonald et al. (2021), have investigated farmers' acceptance of these business models. Previous research has typically examined soil health business models in isolation, without reflecting real-world conditions where farmers must choose among multiple, competing incentive schemes, selecting only one to finance soil organic carbon (SOC) improvements. Under EU Regulation 2024/3012, which introduces the EU's first certification framework for permanent carbon removals, only practices that exceed legal and standard requirements qualify as additional and are eligible for certification (European Union, 2025). As a result, farmers cannot receive multiple payments for the same SOC-enhancing practice, reinforcing the need to choose a single, most suitable model (McDonald et al., 2021).

Contrary to previous studies, to directly compare different business models this study includes multiple SOC-promoting business models simultaneously. This provides a more realistic view of farmer decision-making under exclusivity constraints and additionality requirements.

To fully assess the potential of these models, both producer and consumer perspectives are essential. Since consumers also have discretion in how they offset emissions, this study employs two discrete choice experiments: one with farmers to assess preferences for SOC remuneration models, and one with consumers to gauge preferences for CO₂ offsetting options. By estimating farmers' willingness to accept (WTA) and consumers' willingness to pay (WTP), the study evaluates the market potential of three business models and common contract attributes.

The research aims to:

1. Identify farmers' preferences for SOC remuneration model design.

2. Assess consumer preferences for CO₂ offset models.
3. Integrate both perspectives to evaluate the overall market potential of different models.

From this, policy recommendations can be derived to promote business models with the highest acceptance and impact.

Case study description

CO₂-Land is a non-profit initiative founded in 2021 that promotes regional partnerships between farmers, businesses, and municipalities in southwestern Germany. Its goal is to sequester atmospheric CO₂ in agricultural soils through soil-organic-carbon (SOC) - building farming practices, while simultaneously enhancing soil fertility, water retention, and biodiversity. The initiative has developed its own standard for calculating and certifying CO₂ storage based on ISO guidelines, allowing farmers to receive compensation for each additional ton of carbon stored, financed through the voluntary purchase of **CO₂ certificates** by companies and local governments. Soil management practices include cover cropping, diversified crop rotations, organic fertilization, and reduced tillage, all of which contribute to building organic carbon sinks in the soil. These practices are documented and validated through soil sampling and ISO-standard monitoring. Through regional climate partnerships, CO₂-Land encourages active participation from all stakeholders and aims to establish a scalable model for agricultural carbon sinks.

4.1.2 Literature review

In this section, we examine key success factors for farmer adoption identified by the literature. One of the most critical elements is the payment mechanism. The primary distinction among the three business models lies in how payments are structured: carbon market schemes typically rely on hybrid or results-based payments, whereas AECS and value chain models may also include fixed payments. Notably, the European Union strongly favours results-based approaches, viewing them as more efficient and performance-oriented (McDonald et al., 2021).

Contract duration is another pivotal factor, particularly for long-term goals like carbon sequestration, which require sustained commitment. However, studies show that most farmers prefer shorter contracts, often favouring five-year terms due to concerns about flexibility and long-term obligations (McDonald et al., 2021). Incorporating mechanisms such as inflation adjustments or adaptive terms may improve the attractiveness of longer-term agreements.

Farmers also show highly differentiated preferences for specific soil health practices. Many opt for low-cost measures such as leaving straw residues or conservation tillage, while more capital-intensive options like afforestation or biochar application are frequently rejected. Willingness to accept compensation varies not only by practice but also by regional context and implementation costs (D2.2).

4.1.3 Methodology

4.1.3.1 Attribute selection, design, and implementation of the DCE

To understand the preferences of farmers and consumers, two approximately equal discrete choice experiments (DCEs) were conducted with 366 farmers and 959 consumers in Germany. Data collection was carried out via online surveys during the end of 2024. For the farmer survey, a link to the questionnaire was posted on a service portal where farmers apply for direct payments and agri-environmental-climate schemes. Consumer data was collected through a market research company.

The study focuses on remuneration models aimed at increasing soil organic carbon (SOC) content, which sequesters CO₂ and plays a vital role in enhancing soil health. For farmers, this necessitates adapting their management practices to meet these environmental goals. However, such adaptations typically entail additional costs, potential revenue loss, and increased workload. Given that farmers are already accustomed to compensation for opportunity costs through various AECS, this survey examined how they believe the additional efforts involved in soil and climate-friendly farming should be remunerated.

A remuneration model in this context consists of four attributes. The levels for these attributes were developed based on an extensive review of the literature and an analysis of existing business models (Table 1).

TABLE 1. DCE ATTRIBUTES AND LEVELS

Attribute	Levels
Type of business model	AECS, Carbon farming, Value chain
Contract duration	1, 5, 10, 20 Years
Monitoring (Probability of reaching goals)	Action-based (Low), Hybrid (Medium), Result-based (High)
Payment	30, 60, 90, 120, 150 €

- Type of the business model

The three types of business models investigated in this study are land management practice payments (agri-environmental measures), GHG certificates, and value chain (CO₂ label) business models. For the farmer, these business models differ regarding contract partners, required performance, and risk.

For the consumer survey, the type of business model was described from the consumer's point of view. AECS, therefore, means that a kind of CO₂ tax is levied, the GHG certificate model allows certificates to be purchased, and the value chain approach allows consumers to offset their CO₂ consumption by buying certified food.

- Contract duration

The duration of the contracts is specified in years and is a critical factor for the effectiveness of a business model, as sequestered carbon can be easily released again through intensification practices. For instance, a contract duration of 5 years requires the implementation of selected methods to increase soil organic carbon (SOC), such as conservation sowing techniques and winter greening integrated into crop rotation, to be maintained throughout this period. For consumers, this entails an obligation to make annual payments over the entire duration of the contract. The attribute levels range from 1 year (basic) to 5 and 10 years, which correspond to the standard durations of AECS and carbon farming initiatives, respectively. Lastly, a 20-year duration represents a desirable long-term target, offering greater sustainability and carbon sequestration stability.

- Monitoring

Farmers in AECS and value chains are usually rewarded for carrying out certain practices in an action-based manner (McDonald et al. 2021). Recently, there have also been result-based measures. Carbon farming initiatives are usually result-based or hybrid, i.e. a mix of a fixed payment at the beginning of the contract and a result-based payment at the end of the contract period, based on soil sample results. For consumers, the attribute was framed as 'certainty of target achievement' (i.e., CO₂ storage in the soil). The levels were called 'Low' (action-based), 'Medium' (hybrid), and High ('result-based').

- Payment

Payment is stated in euros per ton of CO₂.

We generated a Bayesian efficient experimental design optimized for mean D-efficiency (Scarpa & Rose, 2008) using STATA15 in both surveys. The design concluded on 18 choice cards separated into three blocks (Figure 1). Each participant was randomly assigned to one block and answered six choice cards, where they could choose between two contract options or the option not to participate.

CC 1.2	Option 1	Option 2	Keine Maßnahme
Geschäftsmodell Subventionsgeber Bezahlung: Durchführung Maßnahme Vertragspartner: Staat			
Dauer der Maßnahme 	1 Jahr	10 Jahre	Keine Maßnahme
Überwachung 			
Prämienhöhe 	60€ pro Tonne CO ₂ (Eine Tonne entspricht z.B. 2 ha konserv. Saat oder 1 ha Winterzwischenfrucht)	120€ pro Tonne CO ₂ (Eine Tonne entspricht z.B. 2 ha konserv. Saat oder 1 ha Winterzwischenfrucht)	

FIGURE 1. CHOICE CARD FOR FARMERS

Consumers who chose one of the two contract options were asked how many tons of CO₂ they would purchase annually under this model. Farmers were asked which SOC-improving practices they would implement and to what extent (hectares). In this way, carbon sequestration and, thus, also CO₂ storage can be calculated for the farmer.

In addition to the choice experiment, the consumer questionnaire included socio-demographic questions and questions on beliefs and attitudes toward climate change. Farmers were asked about farm characteristics, socio-demographic aspects, and current implementation and attitudes towards soil health practices and incentives.

Farmers and consumers were informed of political goals such as climate neutrality or preserving and improving soil health at the beginning of the survey. Consumers were

made aware of the option of offsetting their CO₂ emissions, which average 10.3 tons of CO₂ equivalent per person in Germany (Umweltbundesamt, 2025b).

4.1.3.2 Econometric estimation

At the beginning of the data analysis, we estimated a conditional logit model. The significant Hausman test indicated that the hypothesis of independence of irrelevant alternatives did not hold, and consequently we estimated a mixed logit model, allowing for different preferences of individual study participants. For both farmers and consumers, the model that best represented the data was identified using the quality criteria log-likelihood value, AIC, and BIC. In both cases, the payment attribute followed a log-normal distribution to restrict the price coefficient to be always positive, while all other attributes were included as random variables specified to be normally distributed.

In addition to the general preferences of the study participants, we wanted to analyse in more detail which business models have the greatest market potential. To this end, a market for the respective business model was simulated using a supply and demand curve. The supply and demand curves represent the amount of CO₂ stored or purchased at a certain price.

The willingness to pay of consumers and the willingness to accept of farmers are determined by the negative ratio of the attribute and price coefficients.

To depict a supply and demand curve, the individual WTP / WTA is calculated using the individual participant coefficients of the mixed logit model. For each desired scenario, we calculate the individual WTP / WTA as the sum of the WTP / WTA estimates for attribute *x* multiplied by the individual level of the respective variable. Dummy variables have either 0 or 1 in the equation, depending on whether the attribute level applies. Thus,

$$WTP_n \text{ or } WTA_n = \sum_{i=1}^I WTP_i \text{ or } WTA_i * \Delta x_{ij}$$

where *n* = individual consumer or producer; *x* = attribute levels (*i* = 1, ..., *I*); and *j* = scenario (basic, improved, optimum). As a result, we obtain WTA for each farmer in each scenario or individual WTP for the consumers, respectively.

To this end, three scenarios were first defined for each business model in which the market will be mapped. The three business models are mapped in their current form in the 'basic' scenario. For AECS, this is a contract term of 5 years with action-based monitoring. An improved but still realistically implementable business model is designed in the 'improved' scenario. For AECS, this could mean switching from action-

based to results-based programs. In the 'optimum' scenario, all attribute levels are set to the most effective level for SOC content, i.e., results-based monitoring with a contract term of 20 years. Like AECS, value chain approaches have so far been mostly action-based. An exit from label programs like organic farming is usually possible anytime.

The 'basic' scenario for the GHG certificate model was illustrated based on an existing German carbon farming initiative (Table 2). This initiative is a non-profit association that promotes climate protection and soil fertility in agriculture with the help of SOC increase. Farmers carry out SOC-increasing practices for 10 years. Farmers already receive annual payments based on the expected value during the 10 years, while after 10 years, the actual SOC increase is honoured through soil samples.

TABLE 2. MARKET POTENTIAL SCENARIOS

Business Model	Scenario	Contract duration	Monitoring
AECS	Basic	5	Action Based
AECS	Improved	5	Result Based
AECS	Optimum	20	Result Based
GHG certificates	Basic	10	Hybrid
GHG certificates	Improved	10	Result Based
GHG certificates	Optimum	20	Result Based
Value chain	Basic	1	Action Based
Value chain	Improved	5	Result Based
Value chain	Optimum	20	Result Based

To simulate the German market, farmers and consumers are scaled up to the German population. As the market product under consideration is CO₂ storage, the agricultural area is ultimately decisive for the amount of carbon sequestered. Therefore, we have decided to scale farmers up based on area rather than the number of farmers. The 366 farmers in the sample cultivate a total of 15,888 hectares of arable land, corresponding to an average arable area of 43.4 ha. This corresponds to 0.136% of arable land in Germany. The CO₂ sequestration of a farmer is therefore multiplied by 736 (the reciprocal of 0.136%). 959 consumers correspond to 0.00114% of the German population, which means that one study participant represents 87,069 consumers.

4.1.3.3 Descriptive statistics

Table 3 shows farm and farmer characteristics of the 366 farmers in the study compared to the German average.

TABLE 3. FARM CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SAMPLE

Variables	Sample	Germany
Average farm size (ha)	59.78	66 ^e
Farm size by classes (%)		
<10 ha	8.20	25.3
10-19.9 ha	15.03	19.7
20-49.9 ha	30.05	22.9
50-99.9 ha	26.23	16.7
>= 100 ha	20.49	15.4
Average arable area (ha)	43.41	45.8 ^f
Share of rented land (%)	43.32	
Full-time farms (%)	47,54	52.8 ^g
Organic farms (%)	30,87	11.4 ^h
Production type ^{d)}		
Cash crop	74.59	
Forage	54.64	
Permanent crops	8.47	
Horticulture	1.09	
Dairy	22.40	
Age by classes (%)		
<55 years	70,22	61 ⁱ
>=55 years	29.78	39 ⁱ
Agricultural education (%)	77.05	85 ⁱ

e) BMEL-Statistik: Betriebsstruktur und Entwicklung landwirtschaftlicher Betriebe

f) BMEL-Statistik: Bodennutzung in Deutschland

g) Studie zum Nebenerwerb in der Landwirtschaft: So ist die Lage - Bauernzeitung

h) BMEL-Statistik: Ökologischer Landbau

i) BMEL - Agrarsozialpolitik - Studie zum Arbeitsmarkt Landwirtschaft in Deutschland

The sample is representative regarding the average farm size in Germany and the average arable area. The proportion of full-time and part-time farmers is also close to the German average. Organic farms are slightly overrepresented. This is presumably due to the higher interest of organic farmers in environmental and climate aspects. Farm managers in the survey are slightly younger than the German average.

959 consumers successfully participated in the consumer survey. The sample is representative regarding gender, age, education, and household income. The place of living is also representative (Table 4).

TABLE 4. CONSUMER CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SAMPLE

Variable	Sample	Germany
Male (%) ^{a)}	55.63	49.4
Age (%) ^{b)}		
18-24	3.75	9.9
25-39	24.17	26.6
40-59	42.23	37.3
60-64	11.92	10.5
>65	17.88	15.7
Education (%) ^{c)}		
No degree	0.99	5.12
Low degree	21.19	23.47
Medium degree	34.66	30.23
High degree	43.16	37.58
Household Income (%) ^{d)}		
<1250	14.46	13.0
1250 – 2500	28.37	30.9
<1250	14.46	13.0
1250 – 2500	28.37	30.9
2500 – 3500	21.19	19.0
3500 – 5000	21.19	18.9
>5000	15.78	18.2
Place of Living ^{e)}		
Rural area (<5000)	19	13.55
Small town (- 20000)	22	26.55
Medium town (-100000)	21	27.59
Big city (-500000)	19	14.71
Metropole (>500000)	20	17.52

4.1.4 Results

4.1.4.1 Farmer preferences

Farmers have a higher utility if they do not participate in any of the three business models (Table 5). If they decide to join a business model, AECS is favoured over a GHG certificates model and the value chain. The shorter the commitment period, the greater the utility for the farmer and the greater the willingness to participate. The discrete choice experiment shows that the willingness to accept (WTA) increases significantly more for contract durations between 5 and 10 years, while the increase decreases significantly between 10 and 20 years. This indicates a non-linear relationship in which the growth rate of the WTA is higher in the shorter contract periods and weakens in longer terms. In terms of monitoring, farmers favour action-based monitoring over hybrid and result-based monitoring.

TABLE 5. MIXED LOGIT MODEL TO EXPLAIN FARMER'S DECISION FOR A BUSINESS MODEL CONTRACT.

Contract attributes	Coef.	SD. Error	S.D.	S.D. Error	Mean WTA
AECS	-0.332*	(0.193)	1.705***	(0.169)	19.07
Carbon farming	-1.556***	(0.222)	1.464***	(0.183)	89.41
Value chain	-1.623***	(0.210)	1.361***	(0.200)	93.21
5 years	-0.401***	(0.137)	0.342	(0.267)	23.04
10 years	-1.278***	(0.143)	-0.282	(0.293)	73.44
20 years	-2.073***	(0.199)	1.368***	(0.237)	119.08
Hybrid	-0.332***	(0.122)	0.814***	(0.244)	19.06
Result based	-0.927***	(0.142)	1.192***	(0.191)	53.28
Payment	0.015***	(0.166)	0.015***	(0.105)	
Obs.	6,588				

Standard errors in parentheses.

* p<0.10, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.01

After the farmers answered the choice cards, they were asked how often they included the individual attributes in their decision. If they had taken an attribute into account frequently, they were asked about the preferred expression of this attribute. 62% of farmers stated that they often or always take the type of business model into account in their decision. Of these, just under 60% preferred agri-environmental measures, 23% were in favour of value chains, and only 17% were in favour of a GHG certificate model.

4.1.4.2 Consumer acceptance

In addition to the Choice Model attributes, two interaction terms were added with the ASC (opt-out option) (Table 6). Firstly, the survey included a treatment in which around half of the consumers surveyed received additional information on SOC sequestration in the soil. In addition to the re-emphasized positive effect of CO₂ storage on the environment, the information increasingly referred to the need to maintain practices and business models. Consumers were informed that renewed intensive cultivation methods could quickly reverse the effects of CO₂ storage and that permanence and, thus, long-term contracts are important. The second interaction term relates to whether the respondent cares what others think of them.

TABLE 6. MIXED LOGIT MODEL TO EXPLAIN CONSUMERS' DECISION FOR A BUSINESS MODEL CONTRACT.

Contract attributes	Coef.	SD. Error	S.D.	S.D. Error	Mean WTA
A ECS	1.256***	(0.133)	0.473***	(0.149)	4.46
Carbon farming	1.120***	(0.133)	0.037	(0.162)	3.97
Value chain	1.267***	(0.129)	0.451***	(0.158)	4.50
5 years	-0.081	(0.068)	0.176	(0.233)	-0.28
10 years	-0.238***	(0.079)	0.346**	(0.142)	-0.84
20 years	-0.568***	(0.089)	-0.803***	(0.142)	-2.02
Hybrid	0.548***	(0.060)	0.045	(0.135)	1.95
Result based	1.154***	(0.073)	0.797***	(0.103)	4.10
Payment	0.283***	(0.093)	0.643***	(0.149)	
ASC* treatment	-0.042	(0.166)	-1.216***	(0.153)	
ASC* opinion	-1.328***	(0.227)	1.208***	(0.292)	
Obs.	17,262				

Standard errors in parentheses.

* p<0.10, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.01

Overall, consumers' utility increases if they opt for one of the business models instead of the opt-out option, no matter the type of business model. While a contract term of 5 years shows no significant difference from the one-year basic level, consumers do not want to commit to payments for 10 or even 20 years. While the preference regarding contract duration aligns with that of farmers, the monitoring shows different results. Consumers prefer contracts with a certain target achievement, equivalent to result-based measures. While participants who care a lot about the opinion of others tend to opt for offsetting their emissions and against the opt-out option, the information treatment on permanence shows no significant influence.

4.1.5 Market potential estimation

Figure 2 shows the farmers' supply curve for different business models and scenarios scaled up to German arable land. For this purpose, the individual WTA of the farmers was determined for each scenario. The supply curve shows the potential CO₂ storage in the soil at a certain price for achieving one ton of CO₂ storage (for the farmer, one ton of CO₂ corresponds to approx. 270kg more SOC).

FIGURE 2. PROJECTED SUPPLY CURVES

Scenarios positioned further to the right on the curve indicate greater potential, as they enable higher levels of CO₂ storage at a constant price. In contrast, the 'optimum' scenario demonstrates the lowest potential across all three business models. This is primarily due to its combination of long contract durations and results-based monitoring, which lead to low farmer participation and a high willingness to accept (WTA).

Among the models, AECS exhibits strong potential, as it aligns well with farmer preferences. The value chain approach is also widely accepted, particularly in the basic scenario, where the commitment period is notably short. In contrast, the GHG certificate model shows the least potential. Its relatively low acceptance is driven by the requirement for results-based or hybrid monitoring and minimum contract durations of 10 years, both of which deter participation.

On the demand side, a consumer demand curve was generated using the same methodological approach, allowing for a direct comparison of supply and demand across business models.

FIGURE 3. PROJECTED DEMAND CURVES

Figure 3 illustrates that the type of business model is not a decisive factor for consumers. Instead, scenario design, particularly the duration of the payment obligation and the certainty of target achievement, strongly influences consumer acceptance and willingness to pay (WTP). The 'improved' scenario performs best, as it guarantees high target achievement through results-based monitoring. While the 'optimum' scenario also ensures strong environmental outcomes, its 20-year payment obligation significantly reduces its attractiveness to consumers, making it less favourable than the 'improved' scenario. Despite offering better environmental impact than the 'basic' scenario, the long-term financial commitment in the 'optimum' scenario lowers its perceived value.

To assess the overall potential of the different business models, we compare supply and demand by analysing the average willingness to accept (WTA) and willingness to pay (WTP) for each scenario, as shown in Table 7.

TABLE 7. MEAN WTP AND WTA

	Mean WTA		Mean WTP
AECS 1	108.30	<	156.54
AECS 2	174.80	<	286.68
AECS 3	302.89	>	232.52
Carbon farming 1	302.43	>	183.06
Carbon farming 2	354.19	>	250.21
Carbon farming 3	428.64	>	213.73
Value chain 1	158.24	<	166.90
Value chain 2	273.43	<	285.73
Value chain 3	427.93	>	230.70

Four of the nine scenarios demonstrate high market potential, where the average willingness to accept (WTA) from farmers is lower than the average willingness to pay (WTP) from consumers. This includes the 'basic' and 'improved' AECS scenarios, which stand out due to farmers' particularly low payment expectations. Similarly, the first two value chain scenarios show strong potential, driven by short contract durations, which lead to both high consumer WTP and low farmer WTA. In contrast, the 'optimum' scenario consistently shows low potential, as neither farmers nor consumers are willing to commit to a 20-year obligation, be it in terms of land management or payments.

Across all three GHG certificate scenarios, the WTP from consumers remains stable but significantly below the farmers' WTA. This is largely due to the higher WTA among farmers, driven by two key factors: limited preference for this business model compared to AECS, and reluctance to engage in results-based contracts with durations of 10 years or more.

As a final step in the analysis, we want to present the supply and demand for each business model together to identify a market equilibrium (Figure 4). The graphs for all three business models show a surplus of demand. On average, in our survey each consumer was willing to purchase 2.4 tons of CO₂ per year (the highest 5% was removed as an outlier). Farmers showed an average CO₂ storage of 1.6 tons per ha per year based on the extent of SOC-enhancing practices. To meet consumer demand, approximately 1.5 hectares of arable land per head in the German population would be needed. However, with a total agricultural area of 16.7 million hectares and a population of 80.4 million people, this amounts to an average of only 0.2 hectares per inhabitant. Conversely, the market price for the market equilibrium is very high due to the high demand as stated by the consumers in our survey.

AECS

Carbon farming

Value chain

FIGURE 4. MARKET DIAGRAM FOR EACH BUSINESS MODEL.

4.1.6 Discussion

This study aimed to estimate the potential of different business models in comparison to each other by determining both producer and consumer preferences. The three business models investigated increase the soil's organic carbon content by storing CO₂ from the atmosphere. The business models thus serve both soil health and greenhouse gas reduction by rewarding farmers for the effort required to implement the necessary practices.

Farmers in our survey could choose between AECS (Agri-Environmental Climate Schemes), GHG certificates, value chain initiatives, or opt out of these measures entirely. In practice, many prefer not to participate at all, and if they do, they tend to favour AECS. This reluctance to engage in conservation schemes has been well documented (Greiner 2015; Hasler et al. 2019; Vaissière et al. 2018). A key reason behind this hesitation is the desire to maintain autonomy in farm management. Most farmers are resistant to additional restrictions, particularly given the already substantial bureaucratic burden associated with existing programs (Kuhfuss et al. 2016; Ruto and Garrod 2009). Flexibility is highly valued, and additional regulations are often perceived as an unwelcome constraint (Ruto and Garrod 2009; Ober et al. 2025).

When farmers do choose to engage in a business model that compensates them for building soil organic carbon (SOC), AECS are generally preferred. This preference likely stems from farmers' long-standing familiarity with AECS, which are well-established, offer secure payments, and are perceived as reliable (Lastra-Bravo et al. 2015). In contrast, newer models such as GHG certificates are often viewed with scepticism due to legal and pricing uncertainties (Raina et al. 2024; Dumbrell et al. 2016). The aversion to long-term contracts is also consistent across studies. Such contracts are seen as limiting farmers' ability to adapt to climatic or market fluctuations, thereby increasing perceived risk (Ruto and Garrod 2009; Lastra-Bravo et al. 2015; Figueredo 2024). Similarly, results-based monitoring is often considered riskier than action-based or hybrid approaches, further influencing farmers' participation preferences (Canessa et al. 2023; Burton and Schwarz 2013).

For consumers, the specific type of business model was rather unimportant, and they made little distinction between them. Instead, what mattered more were the duration of the payment obligation and the certainty of achieving climate-related targets. While consumers generally express interest in business models aimed at offsetting their CO₂ emissions, as supported by previous studies (Kragt et al. 2016), they are reluctant to commit to long-term financial obligations. In our study, consumers showed a clear preference for short-term engagements, rejecting payment commitments of 10 or even 20 years.

Moreover, when consumers do agree to make payments, they expect a guaranteed achievement of the stated environmental goals. Our findings also reinforce earlier research showing that individuals who place strong value on the opinions of their social circle are more likely to behave in environmentally conscious ways (Wuepper et al. 2019).

Interestingly, the provision of additional information on the value of carbon farming had no statistically significant effect on consumer preferences. This is likely due to the extensive background information provided to all participants prior to the treatment phase. Before the choice experiment, we offered detailed explanations on how carbon sequestration works and how the different business models are structured. This foundational knowledge likely ensured a high baseline level of understanding across participants, leaving limited room for the additional treatment to have a measurable impact.

For a business model to be viable, consumers' willingness to pay (WTP) must at least match producers' willingness to accept (WTA). When comparing average WTP and WTA across different scenarios, this condition was met in four out of nine cases, specifically, the 'basic' and 'improved' scenarios for both AECS and value chain models. The 'basic' scenarios represent current implementations. In the case of AECS, this typically involves five-year, action-based measures to enhance soil organic carbon (SOC), while value chain models generally offer greater flexibility and can often be terminated at any time (D2.2). However, permanence of SOC-enhancing practices is crucial; reverting to intensive practices can rapidly reduce SOC and release stored CO₂ (McDonald et al. 2021). For this reason, the 'basic' value chain scenario lacks ecological credibility. Similarly, action-based AECS can be inefficient, as they sometimes fail to provide additionality, i.e., farmers might undertake the same practices even in the absence of AECS, and the actual impact of measures is rarely verified (Burton and Schwarz 2013). Consequently, from an environmental standpoint, the basic AECS model is also not advisable.

A major step toward increasing the ecological and economic effectiveness of these business models would be transitioning to results-based payments. Such a shift would ensure that only verifiable carbon sequestration is rewarded, aligning with EU regulations on carbon credits, which mandate the quantification of carbon removals (EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation (EU/2024/3012); European Union, 2025). Additionally, adopting multi-year commitments for value chain models could further improve their environmental integrity. Thus, the improved AECS and value chain models are preferable not only from an environmental perspective but also economically, as the average WTP exceeds the average WTA.

In contrast, GHG certificate models are characterized by a high average WTA among farmers. This scepticism stems from a combination of unfavourable conditions: these models typically requires results-based, long-term contracts, coupled with uncertainties around CO₂ certificate market prices. Farmers are often hesitant to invest in the necessary technologies under these conditions, fearing that price volatility could undermine profitability (Han & Niles, 2023; Dumbrell et al., 2016). While a policy instrument such as a guaranteed minimum price could theoretically stabilize the market, it risks creating a supply surplus if the market price falls below the guaranteed level. In such a scenario, farmers might abandon SOC-building practices once contracts expire, leading to adverse long-term ecological effects. An alternative could be to treat the market price per ton of CO₂ as a performance-based incentive, while offering fixed payments to fully or partially cover the implementation costs of carbon farming. The feasibility and acceptance of such hybrid models should be explored in future research.

The supply and demand curves analysis shows a significantly stronger demand than supply for CO₂ sequestration. This results from an average CO₂ sequestration supply of 1.6 tons per hectare per year, which puts the available supply well below consumer demand. In order to increase greenhouse gas emission offset, farmers should ideally sequester more organic carbon and thus increase CO₂ storage. There are two ways to embrace carbon sequestration in the future. Firstly, 15% of participating farmers in all choice cards have chosen the opt-out option. Future efforts should aim to attract these farmers to SOC practices, with clearly defined requirements, targeted advice, and stable prices as effective starting points. Secondly, the focus should be less on soil health measures on mineral soils and more on afforestation or agroforestry systems and peatland rewetting, as these approaches offer greater sequestration potential (McDonald et al. 2021). Agroforestry systems are applicable for all landowners and long-term by nature, while peatland rewetting is only possible in a limited area but is highly effective (McDonald et al. 2021).

4.2 Germany: AgoraNatura (ZALF)

4.2.1 Context

Improving soil health and biodiversity on agricultural land within the European Union, as envisioned by the EU Soil Strategy for 2030 and the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, necessitates addressing the current funding shortfall through enhanced private sector engagement. Despite this need, the potential of private consumer investment remains underutilized, owing in part to a scarcity of appealing investment vehicles and inadequately structured incentive mechanisms. To this end, our study explores the potential of private consumer investment for soil health and biodiversity improvements in agriculture. Moreover, we make use of an online marketplace for nature conservation projects – [AgoraNatura](#) – investigating the potential of such business models to bridge the current funding gap.

Case study – AgoraNatura

AgoraNatura is Germany's first online marketplace for nature conservation projects in agriculture. Here, farmers are able to offer voluntary nature conservation projects and have them remunerated through interested donors (such as private citizens or private companies). For farmers, this means that they can develop their own project ideas and have them financed by interested donors **through selling project certificates**. The specific design of the projects, as well as the amount of remuneration, are determined by the farmers. Moreover, the projects are certified by experts according to the criteria of the "[NaturPlus-Standard](#)".

4.2.2 Methodology

We conducted a Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) with 1,627 German residents capturing their stated preferences – measured in willingness to pay (WTP) – to explore the market potential of nature conservation certificates aimed at improving soil health and biodiversity on agricultural landscapes. Moreover, these certificates were characterized by two crucial concepts:

- Bundling: A mechanism where several environmental improvements are combined in one single certificate. In this case soil health and biodiversity improvements.
- Blending: A mechanism where public investments are mixed with private investments to leverage or 'trigger' private investment.

With regards to bundling we selected three individual soil services for improvement: 1) pest control, 2) erosion control, and 3) soil-carbon storage. Moreover, we selected three individual biodiversity indicators for improvement: 1) animal diversity, 2) plant diversity, and 3) pollination. A nature conservation certificate was then characterised

by a single improvement of either soil health or biodiversity or a combination of respective improvements.

Concerning blending we chose four different levels of public funding which each certificate may receive: 0%, 15%, 30% or 45%.

Ultimately, we applied two different models to analyse private consumer WTP. A mixed-logit model in WTP-space as well as a latent class model in WTP-space.

4.2.3 Results

Bundling

Across our sample (mixed-logit model) we find positive mean WTP for all attributes and a strong negative mean WTP for the status-quo. **This implies private consumers in our sample show support for the presented nature conservation projects and are willing to invest into respective certificates.**

With respect to individual soil health improvements, we observe positive mean WTP between approx. €41-47. Looking at soil health improvement bundles, the combination of all three soil health improvements leads to the highest mean WTP (approx. €74/certificate).

Regarding individual biodiversity improvements, we find that consumers are willing to pay approx. an additional €38–55 per certificate. Similar to soil health improvements, the highest average WTP is observed for the bundle of all three improvements (€80/certificate).

Consumer preferences exhibit segment-based heterogeneity, with four distinct classes identified. *Class 1* (39%) – likely to be younger and environmentally conscious consumers – shows the highest mean WTP across all bundled soil health and biodiversity improvements. *Class 2* (13%), more likely to be older and less educated male respondents, prefers the status quo but still values certain biodiversity bundles. *Class 3* (28%) supports improvements but lacks price sensitivity, leading to insignificant WTP estimates. *Class 4* (20%) values bundled soil health and biodiversity improvements but is highly price-sensitive, resulting in lower WTP overall.

Blending

We observe that respondents positively value increased public funding for nature conservation projects, implying that public funding may leverage or trigger increased private consumer investment. However, across our sample the increase in public funding only has a marginal positive effect on mean WTP: €13.2/certificate at 15%, €14.8/certificate at 30%, and €15.9/certificate at 45% public funding. However, we find

that for younger and environmentally conscious as well as price sensitive consumers mean WTP for public funding peaks at 30%. The class-weighted mean WTP of our latent class model supports these observations.

4.3.4 Market potential estimation

Our research offers empirical insights into WTP of German residents for improvements in soil health and biodiversity. The results indicate considerable market potential for soil health and biodiversity certificates, thereby supporting public commitments under the EU Soil Strategy for 2030 and the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030. Furthermore, we find that combining improvements in both soil health and biodiversity substantially increases average mean WTP. Nevertheless, preference heterogeneity across consumer segments highlights the importance of designing targeted policy tools. Our findings also suggest that mixing public and private investments (blending) may enhance consumer investment, although public contributions exceeding 30% per project could reduce private engagement due to potential crowding-out effects. Therefore, such funding mechanisms should be developed with caution to incentivise participation. Lastly, online marketplaces for nature conservation certificates such as AgoraNatura may serve as effective channels to support such investment flows. While the findings are robust, limitations of stated preference methods, such as DCEs, persist. Future studies could incorporate real-world data and observed behaviours to improve the development of innovative funding approaches aligned with EU goals for soil health and agri-environmental policy.

4.3 Netherlands: Carbon credits (WU)

4.3.1 Introduction

Under a neoclassical perspective, it would be expected that farmers provide public goods, such as carbon sequestration or biodiversity, when the provision helps them to maximise their profits by receiving additional payments over the incentive mechanisms (Whitby, 1994; Davies & Hodge, 2007). However, it is known that farmers adjust farm management for other reasons as well. This study seeks to explore how farmers respond to the expectation to store CO₂ on farmland, how they perceive different incentive mechanisms, and which beliefs explain their perceptions. It presents the results from a Q-Methodology experiment. Q-Methodology combines quantitative and qualitative techniques. These experiments were already used, in example, by Davies & Hodge (2007), Braitio et al. (2020). Davies and Hodge (2007) analyse how farmers perceive their roles in relation to environmental management, for instance, their responsibility to provide public goods. Braitio et al. (2020) determine farmers' views on soil management and influential factors for their soil-management decisions. Both find that economic aspects are not equally important to all farmers.

The experiment first informed farmers about potential soil health practices that potentially lead to carbon sequestration, the standards that need to be fulfilled for EU-certified carbon credits, and the underlying requirements for AES and private contracts with actors of the food value chain. Next, the participants were asked to order 36 statements in a so-called Q-sorting grid that reflected to which extent farmers agreed or disagreed with the individual statements. The statements referred to farmers' management decisions, their attitudes towards environmental protection, the three analysed incentive models. The results are expected to be of interest to politicians as they allow them to identify which incentives might need to be offered alone or in combination to achieve better soil health and carbon sequestration.

The subsections after the following case study description are structured as follows. First, the three main incentive mechanisms and their underlying legislative frameworks are summarised (Section 2). In section 3, the Q-Methodology and the setup of the experiment for the analysed context are described. The results are presented in section 4, before they are critically discussed in section 5.

Case study description

Rabo Carbon Bank is a private initiative by Rabobank that remunerates farmers for the implementation of sustainable soil management practices. Sustainable soil management practices enhance soil health while sequestering carbon in soils. The sequestered carbon amounts are then quantified and traded as carbon credits. Besides organising the trade of carbon credits, the bank advises farmers on

sustainable soil management practices and connects them with large companies (e.g. outside the agribusiness sector) that seek to buy carbon credits to offset parts of their CO₂ emissions.

Even though the Dutch case study is on **carbon credit trade** only, the NOVASOIL project focuses on two additional business models: These are **public payments** (e.g. for agri-environmental schemes or eco-schemes), and payments over the food **value chain**, where farmers receive a price premium on products produced with more sustainable practices.

The Q-methodology experiment conducted for work package 2 seeks to provide deeper insights into why farmers choose to implement soil health promoting practices, and provides information on farmer' evaluation of the three business models. Preliminary results of the Dutch experiment are presented in the following part.

4.3.2 Analysed incentives

This article analyses farmers' viewpoints on how to best promote soil health practices that potentially lead to carbon sequestration on farmland. The respondents received information on the incentives analysed. Three incentives were considered in the experiment: public payments for ecosystem services, payments through the value chain, where farmers receive an additional payment for a product that also fulfils certain environmental requirements, and carbon markets that organise the trade of carbon credits. Carbon credits are certified 'carbon removal units', where one unit represents one tonne of certified net carbon removal (McDonald et al., 2021).

First, the participants received the information that carbon farming describes all activities where farmers and land users deliver the following outcomes: carbon removal and storage of carbon in biomass or soils, the avoidance of future CO₂ and Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions or the reduction of existing CO₂ and GHG emissions. Examples of carbon farming practices include i. afforestation and reforestation, ii. agroforestry and other forms of mixed farming (e.g. silvopasture), iii. soil health measures on arable land (for instance, reduced tillage, cover crops, improved fertilizer planning, arable land conversion to grassland), iv. the rewetting and restoration of peatlands (McDonald et al., 2021). Therefore, carbon farming refers to actions for carbon sequestration and not to a certain incentive mechanism, even though initiatives for carbon credit trade often state to perform carbon farming. Next, the participants received information on the incentives.

4.3.2.1 Public payments

Public funding for environmentally friendly farm management can be granted over the CAP. Payments for ecosystem services can either be financed through Pillar i) the European Agriculture Guarantee Fund (EAGF) or Pillar ii) the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD). These two funding pillars lead to payment schemes with different characteristics. Payments granted over the first pillar are, for example, annual, while payments granted over the second pillar are multi-annual. In addition, the second pillar payments are co-financed by the member states (European Commission, 2023a).

Farmers must comply with certain conditions to receive payments from the first and second pillar. The so-called 'enhanced conditionality' consists of statutory management requirements that aim at sustainable farming. Farmers receive direct payments from the first pillar for these measures. The measures of the 'enhanced conditionality' aim at good agricultural and environmental conditions (GAEC) (European Commission, 2023a).

Schemes for the climate, the environment, and animal welfare (Eco-schemes) are new tools to deliver the goals set by the European Commission. Practices can only qualify to become eco-schemes when they require management adjustments that go beyond the legislative requirements, and the enhanced conditionality (European Commission, 2023a). In the Netherlands, eco-schemes are implemented using a result-based point system. In the Dutch system, each activity converts into eco-points. They reflect the activities' impact on different environmental objectives (climate, air and soil, water, landscape, biodiversity). The eco-points translate into hectare payments when farmers achieve enough points in total. Farmers can either use one eco-scheme with a high impact or multiple ones with lower ambitions to reach an entry level threshold and to qualify for a payment for all hectares of the farm. If they want to achieve higher payments, multiple measures referring to different objectives need to be combined to reach higher thresholds. There are three threshold levels: bronze (€ 60/ha for all hectares of the farm), silver (€ 100/ha for all hectares of the farm) and gold (€ 200/ha for all hectares of the farm) (Jongeneel & Gonzalez-Martinez, 2023).

Eco-schemes provide incentives for softer management restrictions, while other, more demanding measures are financed from the second pillar of the CAP. These measures include agri-environment-climate commitments, forest-environment-climate commitments, agroforestry, afforestation, and the conversion to and maintenance of organic farming, referred to as agri-environmental schemes (AES) in this study (European Commission, 2023a). Measures financed over the second pillar are multi-annual as the environmental goals require longer and more complex engagement (Guyomard et al., 2023). The contracts usually cover five years (European Commission,

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2023a). The Netherlands chose a collective implementation approach. Since 2016, farmer collectives have been responsible for the implementation of AES. The approach is believed to motivate farmers, to enhance the special coordination of measures (Barghusen et al., 2021).

4.3.2.2 Carbon markets for EU-certified carbon credits

Overall, certified carbon credits should meet the so-called QU.A.L.I.T.Y criteria. QU.A.L.I.T.Y stands for the four requirements the removals need to fulfil to allow certification. In brief, the removals need to be **quantified** in an accurate and robust way, they should generate a net carbon removal benefit that is **additional** (at least above the existing legal requirements), they should ensure **long-term storage of carbon** and have a neutral impact or even a co-benefit for other **sustainability** objectives (European Commission, 2024).

For the first criterion, the following is lined out: Carbon removals must be **quantified** in a manner that is relevant, accurate, complete, consistent, and comparable. Third-party auditing plays a crucial role in ensuring the credibility and reliability of carbon removals. To quantify the net carbon removal benefit, a two-step process is followed. First, the gross amount of additional carbon removals generated by a carbon removal activity compared to a baseline is calculated, utilizing standardized baselines. These baselines reflect the typical performance of similar activities in comparable social, economic, environmental, technological, and geographical contexts, aiming for objectivity, minimal compliance costs, and recognition of early movers. Second, any increase in greenhouse gas emissions associated with the implementation of the carbon removal activity is deducted. These emissions may arise from increased use of fertilizers, chemicals, fuel, energy, or changes in practices (European Commission, 2024).

For the second criterion **additionality**, the following needs to consider: The activities need to exceed statutory requirements, ensuring that operators undertake actions not mandated by law. Therefore, the standardized baseline for farmers should reflect the carbon emissions of farms complying with existing legislative frameworks (European Commission, 2024). Given that almost all farmers receive CAP payments the enhanced conditionality requirements of the CAP most likely also need to be exceeded.

Long-term storage means that ideally, carbon storage should be permanent. This is defined as centuries long and might be achieved through methods like geological storage or carbon mineralization. However, different carbon removal activities vary in processes, storage mediums, and timescales. Carbon farming on arable land, peatland rewetting or afforestation is considered to rather lead to removals spanning decades (European Commission, 2024).

The last criterion is sustainability. It is described that carbon farming should not only mitigate climate change but also offer co-benefits for **sustainability**, necessitating the introduction of minimum sustainability requirements. The requirements will ensure that carbon removal activities have a neutral or positive impact on other sustainability objectives such as biodiversity, water and marine resource protection. More concretely the requirements will disqualify practices like afforestation with monocultures that harm biodiversity from certification (European Commission, 2024).

The key carbon farming methods include afforestation, reforestation, agroforestry, and soil health measures like peatland rewetting (McDonald et al., 2021). Peatlands, comprising 34% of agricultural emissions in the Netherlands (Norris et al., 2021). However, this can render them unsuitable for farming, prompting the exploration of alternatives (Wetlands International, 2023). Soil health measures, that might be favoured by farmers for allowing continued agricultural production, face challenges like reversibility. Despite ongoing quantification discussion for the EU-certified credits, peatland rewetting, afforestation, and agroforestry are determined to be the most promising options (COWI et al., 2021; McDonald et al., 2021), while soil health measures received critical evaluation (Buck & Palumbo-Compton, 2022; Paul et al., 2023).

4.3.2.3 Private initiatives of the food supply chain

Environmental protection contracts can also be between stakeholders of the food value chain (e.g., supermarkets or processors) and farmers. Harmanny & Schulp (2023) conducted a literature review and an online search for existing public and private funding schemes for environmental outcomes in the Netherlands. The authors show that more than 50% of the contracts are either completely private or funded by a combination of private and public funding. In general, contracts present binding agreements between two parties that can be natural or legislative entities (e.g., companies are legislative parties). They are usually based on national-specific frameworks and touch on multiple areas of law and provide the parties with a certain degree of legal certainty (Runge et al., 2022).

Value chain contracts for the provision of ecosystem services, which include environmental aspects, are often production contracts, where farmers agree to deliver a product that was produced under certain standards. Payments for environmental aspects are usually not granted separately but are granted via a higher product price. In addition to higher prices, farmers are often provided with a purchase guarantee for certain volumes of product. The downstream value chain actor (e.g., a supermarket) will usually cover the higher costs by selling the product at higher prices to consumers (Runge et al., 2022). To avoid consumers being misled in their purchase decisions, the EU seeks to ban greenwashing and unsupported claims. The use of claims such as 'eco-friendly', 'climate-neutral' or 'climate-friendly' will be forbidden from 2026 on

when companies cannot prove via approved certification schemes that their off-sets and biodiversity contributions are valid (European Parliament, 2023).

4.3.2.4 Mode of payment

Last, information on the mode of payment was included. Both AES and eco-schemes can either be action-based, result-based, or hybrid. Private payments over the value chain might also be. While carbon credits sold over carbon credit markets will lead to a result-based payments. Generally, a payment is considered action-based when it rewards the required measures (e.g., reduction of tillage, application of organic fertilisers only). The amount of payment is usually based on the average income forgone when implementing the practice (Runge et al., 2022). In contrast to this, a scheme is considered result-based when the reward is based on the achievement of a desired output (e.g., the tons of carbon stored per hectare). Since result-based schemes do not remunerate specific practices, farmers can usually choose the measures that they apply freely (Herzon et al., 2018). Action-based payments have the advantage of being easier to monitor compared to result-based schemes. Farmers may prefer this approach because it ensures payment. However, Bartkowski et al. (2021) and Burton & Schwarz (2013) argue that uniform payments across farmers and a lack of alignment with specific goals, such as carbon sequestration, lead to inefficiencies. Result-based schemes can enhance the effectiveness. Hybrid schemes seek to overcome the disadvantages of purely result-based and purely action-based schemes. In hybrid schemes, part of the payment is fixed and based on the measures applied. Hybrid schemes could, for instance, grant bonus payments when certain results are reached (Herzon et al., 2018).

4.3.3 Methodology

This section first describes the Q-Methodology, before providing a detailed description on how a Q-Methodology experiment was set-up for the analysed context.

4.3.3.1. Q-Methodology

Q-Methodology was developed by Stephenson (1953) and allows the analysis of subjectivity. The method seeks to identify common attitudes, perceptions, preferences, and feelings among groups of subjects. Q-Methodology experiments often work as follows. First, the participants receive relevant information for the analysed topic. Next, they are presented with statements (Q-sets) that reflect all possible viewpoints on the topic. In the following step, the respondents are asked to pre-sort the statements based on their level of agreement into three categories

(agreement, neutral perception, disagreement). Finally, they are asked to perform the final sorting exercise, where they are required to sort the statements in more detail into a grid (Q-sorting table). The grid usually takes a normal distribution, and the respondents are asked to place the statements based on their level of agreement (e.g., from strong disagreement to strong agreement that is expressed on a Likert Scale) (Sandling, 2024).

In the quantitative by-person factor analysis, similar Q-sorts (a Q sort is a finalised sorting exercise) are identified and clustered into groups – the factors. Each conducted Q-sort enters as a variable. The term by-person factor-analysis is used because each Q-sort represents one person's point of view. In the analysis, all Q-sorts enter a matrix holding the cross-correlations between the Q-sorts. Principal component or centroid factor analyses are then applied to identify the factors. A Q-sort (person) is loaded on a factor when the loading is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), the factor loading represents the correlation of the Q-sort and the factor. Each factor represents a group with similar views. Next, factor rotation is applied. The factor rotation aims at easy interpretable results, factor rotation affects the number of distinguishing statements and the number of Q-sort loaded on a factor. Last, factor scores are calculated per statement, they represent the average rating results. When statements are significantly differently evaluated, they are distinguishable. Statements that received similar scores across all factors are called consensus statements. Neutral statements are neither distinguishing nor consensus – they have factor scores indicating a neutral perception (Akhtar-Danesh, 2018). The presented estimation was conducted with the Stata packet q factor.

4.3.3.2 Statement Selection

The so-called Q-concourse is a collection of potential viewpoints of the topic. Webler et al. (2009) provide guidance on the selection of appropriate statements and advise that they should be: relevant, meaningful for the participants, easy to understand, and can have an excess meaning (can be interpreted in different ways). The concourse underlying the experiment is a ready-made concourse, meaning it is mostly based on a previously conducted literature review (Sandling, 2024). Out of the initial Q-concourse, 36 statements were included in the experiment. Recent Q-Methodology experiments with farmers used a similar number of statements, Davies & Hodge (2007) included 33 statements, Braitto et al. (2020) included 34 statements, and Norris et al. (2021) conducted an experiment with 37 statements.

The participants were informed that they should order the statement to provide information on the research question '*What motivates Dutch farmers to invest in soil*

health?'. The statements referred to different aspects of soil health, incentives for soil health measures, contracting details, and beliefs of farmers.

TABLE 8. STATEMENTS AND STATEMENT LABELS

No.	Translated statement	Label
1	Soil health practices can reliably increase soil organic carbon content in the long run.	long-term increase
2	Soil health practices are part of good farm management.	good farm management
3	The public should remunerate investments in soil health as they lead to public goods (e.g., improvements water quality, biodiversity)	multiple public goods
4	Soil health measures make my farm more resilient against climate change.	resilience climate change
5	Soil carbon content is of lower interest to me than soil structure, soil water holding capacity and lower soil erosion.	soil structure
6	I would be open to plant trees and rewetting of my peatlands to sequester carbon.	hard measures
7	Additional training and education are good enough to motivate me to implement additional soil health measures.	training & education
8	The whole food supply chain (farmers, producers, and consumers) needs to find solutions to finance additional soil health measures	solutions food supply chain
9	I would find carbon farming contracts more attractive when my successors would be able to leave the contract.	termination option
10	Long term contracts would become more attractive when the payments would be adjusted to inflation.	inflation
11	Contracts are more attractive if I can choose the measures, I would like to implement	choose measures
12	Short-term land tenure contracts make it difficult for me to invest in soil health.	short tenure
13	I can commit to contract with a longer runtime than 10 years.	long-term contracts
14	I would rather participate in carbon farming when the activities would be organised by farmers' groups (e.g., an agricultural collective)	farmers' groups
15	Farmers should cover the costs for soil sampling.	soil sampling costs
16	Result based payments should exclude farmers having high carbon contents in soils to promote additional action against climate change.	result-based
17	These costs of adjustments in farm management need to be compensated by payments for the measures.	action-based payments
18	The payments offered over the CAP (AES and eco-schemes) are high enough to set good financial incentives.	CAP good incentives
19	AES and eco-schemes are for hobby farmers and those on poor quality soils.	hobby farmers

20	I believe there will a viable carbon market in the future	CM attractive
21	It would be a good incentive when it would be allowed to combine payments from the CAP (AES and eco-schemes) and private payments (from the value chain or over carbon markets)	payment combination
22	Already existing initiatives for carbon farming (in example by Rabobank and ZLTO) will lose their participants when they will aim to tighten their requirements to fulfil the EU certification guidelines.	existing initiatives
23	Carbon markets for EU certified carbon credit are too risky.	CM risky
24	Hybrid payments - that are partly cover the costs of the measures and are partly based on outcomes (sequestered amounts) - are fair	hybrid payments
25	Next to voluntary initiatives (Eco-schemes, AES, value chain or carbon credit trade) the legislative framework needs to be tightened.	legislation
26	High competition does not allow me to implement additional soil health practices.	high competition
27	When I compare myself to nearby farmers – I am always open for new business models.	entrepreneurial
28	To state that CO ₂ emissions are lowered by soil health practices is greenwashing.	greenwashing
29	Productivity is not my main priority when I decide about farm management	productivity
30	Farmers need to protect water and soils for future generations.	future generations
31	'Carbon farming' limits my freedom to run my farm as I wish.	freedom to farm
32	I would accept that soil health practices may have a negative impact on my income in the short run.	short-term income
33	Farmers are both, producers of agricultural products and nature protectionists.	nature protectionists
34	The Dutch soils are in good conditions (additional soil health measures are not necessary)	soil conditions are good
35	Good agricultural practices mean finding a balance between nature protection and the production of agricultural goods.	balance
36	I would like to focus more on agriculture and less on administrative aspects (I am uninterested contracts of any kind).	focus farming

4.3.3.3 Data Collection

The online platform (Q Method Software) was used to conduct the experiment. The data was collected in winter/early spring 2024 and 2025. This period was chosen as farmers are less busy conducting field work. Some responses from arable farmers were collected by a market research company strongly focused on agriculture and able to reach arable farmers only. The remaining farmers were reached on farm fairs, and by driving to farms in the university's vicinity.

The participants first received information about the aim of the experiment. Then, they were informed about the three potential incentive mechanisms. In this step, they had the choice to either watch a seven-minute video on the topic, or to read the information.[1] Next, farmers could decide to pre-order the statements (initial sort) before performing the actual sorting into the Q-sorting grid. When pre-ordering the statements, they could choose between three categories: disagreement, neutral, agreement. Afterwards, the participants were asked to sort the 36 statements into the Q-sorting grid. The Q-sorting grid took a quasi-normal distribution. Farmers were asked to place the statements based on their level of agreement or disagreement (the scale ranged from: least agree to most agree (-5, -4, -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5)) with the respective statement.

The statements were randomly presented to the farmers during the sorting exercise. After finishing the sorting exercise, farmers were asked to provide information on themselves and their farms. In addition, a direct question on how to best promote soil health was included (via i. public funding, ii. markets for EU-certified carbon credits, iii. private nature protection contracts with value chain partners).

The current sample includes 16 farmers, and the data collection currently continues. Brown (2003) advised to include no more than 40 participants in the analysis, while Webler et al. (2009) propose a typical sample size of 12-36. The already mentioned Q-Methodology experiments by Davies & Hodge (2007) included 100 farmers, while Braitto et al. (2020) analysed the responses from 34 participants, and Norris et al. (2021) included 15 Dutch farmers. In general, it is described that the experiment's results can be improved by focusing on a diverse rather than a very large sample. Diverse samples allow displaying multiple viewpoints and are not necessarily representative of the population.

4.3.4. Results

4.3.4.1. Descriptive Statistics

Table 9 provides the descriptive statistics for the analysed sample. The participating farmers are 45 years old on the average, and most of them are male (87 %). 44 % of them have a higher agricultural education (university degree). Most of them operate their farm conventionally (75 %), and farm on 82 hectares of land. Their most common soil type is clay (68 %). The estimated soil organic carbon content is mostly estimated to be between 1 and 3 % (56 %). Most of the farms had a secure succession (63 %). When asked how they would classify their farms, 81 % opted for arable farming. Looking at their distribution across the Dutch provinces, they appear relatively well distributed.

TABLE 9. SUMMARY OF THE DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF THE PARTICIPANTS.

Description	Mean
Year of birth	1979
Share of male participants	87 %
Share of participants with university degrees	44 %
Share of organic producers	25 %
Hectares of the farm	82
Share of arable farms	81 %
Soil organic content of the farm	56 % (1-3% SOC)
Predominant soil type	31 % sand, 68 % clay
Share of farms with secure succession	63 %

4.3.4.2. Extraction and Specification of the Factors

There is no general rule on how many factors to extract from the data analysed. One suggestion is to extract factors that display at least two significant factor loadings. An alternative is Humprey's rule, that is that a factor should be extracted when the cross-product of its two highest loadings exceeds twice the standard error (Davies & Hodge, 2007). Another option is to consider the Eigenvalue determined for different numbers of factors and to determine when the slope levels off.

The latter rule was applied to extract three factors. The analysis explains 56 % of the underlying variation in the responses, with 14 of the 16 Q-sorts loading significantly on at least one factor. The names of the factors are based on the distinguishing statements of the identified factors. They reflect the views of similar-minded participants. The first factor represents the *pro-environmental entrepreneurs*, with nine farmers loading on this factor alone. The second factor stands for *the traditional food providers*, with three farmers loading on this factor alone. The third factor represents the *carbon farming* enthusiasts (two farmers). Table 10 holds information on the factor estimates for the statements. The distinguishing statement has a score that is significantly different from the scores of the other factors. The higher the factor estimate, the more important the statement (Akhtar-Danesh, 2018).

TABLE 10. FACTOR SCORES OF THE STATEMENTS (E: PRO-ENVIRONMENTAL ENTREPRENEUR, T: TRADITIONAL FOOD PROVIDER, C: CARBON FARMING ENTHUSIAST)

No.	Label	Factor 1 (E)	Sig. Factor 1	Factor 2 (T)	Sig. Factor 2	Factor 3 (C)	Sig. Factor 3	Consensus Statements
1	long-term increase	2		1		2		x
2	good farm management	3		-1		3		
3	multiple public goods	1	x	3		4		
4	resilience climate change	5	x	0		0		
5	soil structure	-1		5	x	-3		
6	hard measures	-2		-5		-3		
7	training & education	0		-1		-2	x	
8	solutions food supply chain	3	x	0		1		
9	termination option	0		-1		1		x
10	inflation	0	x	2	x	5	x	
11	choose measures	1		4		1		
12	short tenure	0	x	3		3		
13	long-term contracts	-1		-2		0		
14	farmers' groups	0		0		4	x	
15	soil sampling costs	-2		-4		-2		
16	result-based	-4		-3		2	x	
17	action-based payments	1		1		-1		
18	CAP good incentives	-3		-2		-1		x
19	hobby farmers	-4	x	0		1		
20	CM attractive	-2		-2		0		
21	payment combination	-1		-3	x	0		
22	existing initiatives	-1		0		-1		x
23	CM risky	-2		1	x	-1		

24	hybrid payments	0		-1		0		x
25	legislation	1	x	-4		-4		
26	high competition	-3	x	2		2		
27	entrepreneuria l	3		-1		1		
28	green washing	-1	x	1	x	-5	x	
29	productivity	2	x	-2		-4		
30	future generations	1		0		-2	x	
31	freedom to farm	-3		2	x	-1		
32	short-term income	2	x	-3		-3		
33	nature protectionists	2		1		3		x
34	soil conditions are good	-5	x	2	x	-2	x	
35	balance	4		4		2		
36	focus farming	4		3		0	x	

The Pro-environmental entrepreneurs

There are 12 distinguishing statements for the factor. The pro-environmental entrepreneurs believe that soil health-friendly farming helps to make their enterprise more resilient against climate change (no. 4) and would even accept short-term income losses to improve their soil quality in the end (no. 32). This might be driven by perceiving the quality of Dutch soils as relatively poor (no. 34), or by their agreement that productivity does not mainly drive their farm management decisions (no. 29). They further believe that the market allows farmers to extensify their operations (no. 16), and that the public should remunerate the various public goods provided by soil health practices (no. 3). Considering potential financial numerations, they agree that the actors involved in the food supply chains need to find solutions to remunerate public goods (no. 8). Besides this, they might be open to participating in AES - they disagree with the statement 'AES and eco-schemes are for hobby farmers and for farmers on poor quality soils' (no. 19). They might have a slight interest in carbon markets, as they slightly (-1) oppose the statement that 'To state that CO₂ emissions are lowered by soil health practices is greenwashing' (no. 28), in addition, they perceive long contracts as acceptable (no. 12).

The Traditional Food Providers

The *traditional food providers* do not share this attitude, seven statements are distinguishing for them. This might be explained by their agreement to the statement 'The Dutch soils are in good condition'. They also state that other measures that determine soil quality (e.g., water holding capacities, low erosion) are more important to them than the soil organic carbon content (no. 5). They further agree that carbon farming activities would limit their ability to run their enterprise as they like (no. 31). This belief might explain why they rather oppose carbon markets which might be indicated by their slight agreement with the statement 'To state that CO₂ emissions are lowered by soil health practices is greenwashing' (no. 1). Moreover, they strongly oppose the idea that 'It would be a good incentive when it would be allowed to combine payments from the CAP (AES and eco-schemes) and private payments (from the value chain or over carbon markets)' (no. 21). Hence, none of the analysed incentives might help to motivate this group.

The Carbon Farming Enthusiasts

The last group represents *carbon farming enthusiasts* with eight distinguishing statements. The group was named carbon farming enthusiasts as they strongly oppose the statement 'To state that CO₂ emissions are lowered by soil health practices is greenwashing' (no. 28). This could indicate an interest in selling carbon offsets. Furthermore, they agree with 'Result based payments should exclude farmers having high carbon contents in soils to promote additional action against climate change' (no. 16). This indicates a willingness for ambitious action against climate change. Furthermore, they value inflation-adjusted payments (no. 10) as additional incentives. This aspect might be of special importance to them as carbon credit trade requires relatively long contracts. Furthermore, they would rather participate in initiatives from farmers groups (no. 14). These are the most common set-ups of current early trails for carbon credit trade in the Netherlands. Last, their disagreement with statement no. 7 'Additional training and education are good enough incentives to motivate me to implement additional soil health practices'. indicates that they demand financial incentives to adjust their farm management and that they will not take action for free.

Consensus Statements

Besides these distinguishing statements, some consensus statements are identified. A consensus statement displays similar scores across all factors. Farmers slightly agree that they must play a role in nature protection (no. 33 'nature protection') and that 'Soil health practices can reliably increase the soil organic carbon content in the long run'. Furthermore, they uniformly disagree with statement no. 18 'The payments offered over the CAP (AES and eco-schemes) are high enough to set financial incentives'. For other statements that referred to potential additional incentives, such as no. 9

'termination option', no. 24 'hybrid payments' and no.22 'Existing initiatives' rather neutral perceptions are found across all factors.

4.3.5 Discussion and conclusion

The analysis yielded three different viewpoints: i. *the pro-environmental entrepreneur* (E), ii. *the traditional food provider* (T), iii. *the carbon farming enthusiast* (C). The next section discusses the main characteristics of the groups, their evaluations of the different incentives, and provides insights into how to promote soil health measures among these farmers. The section closes with the implications of the findings for the market potential of the different incentives.

4.3.5.1 Incentivising the pro-environmental entrepreneurs

The *pro-environmental entrepreneurs* show a stronger interest in solutions with value chain partners. From a research perspective, there is a need for further exploration into, for instance, what farmers expect from value chain partners and how to ensure fairness. Currently, only one experiment conducted by Weituschat et al. (2023) investigates value chain contracts for soil health, and it does not cover these aspects. Weituschat et al.'s (2023) article determines farmers' willingness to participate in production contracts under Barillas' sustainable farming initiative, and they strongly focus on the measures demanded. Furthermore, it might be of interest to investigate consumer preference and whether they respond to soil health claims as well, as claims for climate neutrality might become more difficult.

Additionally, there is potential for researchers to enhance Dutch AES, the most significant funding source of the CAP, as its current incentives were negatively perceived by all groups (no. 18). The '*pro-environmental entrepreneurs*' might be interested in both value chain payments and AES. They strongly disagree that AES are only for hobby farmers and those on low quality soils only (no. 19). It might be that improved AES are well accepted by farmers in factor one. Improvements in the CAP payments that lead to higher take-up rates are also of special interest to the Netherlands, where participation rates are among the lowest across Europe (Zimmermann & Britz, 2016).

The finding that farmers display a certain interest in AES compared to carbon markets would also be in line with the literature from the US (Canales et al., 2024; Gramig & Widmar, 2018). They find that farmers are more interested in AES than carbon markets because AES more commonly offer action-based payments

4.3.5.2 Incentivising the Carbon Farming Enthusiasts

For the third factor, *'the carbon farming enthusiasts'*, it should be critically evaluated if carbon credit trade for soil health measures is likely to become a reality. While the quantification process for EU-certified credits is still undergoing development, certain measures with significant potential for carbon storage and positive co-benefits for biodiversity are already being identified for prioritisation. Notably, carbon storage in peat soils, reforestation, and agroforestry are emerging as promising alternatives, both in terms of their scalability and environmental impact (COWI et al., 2021; McDonald et al., 2021; McDonald et al., 2023). Soil health measures are currently subject to critical evaluation, especially because carbon sequestration is easily reversible on farmland (Paul et al., 2023). Farmers across all groups disagreed with the statement that they might plant additional trees or rewet peatland to be able to store more CO₂. This dislike towards harder measures is commonly described, for instance, also by Weituschat et al. (2023) for different practices on arable land, by Norris et al. (2021) for peatland rewetting in the Netherlands and by Dumbrell et al. (2016) for the planting of trees.

Researchers and other stakeholders interested in farmers' willingness to engage in carbon credit trade could further explore the carbon credit trade initiatives already set up by groups of farmers. Farmers, on the third factor, agreed that they would rather participate when part of farmers' groups being in the Netherlands, such a group is ZLTO. ZLTO is a farmer's organisation that started early trials on the topic (ZLTO, 2024). The positive perception of activities from farmers' groups might also be particularly evident in the Netherlands, where farmers' collectives have organised nature protection activities since 2016 (Terwan, 2016). The importance of tight social networks that might exist in such collectives is also highlighted by Braitto et al. (2020) as an essential factor to promote soil health. Besides these social aspects, another reason why farmers' groups are perceived positively is that monitoring costs for carbon farming are expected to be substantial, and a collective implementation might help to share costs for monitoring and administration (Buck & Palumbo-Compton, 2022; Tiusanen et al., 2022).

4.3.5.3 Incentivising the Traditional Food Providers

Farmers sorted into the second factor *'traditional food providers'* seem less likely to improve their soil health with the help of any of the three suggested incentives. Other soil quality aspects that are closer linked to the production potential are more important to this group than carbon sequestration. However, many improvements, for instance, of soil structure and in the availability of nutrients and water go hand in hand with higher carbon contents (Lal, 2016). This should be emphasised when talking to traditional food providers.

In addition, research from the Netherlands shows that the inclusion of more soil health promoting practices (e.g. more cattle manure, more catch crops and higher grain shares) can increase the income from arable farming in the long run (Kik et al., 2023). Some farmers seem to already share this belief - potential improvements in long-term profitability are described as decisive in multiple articles on farmers' acceptance of soil health AES or carbon credit contracts (Buck & Palumbo-Compton, 2022; Canales et al., 2024; Tiusanen et al., 2022). Even though farmers in the third group strongly disagreed that better knowledge provision and training are enough to change farm management, training opportunities should be explored further. In theory the profit-oriented *traditional food providers* should be interested in strategies that increase their income in the long run. That some groups of farmers are difficult to motivate is confirmed by other authors. Their perception is shared by *Commodity Conservationists* and *Jeffersonians* farmers in Davies & Hodge (2007), or Braitto et al.'s (2020) *traditional food providers* and *profit maximisers*.

4.3.5.4 Perception of other incentives

Besides these differences, the experiment also allowed to identify statements the farmers agreed upon. One is the already discussed negative evaluation of the current financial incentives offered over the eco-schemes or the AES. Another statement is no. 33 'Farmers are both producers of agricultural products and nature protectionists'. As expected, the first and third viewpoints agree more strongly with this statement. For the second viewpoint (*traditional food providers*), the question arises how to support action. One option to promote pro-environmental action might be to better educate on the effects climate change will have on Dutch agriculture. Hail, floods and storms have already become more common and challenging for Dutch agriculture (The Ministry of Agriculture Nature and Food Quality, 2023). Only farmers in factor one believe that their farm will become more resilient to climate change when soil health practices are implemented. Nevertheless, that farmers tend to agree with statement 33 raises hope that better soil health can be achieved in the Netherlands.

Besides statements that might allow identifying farmers interested in the three major incentive mechanisms (public payments, carbon credit trade and contracts with value chain partners), some statements referred to additional incentives that could be offered as being part of all other contracts. One statement that displays significant loading for the second and third factors is no. 10 'inflation'. It deserves attention on how to make long contracts more attractive and inflation-adjusted payments could be a solution for contracts including action-based payments. Furthermore, the experiment included a termination option for a successor. This was included because Rochecouste et al. (2017) describe that farmers dislike long nature conservation and carbon farming contracts because they do not like to limit their flexibility and the flexibility of their

successor. This statement 'I would find carbon farming contracts more attractive when my successors would be able to leave the contract' (no. 9) is rather neutrally perceived across all groups. However, the idea might still deserve attention in up-coming experiments. For nature protection it is commonly described as problematic that farmers are unwilling to opt for long contracts (>10 years) (Harmanny & Schulp, 2023; Mamine et al., 2020; Schaub et al., 2023).

Last, a word of caution is necessary as this article uses Q-methodology. The underlying sample is not representative of the Netherlands. As common in Q-methodology experiments, it was aimed to include a diverse set of farmers and many face-to-face interviews, farmers more interested in the topic might have been more likely to agree to participate. Therefore, the result that most farmers have an interest in value chain payments and might be interested in improved AES might not represent the general farming population. Still, the conducted Q-methodology experiment highlights that farmers perceive the incentives on offer quite differently, and that some farmers (*traditional food providers*) will be difficult to motivate. Furthermore, the method detected additional incentives, namely AES improvements, that might be of interest for the first factor '*pro environmental entrepreneurs*' and the last factor '*carbon farming enthusiasts*'. Collective implementation of carbon farming with farmer groups could help to motivate these farmers.

4.3.5.5 Market potential of the different incentives

The results suggest that farmers in this sample display an interest in private contracts with value chain payments (*the pro-environmental entrepreneurs*). Half of the sample of farmers are grouped in this category. Some farmers are also interested in the opportunity to sell carbon credits (*carbon farming enthusiasts, 20% of the sample*). However, the group '*traditional food providers (20% of the sample)*' is not interested in any of the incentive mechanisms. Across all groups, farmers agree that the CAP currently fails to set good incentives over eco-schemes or AES. Overall, the results are in line with the finding of Braito et al. (2020) that not all farmers respond equally well to the financial incentives on offer.

4.4 Italy: Italian consumers (UNIFE, UNIPI)

4.4.1 Case study description

The Italian case study was carried out by the University of Ferrara (UNIFE) and the University of Pisa (UNIPI). The study investigates the willingness of Italian consumers to financially support farmers in adopting conservation agriculture practices to improve soil health. While UNIFE made the experimental design and collected 414 observations, UNIPI collected 600 observations. The overall sample (1014 observations) is representative of age, gender and education. Three hypothetical programs have been considered: i) area-based payment, ii) result-based payment and iii) hybrid payments. The area-based scheme consists of a fixed payment per hectare granted to farmers who adopt conservation agriculture practices. By contrast, the result-based scheme provides payments linked to the certified increase in soil organic matter. Finally, the hybrid scheme combines both approaches, with 50% of the payment based on area and 50% on results).

This study contributes to the development of alternative mechanisms to public funding and provides valuable insights for designing contracts between consumers and farmers to effectively increase soil health in Italy.

4.4.2 Method

Questionnaire Structure

The questionnaire submitted to Italian consumers was divided into five distinct sections, aiming to systematically and coherently explore preferences regarding the willingness to pay for soil health-related conservation agricultural practices. The sections are described in detail below:

1. Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE): The first and central section of the questionnaire consisted of a series of “choice cards” designed to simulate realistic program scenarios. Consumers were asked to choose between two program options (A and B), each with different characteristics, or to reject both via the “opt out” option. The aim was to investigate preferences regarding the duration of program commitment, the estimated increase of organic matter in the soil, the type and structure of payment and the amount of payment per hectare.

3. Socio-demographic Section: This section collected personal information, including age, gender, education of respondent and the household level of income.

4. Socio-psychological Constructs: Consumers were asked to express their level of agreement with statements about their social and personal norms, their trust in other people as well as in institutions, their environmental concerns and their perception of impacts on human health.

5. Environmental Risk Perception Section: This section explored how consumers perceive the risk associated with soil degradation in the area where they live. It included questions on perceived degradation of chemical, physical and biological soil factors.

Attribute Selection and DCE Design

To design a Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE), it is essential to select relevant, understandable, and realistic attributes for participants, in this case, consumers. The attributes were chosen based on scientific literature on adopting agri-environmental practices (Franceschini et al., 2023; Franceschinis et al., 2022). Four main attributes were considered:

TABLE 11. DCE ATTRIBUTES AND LEVELS

Attribute	Levels	Description
Annual payment per hectare	100 €, 200 €	Compensation to farmers who adopt conservation practices
Type of payment	100% fixed; 50% fixed + 50% result-based; 100% result-based	Payment modalities: fixed, performance-based or hybrid
Estimated organic matter increase	Low, Medium, High	Represents the certified increase of organic matter in the soil
Commitment duration	5, 10, 20 years	Minimum period of commitment

Payments from €100 to €200/ha reflect realistic ranges, consistent with CAP incentives and marginal costs associated with practices such as no-till farming and cover crops.

Durations from 5 to 20 years reflect the time required to obtain tangible soil benefits.

Payment types test preferences between area-based and result-based mechanisms, a key aspect in the literature, as the latter are expected to provide cost-effectiveness of the measure (D'Alberto et al., 2024; Vergamini et al., 2024)

Organic matter increase reflects consumers' awareness about soil degradation and their willingness to pay for soil health (Franceschinis et al., 2023; Franceschinis et al., 2022).

Each survey participant received randomised choice cards containing two program alternatives (A and B) and a third "opt-out" option. An example is shown below:

TABLE 12. EXAMPLE CHOICE CARD

Attribute	Alternative A	Alternative B
Durata dell'impegno a supportare le pratiche di agricoltura conservativa	5 anni	20 anni
Variazione (aumento) del contenuto di sostanza organica nel suolo	Basso	Alto
Pagamento per ha	€100 per ha	€200 per ha
Tipo di pagamento	100% in base all'aumento della sostanza organica	50% di pagamento fisso per ha + 50% in base all'aumento della sostanza organica

The survey was set up online on the Qualtrics platform. Data collection for the experiment began in January 2025 and ended in March 2025.

Estimation

For the estimation, a mixed logit model was estimated.

While the mixed logit accounts for preference heterogeneity using individual-specific coefficients, it lacks detailed information on differences in attribute perception (Train, 2009). WTP measures the substitution rate between an attribute and monetary value (Train, 2009). In models with random effects, calculating the ratio directly would lead to unreasonably high values (Train & Weeks, 2015), hence the price coefficient was considered fixed when calculating WTP for the mixed logit model.

The Willingness to Pay (WTP) is a measure used to quantify the monetary payment that consumers are willing to give to farmers. It is particularly useful in evaluating trade-offs between monetary and non-monetary attributes in program design. It indicates the amount of money (in euros per hectare) a consumer would give to farmer to adopt conservation agriculture practices to increase organic matter in the soil.

4.4.3 Survey results

Descriptive statistics

The sample includes 1014 Italian consumers. The main socio-demographic characteristics are reported in Table 13.

TABLE 13. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES.

Variable	Description	Mean	Percentage	Std. Dev.
Age	Age of interviewed	47 years	N.A.	13.4
Gender	Male	N.A.	53%	N.A.
	Female	N.A.	47%	N.A.
Education	Primary school	N.A.	4%	N.A.
	Secondary school	N.A.	9%	N.A.
	High school	N.A.	49%	N.A.
	Master degree	N.A.	37%	N.A.
	More than Master degree	N.A.	1%	N.A.
Income	Under 1,000 euro/month	N.A.	9%	N.A.
	Between 1,000 and 1,500 euro/month	N.A.	15%	N.A.
	Between 1,500 and 2,000 euro/month	N.A.	19%	N.A.
	Between 2,000 and 2,500 euro/month	N.A.	17%	N.A.
	Between 2,500 and 3,500 euro/month	N.A.	17%	N.A.
	Between 3,500 and 5,000 euro/month	N.A.	16%	N.A.
	More than 5,000 euro/month	N.A.	7%	N.A.

Note: N.A.: not applicable

These data are representative of Italian consumers in terms of age, gender and education. The average age is 47 years, and 53% of the sample are male, while 47% are female. Most consumers (around 49%) reporting having a high school diploma, while 4% have only a primary school education. In terms of income, 19% of consumers

declared earning between 1,500 and 2,000 euros per month, while the 9% receive less than 1,000 euros.

4.4.4 Market potential estimation

The mixed logit model results are presented in the following table 14.

TABLE 14. MIXED LOGIT MODEL RESULTS.

Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	z	MWTP (€)
Payment per hectare	-0.002***	0.000	-5.63	-
Duration (years)	-0.027***	0.004	-6.70	-11.59
Increase of organic matter	0.284***	0.034	8.35	120.37
Payment type	0.069**	0.028	2.42	29.36
Opt-out (no contract option)	-5.261***	0.462	-11.38	-

(**p < 0.05, ***p < 0.01)

The coefficients indicate that Italian consumers are more likely to financially support farmers who adopt conservation agriculture practices when a lower per-hectare payment is required (as shown by the negative and significant coefficient). A negative coefficient is also observed for the duration attribute, suggesting that consumers show aversion to longer programs durations. Conversely, the likelihood of participation in conservation agriculture programs increases when there is a high certified increase in soil organic matter and when payments to farmers are result-based (i.e., linked to increases in organic matter). The statistical analysis suggest that Italian consumers are willing to economically support farmers adopting conservation agricultural practices if the payment and duration of commitment are not too high, and if there is an increase of organic matter. Moreover, consumers prefer programs where payments to farmers are based on measurable results rather than a fixed per-hectare subsidy.

The Willingness-to-pay (MWTP) values provide further insight:

- consumers are willing to pay 11.59 euro less per hectare for each additional year of contract duration;
- They are willing to pay 29.36 euro more per hectare if payments are result-based;
- They are willing to pay over euro 120 more per hectare for a high certified increase in soil organic matter.

4.5 Estonia: Seed centre (METK)

4.5.1 Case study description

METK is the Estonian Centre for Rural Research and Knowledge, operating under the governance of the Estonian Ministry of Rural Affairs. METK serves as a national research institution specializing in the development of sustainable agricultural practices, plant breeding, and the integration of soil science with agrotechnology.

METK is actively engaged in the breeding of a wide range of agricultural crops and the production of high-quality seed material. The organization conducts comprehensive research on the effects of various crops and agrotechnological practices on soil physical, chemical, and biological properties. Activities include systematic soil sampling, laboratory analyses, field-based soil research, and the development of digital soil maps and advisory systems that support precision agriculture based on site-specific soil characteristics.

The Seed Centre at METK manages approximately 1,100 hectares of land dedicated to high-quality seed production. Species cultivated for seed include major field crops such as cereals, oilseed and turnip rape, vegetables, forage grasses, and legume crops. The seed production chain encompasses all stages from breeder seed to certified seed. This ensures the availability and long-term continuity of METK-bred Estonian varieties. On average, METK varieties are certified on approximately 4,600 hectares of farmland annually, yielding about 5,500 tonnes of certified seed (e.g., 4 t/ha by cereals and 0,5 t/ha by grasses)

Current seed production systems rely primarily on conventional agricultural practices, including intensive tillage (such as ploughing), mineral fertilisation, and the application of synthetic pesticides. While these methods support high productivity and seed quality, they are associated with negative environmental externalities, including soil degradation and increased greenhouse gas emissions.

Objective of the Study

The primary objective of this study is to assess the long-term impact of intensive seed production on soil health by evaluating and comparing soil quality indicators in fields under prolonged seed production with control fields not used for seed cultivation.

Proposed Business Model

The proposed business model focuses on sustainability and includes the following components:

- Taking measures to reduce the carbon footprint of seed production;

- Evaluating the carbon footprint of seed production;
- Certifying the carbon footprint of seed;
- Marketing low-carbon seed at a premium price.

A survey was conducted among Estonian farmers to assess their willingness to pay more for carbon-certified farming inputs, including carbon-certified seed.

4.5.2 Methodology

This study was conducted to assess the feasibility of a business model supporting soil health through certified seed production in Estonia. The primary objective was to investigate Estonian farmers' willingness to pay a premium for carbon-labelled seeds and to identify the factors influencing their decision-making.

Survey design and distribution

A structured questionnaire was developed to explore farmers' attitudes toward sustainability, certified seed use, and carbon labelling. The survey included both closed and Likert-scale questions, targeting variables such as farming practices, participation in carbon programs, income level, education, gender, and environmental preferences.

The questionnaire was distributed electronically in late 2024 to a targeted sample of **active farmers in Estonia who owned more than 10 hectares of agricultural land**. This inclusion criterion ensured that the responses came from farmers with substantial land-based operations likely to engage in seed purchasing and crop production decisions.

Sampling and respondents

From the distributed survey, **122 to 169 valid responses** were collected, depending on the specific questions analysed. The sample included farmers from diverse geographic areas and production systems within Estonia. All participants were anonymous, and their participation was voluntary.

Data analysis

The collected data were analysed using **logistic regression models** to identify significant factors influencing the willingness to pay for carbon-labelled seeds. The models tested variables related to environmental values, participation in sustainability programs, current seed use practices, socio-economic background, and perception of market.

4.5.3 Results

This study analysed Estonian farmers' willingness to pay (WTP) for carbon-labelled and environmentally labelled seeds using survey data from active farmers owning more than 10 hectares of land. A series of logistic and interval regression models were used to explore how gender, education, income, and attitudes affect purchasing decisions under different environmental labelling scenarios.

Willingness-to-pay for carbon-labelled seeds

A majority of farmers ($n = 73$) reported that they were not willing to pay more for carbon-labelled seed. However, 52 respondents expressed willingness to pay more if carbon labelling brought a **market advantage**, while smaller groups supported paying more if the cost was **offset by carbon credits** ($n = 20$) or if the seed contributed to the **company's ESG value** ($n = 5$).

Market Advantage Scenario: Male farmers were significantly more likely to accept a premium price if carbon-labelled seeds provided a market advantage ($p = 0.0278$). Applied higher education also increased the likelihood of WTP, with a borderline significant effect ($p = 0.0512$).

Carbon Credit Offset Scenario: A significant negative association was observed between the belief that farmers should support sustainable seed producers and WTP in this context ($p = 0.0032$), suggesting scepticism about indirect benefits when framed as carbon offsetting.

ESG Value Scenario: Farmers with monthly household incomes of **1500–2000€** ($p = 0.0429$) and **3500–5000€** ($p = 0.0147$) were more likely to pay a premium if carbon-labelled seeds enhanced their company's ESG profile. In contrast, belief in technological solutions to environmental issues without lifestyle changes reduced willingness ($p = 0.0120$).

WTP when cost is offset (interval regression)

Using interval regression to evaluate premium thresholds (0%, 10%, 20%), results show that male respondents had a **2.28 percentage point lower** latent WTP than females ($p = 0.0083$). No other variables reached statistical significance, though some income groups showed positive, non-significant effects.

WTP for environmentally labelled inputs

When asked about paying more for environmentally produced agricultural inputs (seeds, fertilizers, fuel), the majority of respondents (n = 101) answered **no**. Only 9 were willing to pay up to 10% more, and 51 agreed to a 5% premium.

Income Effect: Respondents with **1500–2000€** ($p = 0.0374$) and **3500–5000€** ($p = 0.0079$) monthly income levels were significantly more likely to accept a higher price for environmentally friendly products.

Producer Support Belief: A consistently significant negative effect was found across models: farmers who agreed with the statement that seed producers should be supported through sustainable purchasing were themselves **less likely** to pay more for labelled inputs ($p = 0.0025$).

Summary of significant findings

TABLE 15. SUMMARY OF SIGNIFICANT FINDINGS

Factor	Effect on WTP	Significance
Male gender	Higher WTP for market advantage; lower for offsets	$p < 0.05$
Applied higher education	Higher WTP for market advantage and offset	$p < 0.05$
Income (1500–5000€)	Higher WTP for ESG value and eco-labelled inputs	$p < 0.05$
Belief in tech solutions	Lower WTP for ESG-based carbon labelling	$p < 0.05$
Support for seed producers	Lower WTP across offset and environmental scenarios	$p < 0.01$

Interpretation

The findings highlight that Estonian farmers' willingness to support sustainability through seed choices is shaped more by **economic pragmatism and personal worldviews** than by generalized environmental values. Market-based benefits, income level, and education drive positive responses, while indirect or collective benefits (e.g., carbon credit schemes or ESG metrics) receive less support. The consistent negative impact of the "support for seed producers" belief suggests a

potential gap between **normative attitudes** and **personal action** in sustainability-related decision-making.

4.5.4 Market potential

The study shows that in Estonia, farmers' willingness to pay for carbon- or environmentally labelled seeds remains limited, with most respondents unwilling to pay a premium unless the label brings a clear market advantage. This reflects a broader pattern of economic pragmatism: farmers are more likely to support sustainability through seed choices when it helps them secure better prices, access new markets, or strengthen their competitive position, rather than out of abstract environmental motivation. Higher education, mid-to-higher income levels, and in some cases gender play a role in shaping openness to premiums, but overall, the Estonian market potential is modest and likely concentrated in niche segments. Early adopters will most likely be farmers who supply premium food chains, restaurants, and export markets where sustainability labelling already matters. At the same time, there is a perception that the costs of sustainability should be borne by input suppliers or offset by tangible benefits, which suggests that labelled seeds must demonstrate either agronomic gains (such as better resilience or reduced input needs) or downstream financial rewards to find traction.

The wider EU market presents a different picture. In Western and Northern Europe, consumers, retailers, and policymakers are already driving demand for carbon labelling in food, and input markets are more closely tied to sustainability schemes. Here, carbon- or eco-labelled seeds could gain significant ground if positioned as tools for farmers to meet market and policy requirements. The European Green Deal, CAP eco-schemes, and the forthcoming Soil Health Law are strong policy levers that can accelerate adoption, especially when combined with private certification schemes or corporate ESG commitments. In these contexts, carbon-labelled seeds can move from a niche product into the mainstream, particularly when linked to supply contracts or sustainability-oriented cooperatives.

Taken together, the findings suggest that while Estonia may serve as a valuable testbed for piloting these seeds in high-value niche markets, large-scale uptake will only follow if clear financial or agronomic benefits are visible. In contrast, the EU-wide potential is far greater, especially in markets where consumer demand, ESG obligations, and policy incentives converge. Success depends less on the label itself and more on the ability to position it as a business opportunity: a way to secure contracts, reduce risks, and strengthen profitability while contributing to broader sustainability goals.

4.6 Bulgaria: Agrotourism (NBU)

4.6.1 Introduction and case study description

Introduction

The case study in the Plovdiv and Pazardzhik regions, which employs the business model of "Integrated production in vineyards with a winery and rural tourism," is important for increasing production efficiency, reducing marketing costs, and improving competitiveness in rural areas. Additionally, it can provide many ecosystem functions and services, such as water and nutrient cycling, biodiversity, and economic viability.

Environmental challenges and the socio-economic setting are two focal points that must be considered. From an environmental perspective, there are two major focal points. First, there are the climatic conditions, which are exacerbated by climate change: floods, droughts, landslides, hurricane winds, and hailstorms. The increased frequency of heavy rainstorms, characterized by high intensity and short duration, will lead to increased short-term surface runoff and the risk of water erosion on slopes. Most of the aforementioned events are purely natural and difficult to foresee and control; however, they put pressure on everyday operations. On the other hand, agricultural practices may lead to soil erosion, one of the biggest soil problems in Bulgaria.

Case study description

The aim of the Case Study is to value the potential of local traditional and regional traditional products in the wine sector and strengthen their relationship with communities in order to develop the local economy and agricultural sector.

4.6.2 Method

The aim of the survey is to analyse the production and consumption of traditional products (wine), as well as their integration with rural tourism as a result of applying the business model "Integrated Vineyard Production with Wine and Rural Tourism" in the Plovdiv and Pazardzhik regions. In this context, we seek to assess consumer attitudes toward the consumption of wines produced with and without agri-environmental measures (AEM) aimed at preventing soil erosion, and their combination with rural tourism.

The questionnaire is divided into three parts: Part A – General Questions; Part B – Choice Experiment Card; Part C – Questions related to environmental protection. For the purposes of this study, we selected the implementation of one specific agri-

environmental measure (AEM) – cover crops in the inter-rows of vineyards – to reduce soil erosion and improve soil health. Cover crops are considered to offer multiple benefits for the soil, including reducing erosion, decreasing compaction, increasing organic matter, and more.

In the choice experiment respondents are asked to choose between several hypothetical alternatives that differ in specific characteristics (attributes). In this particular case, participants choose between four versions of a wine product, with each alternative described by a combination of the following attributes: the presence or absence of agri-environmental measures (AEM), the impact on soil erosion (reduces or does not reduce), the provision or absence of cultural services (such as wine tourism), and the price of the product (8 EUR, 10 EUR, 14EUR, or 18 EUR per bottle). The respondent's task is to select the preferred alternative among the four options presented in each choice card.

	Option 1	Option 2	Option 3	Option 4
Products with AEM or without AEM	NO AEM	NO AEM	AEM	AEM
Wine tourism	NO	YES	NO	YES
Price, €/ bottle of wine	8 €	10 €	14 €	18 €

FIGURE 5. DCE ATTRIBUTES AND LEVELS

The methodology involves creating an experimental design in which the different levels of the attributes are systematically combined to generate realistic but varied product profiles. Each respondent views one or several such cards and makes a choice, allowing researchers to collect data on their preferences. Using statistical models (e.g., logit models), the analysis identifies which attributes most strongly influence decision-making. Additionally, the respondents' willingness to pay (WTP) for various non-monetary benefits – such as environmental or cultural services – is estimated, as well as the trade-offs consumers are willing to make between price and additional product benefits.

The aim of this approach is to determine which factors are most significant to consumers when choosing wine products, the extent to which they value additional characteristics such as contributions to environmental protection or the development of wine tourism, and whether they are willing to pay a higher price for these benefits.

The questionnaire was distributed electronically and the survey finished in late 2024. From the distributed survey, 431 to 284 valid responses were collected, depending on the specific questions analysed.

4.6.3 Survey results

Analysis of preferences by age

Option 3 (with AEM, no tourism) was the most preferred overall (123 of 284 respondents). Younger respondents (18–40) showed a strong preference for AEM options, especially Option 3. Cultural services (wine tourism) in Option 2 and Option 4 influenced some preferences, but not as much as the presence of AEM.

The p-values > 0.05 indicate that no statistically significant relationship exists between age group and product choice at the conventional 5% significance level. However, the Linear-by-Linear Association test result ($p = 0.052$) is marginal, suggesting a potential weak trend – perhaps younger consumers are more inclined toward environmentally friendly options, but the evidence is not strong enough to confirm this definitively.

Environmental sustainability matters: The majority preferred options using agri-environmental measures, even when those options were more expensive. This suggests willingness to pay for environmental benefits like soil erosion reduction.

Cultural services have secondary importance: Wine tourism added value but was not the primary driver of choice. Option 3 (no tourism, with AEM) was more popular than Option 4 (with both AEM and tourism), likely due to price sensitivity.

Age influence might exist, but not significant: Younger respondents (18–40) are more open to eco-friendly wine options, but the difference by age is not statistically significant.

Price sensitivity persists: While consumers valued AEM, there was still a noticeable drop-off at higher price points (Option 4 at €18 was less preferred despite offering both AEM and cultural services).

Producers should consider adopting and communicating the use of AEM in wine production, as it positively affects consumer preference. Marketing efforts could highlight environmental benefits rather than just cultural experiences.

Analysis of preferences by gender

Option 3 (wine with AEM, no tourism, €14) is the most preferred option across both genders. It reflects a strong interest in environmentally sustainable wine, even without added tourism or the lowest price. Men favoured Option 3 (67 responses) slightly more than women (56 responses). Men showed higher preference for Option 2 (45 men vs. 37 women) – indicating somewhat more interest in wine tourism, even without AEM. Women were slightly less inclined to select the cheapest, least sustainable option (Option 1: 5 women vs. 14 men). Both genders prioritize environmental sustainability (AEM) over wine tourism and price – but men are marginally more responsive to the cultural/tourism value, while women show slightly more consistent environmental preferences.

All p-values are above 0.05, which means there is no statistically significant difference in wine product preferences between men and women. Gender does not strongly influence the choice between the four wine options in this sample.

Environmental sustainability (AEM use) is a stronger driver of preference than price or tourism, regardless of gender. Wine tourism has moderate appeal, especially among men, but it's not a dominant factor. Price is not the only concern – even higher-priced, environmentally friendly wines (Option 3 and 4) are widely preferred.

Analysis of preferences by education

Across all education levels, Option 3 (AEM, no tourism, €14) is the most preferred. However, the degree of preference shifts significantly with education level.

Primary education shows more balanced spread across all options. Option 2 (with tourism but without AEM) is most selected (22), showing interest in wine tourism even without environmental benefits. Lower concern for AEM; suggests less awareness or lower prioritization of environmental impact.

Option 3 slightly leads (20 responses) in high school education, indicating growing awareness of AEM benefits. Less interest in Option 1 (only 3 selected it), indicating shift away from the lowest-price option.

High school with specialization shows strong preference for Option 3 (82 responses) and Option 4 (44 responses) - both with AEM. Indicates high environmental awareness and willingness to pay more for sustainable and experiential products. Option 2 (with tourism only) also gets strong support (48), showing dual value of sustainability and tourism in this group.

All p-values are below 0.05, indicating a statistically significant association between education level and product preference confirming that higher education correlates with stronger preference for environmentally sustainable wine products.

As a conclusion environmental sustainability (AEM) is increasingly important with higher education. Primary education group values lower prices and tourism experiences more than soil health or AEM. Specialized education group is most environmentally and culturally engaged, showing readiness to pay for added value (AEM + tourism).

Analysis of preferences by income

Lower income groups (< €1,500) shows more evenly spread choices; Option 3 (AEM, no tourism) is most popular, but not dominant. Significant selection of Option 2 (with tourism but no AEM), especially among the lowest group. Price appears to be a stronger constraint; interest in sustainable wine exists, but affordability limits preference for the highest-priced Option 4.

Middle income (1,500 – 2,500 €) group shows strong preference for Option 3 (AEM, €14) – sustainability clearly matters. Option 2 is also popular among these groups, suggesting a balance between tourism and environmental values.

For higher income groups (> €2,500) Option 4 (AEM + tourism, €18) becomes increasingly dominant. At €3,500 – €5,000: 13 out of 17 chose Option 4 (76%); At €5,000+: all 5 respondents selected Option 4 (100%). These groups clearly prioritize quality, sustainability, and experience over price.

As income increases, preference shifts toward environmentally sustainable and culturally rich (tourism) wine, even at higher price points. The very low p-values (< 0.001) indicate a strong, statistically significant association between income level and wine product preference. The linear-by-linear association confirms a clear upward trend: higher income strongly correlates with choosing more expensive, sustainable, and experience-oriented wines.

Environmental sustainability (AEM) is a universal preference across income groups, but willingness to pay for it increases with income. Wine tourism is appreciated more as income rises, especially in the high-income brackets. Price sensitivity is higher in low-income groups, who still value sustainability but make more balanced choices.

4.6.4 Market potential estimation

The survey results clearly show that environmental sustainability – represented by the use of agri-environmental measures (AEM) – is the strongest factor influencing wine product preference. Across all demographic groups, Option 3 (wine with AEM, no tourism, €14) was the most preferred, suggesting that consumers are willing to pay a higher price for environmentally friendly wine. Although wine tourism and pricing influenced choices to some extent, they were secondary to the perceived ecological benefits. This trend highlights a growing public awareness and valuation of ecosystem services such as soil erosion prevention in agricultural production.

Education and income emerged as statistically significant predictors of preference. Respondents with higher education levels, particularly those with specialized training, demonstrated a stronger inclination toward sustainable and experiential wine options. Similarly, higher-income consumers were more likely to select premium options that combine environmental benefits with cultural services (e.g., wine tourism), despite higher prices. These groups show a clear readiness to pay for added value in wine products, making them prime targets for premium, environmentally sustainable wine marketing strategies.

In contrast, age and gender did not show statistically significant associations with wine preference, although some trends were noted. Younger consumers tended to favour sustainable options more than older ones, and men showed slightly greater interest in wine tourism than women. Still, both genders prioritized environmental attributes over price or cultural add-ons. These findings suggest that sustainability messaging has universal appeal across age and gender, but that tailored marketing efforts should focus more on education and income segments, where preferences and purchasing power align most strongly with sustainable and premium wine offerings.

Demographic profile of support for sustainable wines

The survey results show strong overall support for traditional wines produced with agri-environmental measures (TWAEM), with a clear majority of respondents agreeing that these wines provide significant environmental, health, and quality benefits. Statements regarding the role of TWAEM in improving health (Q6.4), reducing soil erosion (Q6.5), and justifying a higher price due to health benefits (Q6.7) received particularly high levels of agreement – above 85% in most cases. Respondents also widely recognized the role of TWAEM in supporting sustainable consumption and landscape conservation, though statements about taste (Q6.1) received slightly more varied responses. Despite the price being a potential barrier, the data indicate a general willingness to pay more for wine that offers environmental and health advantages.

When analysed by demographic groups, the data reveal important distinctions. Age showed no statistically significant differences, but there was a clear trend: younger participants (ages 18–40) were more likely to agree with the benefits of TWAEM across nearly all statements. Gender differences were generally minimal, with both men and women supporting TWAEM benefits; however, men were more likely to value landscape conservation (Q6.2), the only statement with a significant difference by gender ($p = 0.046$). On the other hand, education level showed several statistically significant effects, particularly in questions related to health (Q6.4), erosion control (Q6.5), and health-based price justification (Q6.7). This suggests that higher education – especially specialized education – correlates with stronger environmental and health awareness related to wine consumption.

Trust and uncertainty in TWAEM benefits

Across the sample, most respondents disagreed with statements expressing scepticism about TWAEM. For example, 67% disagreed that TWAEM have poorer taste (Q7.1), and 55% disagreed that their quality does not match the price (Q7.2). While some uncertainty exists about whether health claims might be exaggerated (Q7.3) and whether TWAEM directly reduce erosion (Q7.4), the majority of respondents were either disagreeing or unsure – indicating limited but present scepticism.

By age, younger respondents (18–40) were more confident in the benefits of TWAEM, with higher disagreement on negative statements. Notably, Q7.2 showed a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.014$), suggesting that age impacts how respondents perceive value for money in TWAEM. Gender differences were minimal across all risk statements, with no statistically significant variation. However, men were slightly more likely to agree that quality may not justify price (Q7.2) and that health benefits might be exaggerated (Q7.3).

Education level played a more significant role. Respondents with only primary education were more likely to agree with negative statements, particularly regarding taste (Q7.1, $p = 0.010$). Those with specialized education were less sceptical overall, supporting the notion that education correlates with greater confidence in the integrity and value of TWAEM.

Income level also influenced perceptions. For Q7.4 (erosion benefits), income differences were statistically significant ($p = 0.001$). Higher income groups were more confident that TWAEM contribute to reducing erosion, while lower income groups were more uncertain or sceptical. This suggests that trust in environmental claims grows with income, potentially reflecting exposure to environmental education or value alignment.

Exploring support for wine tourism: The role of education and income

Support for wine tourism as a cultural service was overwhelmingly positive. Over 83% agreed that visiting wineries enhances knowledge of local traditions (Q8.1), and nearly 90% valued vineyard tours (Q8.3). The overall wine tasting experience (Q8.2) was the highest-rated, with 254 of 284 respondents (89%) in agreement. Additional tourism services (Q8.4) were slightly less supported but still viewed positively (59% agreement).

Age differences in tourism preferences were negligible, with no statistically significant results, indicating that cultural interest in wine tourism spans generations. Similarly, gender analysis revealed that women and men are equally enthusiastic about the wine tourism experience. However, Q8.2 and Q8.4 showed significance by gender ($p = 0.018$), with women being marginally more positive toward additional services.

In contrast, education showed significant effects. Respondents with specialized education were significantly more likely to value educational and experiential tourism elements (Q8.1, $p = 0.001$; Q8.2, $p = 0.032$). This implies that education not only influences product trust but also shapes cultural and experiential expectations.

Lastly, income significantly influenced support for additional services (Q8.4, $p = 0.000$). Higher income respondents were more likely to value complementary activities like eco-trails and horseback riding, indicating that disposable income enhances appreciation for expanded tourism offerings.

Socioeconomic Influences on Environmental Values

The survey reveals that most respondents acknowledge the importance of soil-related ecosystem services, such as reducing soil erosion (Q9.1), increasing nutrients (Q9.2), and improving biodiversity (Q9.3). Agreement was strongest on nutrient enrichment (Q9.2), with over 88% responding positively. While differences by age and gender were not statistically significant for these questions, educational background and income did show strong effects. Respondents with higher education levels, especially those with specialized training, were more likely to agree with all three environmental statements, with significant differences in Q9.2 ($p = 0.000$) and Q9.3 ($p = 0.002$). Similarly, income had a significant effect on perceptions of nutrient improvement (Q9.2, $p = 0.000$), confirming that environmental literacy and economic resources correlate with greater appreciation of soil health practices.

When it comes to climate change beliefs and mitigation behaviours, the findings show a general belief in climate change, but with significant divisions by income and gender. While 103 respondents stated they believe climate change is real (Q10), men were more sceptical, with a larger share expressing doubt. The gender gap here was

statistically significant ($p = 0.002$). Likewise, higher income respondents were more likely to acknowledge climate change, while lower income groups showed stronger denial. Regarding CO₂ compensation behaviours (Q11), while most respondents do not offset their carbon footprint fully, those with higher education and income are significantly more likely to do so occasionally or even for their full lifestyle ($p = 0.011$). However, actual purchase of carbon certificates (Q12) remains almost non-existent, with only one respondent reporting such an action – indicating a clear gap between environmental attitudes and behaviours.

The survey also probed deeper beliefs about environmental solutions and values. On the statement "Science and technology will solve many environmental problems without us having to change our way of life" (Q13), responses varied widely across demographic groups. Education and income had the strongest influence, with more educated and higher-income respondents showing greater scepticism toward this passive view ($p = 0.000$). When asked about their awareness of soil health (Q14), age, gender, education, and income all showed statistically significant differences, especially income ($p = 0.000$). Those in higher socioeconomic brackets reported more frequent reflection on soil health. Lastly, although only one respondent rated healthy soils as "very important" for their well-being (Q15), and despite most responses clustering around "unimportant" or "neutral," significant differences were found by gender ($p = 0.000$) and income ($p = 0.000$), again suggesting that economic stability and gendered perspectives may shape environmental priorities. Finally, views on government support for farmers who enhance soil and biodiversity (Q16) were largely positive across all groups, but significantly more so among those with higher education ($p = 0.001$).

4.6.5 Discussion

Income level had the most pronounced and statistically significant influence on perceptions of TWAEM. Higher income groups consistently expressed greater agreement with all statements, especially those tied to health, sustainability, and price justification. Respondents earning over €3,500 per month almost unanimously supported the idea that the higher price of TWAEM wines is justified by the benefits they offer. These findings suggest that awareness of TWAEM benefits grows with both income and education, and that financial capacity increases willingness to support sustainable wine production. In contrast, age and gender play more modest roles, with only small differences observed. Overall, the data support the conclusion that TWAEM are widely accepted and valued, particularly by more educated and higher-income consumers.

The data reveal a high level of support for both TWAEM and wine tourism, especially among younger, more educated, and higher-income participants. While some scepticism exists about TWAEM's taste or health claims, it is largely limited to older or less educated respondents. Cultural services associated with wine tourism are almost universally appreciated, with the strongest support from those with specialized education and higher income.

The survey data indicate that education and income are the most consistent and significant factors shaping environmental perceptions and behaviours. While age and gender show occasional effects, particularly in climate scepticism and value-based questions, it is economic and educational capital that most reliably predict environmental awareness, pro-environmental attitudes, and partial engagement in mitigation actions like CO₂ offsetting. These findings suggest that future environmental communication and policy efforts should prioritize accessible education and incentives for low-income groups, while continuing to support informed action among higher-income, environmentally conscious citizens.

4.7 Denmark: Soil health label (UCPH)

4.7.1 Introduction and case study description

In this study, we take a different approach from the case studies already presented, where traditional discrete choice experiments are applied to estimate the value of specific attributes. Instead, our focus is on understanding the utilities and price elasticities of demand for food products with and without soil health labels, rather than estimating willingness to pay for a single attribute.

The aim of this study is to investigate the potential of introducing a new consumer-oriented soil health label on foods and, in particular, to assess the implications such a label may have for soil health business models. We do so by examining how such a label influences Danish consumers' demand for various food products in a hypothetical online supermarket setting. The underlying motivation for our investigation is the idea that demand for food can be shaped by consumers' beliefs and/or knowledge about how food production impacts ecosystem services, including soil health. Theoretically, if consumers have positive preferences for agricultural practices that improve soil health, this should be reflected in their purchasing behaviour. More specifically, consumers should exhibit a willingness to pay a price premium for food products that are produced under such agricultural practices compared to conventionally produced food products. In this context, it would constitute a potential soil health business model if farmers can pass (part of) the additional costs of implementing soil health practices on to the consumers by increasing prices to a level that consumers would accept given the improved soil health is of value to them.

While some studies have explored consumer preferences for soil functions like carbon sequestration, flood protection, and water infiltration (Bartkowski et al., 2022; Franceschinis et al., 2023), research examining the role of soil health labels on consumer demand for food in the context of promoting ecosystem services is lacking. Our study fills this gap by developing a soil health label depicting soil health improving practices that can be adopted and implemented by farmers to enhance ecosystem services. While there are various practices that improve soil health, in this study we develop a soil health label based on practices involving no or reduced tillage, continuous soil cover with plants, more diverse crop rotations, and the integration of crop and livestock production (FAO, 2014; Meunier et al., 2024; Peigné et al., 2016). These practices are recommended as part of sustainable land management and have been associated with positive environmental and agricultural yield indicators (Bai et al., 2018; Kassam et al., 2019; Krupek et al., 2022; Palm et al., 2014; Pittelkow et al., 2015). For example, in a Danish context Vestergaard (2023) calculated the climate effects of no or reduced tillage, continuous soil cover, and diverse crop rotations, showing that

these practices can enhance soil carbon sequestration and benefit other environmental outcomes.

As discussed by Caputo and Lusk (2022), survey-based discrete choice experiments are increasingly used to elicit consumer demand for food. While these methods offer advantages, such as the ability to estimate the value of specific attributes, they also come with limitations. For example, they present simplified choice scenarios where consumers typically select from a limited set of alternatives versions of a given food product, whereas real-world food decisions often involve preparing meals by combining multiple food products. To address this, Caputo and Lusk (2022) proposed the basket-based choice experiment (BBCE), a more realistic method that captures consumers' substitution and complementarity patterns among a wide range of food items in a supermarket-like setting. This approach is particularly useful for predicting demand shifts due to price changes.

In this study, we apply the BBCE approach to estimate demand for soil health-labelled foods and analyse substitution and complementarity patterns between labelled and unlabelled items. Using a hypothetical online supermarket setup featuring 28 available food products, survey respondents are asked to shop for ingredients to prepare one of the three common dinner dishes in Denmark, i.e., either burger, chicken with vegetables, or spaghetti Bolognese, depending on which of these meals they have prepared most frequently in the past year. Each participant is subjected to nine different shopping tasks, each with the same range of food products available, but where the prices of the products vary from task to task. This design allows us to address the following key questions: What are consumers' utilities for soil health-labelled foods? How does the label influence substitution or complementarity patterns in food choices? How does a price change affect demand for these and other food products? These insights can help policymakers understand the market potential of soil health labels and if consumers value foods produced with explicit soil health practices.

4.7.2 Method

Study design: The method applied in this study is grounded in classical consumer utility maximization theory (Palma and Hess. 2022). This framework posits that consumers make choices among several products, with their decisions influenced by both their total budget and the prices of the products under consideration. In addition, consumer decisions are affected by the substitutability and complementarity of the products. Since consumers make choices among multiple products in their daily lives, a method capable of addressing multi-product choice problems is required. As noted above, the BBCE is well-suited to this purpose in studies of consumer demand for food

(Caputo & Lusk, 2022). The approach begins with the recognition that food choices often involve patterns of complementarity and substitution. Thus, a method that allows consumers to select individual food items or combinations of items to create a desired meal is essential. While consumers make choices in the BBCE similar to those in a standard discrete choice experiment, the BBCE additionally enables them to indicate the quantity of products they wish to select or consume. Moreover, it explicitly accounts for substitution (choosing one product over another) and complementarity (pairing products together).

In a typical food-related BBCE, consumers are presented with several choice sets, each containing multiple food products that can be combined to form a meal. These choice sets are identical except for variations in price. Consumers are generally asked to disclose their food expenditure budget, and when making their choices, they are reminded of this budget – an approach that enhances the realism of the study. The BBCE method is not yet common in the food preference literature, but interest in its application is growing. The few studies that have employed it (Caputo & Lusk, 2022; Kilders et al., 2024; Neill & Lahne, 2022) concluded that the BBCE enables the measurement of substitution and complementarity effects, as well as price elasticities, which can be used to predict demand shifts resulting from price changes. Such findings are valuable for policymaking, as they can reveal, for example, whether increased consumption (or increased price) of one type of food leads to increased or decreased consumption of another.

Consistent with Caputo and Lusk (2022), we designed a consumer food shopping scenario in which respondents are asked to purchase ingredients to prepare a dinner meal for their household. To provide a diverse range of meal options, we included three meal options that are among the most commonly consumed dinner dishes in Denmark, based on a 2023 national food culture survey (Madkulturen, 2023): burgers, chicken with vegetables, and a pasta dish, specifically, spaghetti Bolognese¹. For each dish, we identified seven main ingredients, offering both meat and plant-based alternatives where relevant to ensure that the shopping scenario reflects real-world conditions in which consumers can choose between alternative food products. Table 16 summarizes the considered meals and their corresponding ingredients which were available in shopping situations. Respondents are assumed to have basic ingredients, such as salt and oil, at home, and they were explicitly reminded of this during the survey. Although additional ingredients may be used to prepare each meal in Table 16, we limited the number of main ingredients to seven to reduce the number of

¹ We acknowledge that this dish may be inspired by, but is not the same as, the authentic tagliatelle al ragu served in Bologna.

parameters to be estimated, consistent with Caputo & Lusk (2022), Kilders et al. (2024), and Neill & Lahne (2022).

TABLE 16. MEALS AND THEIR MAIN INGREDIENTS

Burgers	Chicken with vegetables	Spaghetti Bolognese
Beef burger patties (500g)	Chicken breast (500g)	Minced beef (500g)
Chicken breast (500g)	Plant-based mince (500g)	Minced chicken (500g)
Plant-based burger patties (500g)	Potatoes (500g)	Plant-based mince (500g)
Burger buns (300g)	Lettuce (1 piece)	Pasta (500g)
Lettuce (1 piece)	Onions (1kg)	Onions (1kg)
Tomatoes (500g)	Tomatoes (500g)	Chopped tomatoes (400g in can)
Cucumber (1 piece)	Bell pepper (1 piece)	Carrots (500g)

Note: Beef burger patties, chicken breast, and plant-based burger patties are expected to be substitutes for burgers; chicken breast and plant-based mince for chicken with vegetables; and minced beef, minced chicken, and plant-based mince for spaghetti Bolognese.

To investigate the role of a soil health label in consumer demand for food, each product listed in Table 16 is available in four variants: conventional, soil health labelled, organic, and organic with a soil health label. These variants represent the different farming practices that farmers can use when cultivating the respective food ingredients. As part of the consumer food shopping scenario, descriptions of the four variants are presented to respondents during data collection. Table 17 provides these descriptions. We included the organic label to capture, as fully as possible, the main food variants available in Danish grocery stores. Many food ingredients are offered in both organic and non-organic versions, and the purchase and consumption of organic products is growing in Denmark.

TABLE 17. DETAILED DESCRIPTIONS OF THE FOUR INGREDIENT VARIANTS.

Ingredient variant	Description	Food label
Conventional	In conventional production (the most common form of agriculture in Denmark), food is cultivated with general consideration for the soil's ability to support agricultural production in the long term. However, no specific attention is given to broader aspects of soil health, and there are no explicit requirements related to soil health in the cultivation practices	Not available
Soil health labelled	This type of production requires farmers to implement specific measures aimed at promoting soil health. These include reduced ploughing, more frequent crop rotation, maintaining continuous plant cover, or integrating crops and livestock. Imagine that food produced in this way will, in the future, be labelled with a new icon, a plant symbol with soil, which can be seen here.	
Organic	In organic production, food is cultivated without the use of synthetic fertilizers or pesticides. Instead, farmers must focus on natural substances and processes – for example, combining crops with livestock or rotating crops from year to year – so that the soil can support food production in a way that benefits the environment, people, and animals. Food produced in this way is labelled with the red Ø-label.	
organic with a soil health label	It is possible to combine organic farming with specific measures aimed at promoting soil health. Food produced in this way will be labelled with both labels.	

The soil health practices that farmers can implement on their land are described in Table 18. These practices were identified through literature review and expert consultations. Before viewing the descriptions, respondents were introduced to the potential negative effects of intensive agriculture on soil health and how farmers can help reverse it. This was explained as follows:

“Intensive farming practices can damage soil health, for example, through excessive ploughing or by growing the same crops year after year. However, farmers can actively promote healthy soil by implementing various targeted measures when cultivating their land.”

TABLE 18. SOIL HEALTH IMPROVING PRACTICES CONSIDERED IN THIS STUDY.

Soil health improving practice	Description
No or reduced tillage	Farmers can reduce or completely avoid ploughing their agricultural land to minimize soil disturbance, leaving crop residues such as leaves, stems, and roots on the soil surface. This helps preserve the soil structure and its microorganisms and can also increase the amount of organic matter in the soil.
Continuous plant cover	Farmers can ensure that living plants cover their agricultural land throughout the year to protect the soil from erosion caused by wind and rain. This helps restore and maintain the organic matter in the soil.
More diverse crop rotation	Farmers can rotate different crops more frequently than usual. This can help reduce plant diseases and pests and contribute to maintaining a good balance of nutrients in the soil.
Combining Crop Cultivation and Livestock Farming	Farmers often have the opportunity to both grow crops and keep livestock, such as cows or pigs, on the same land at different times. For example, animals can graze on fields with cover crops. Manure from the animals naturally adds nutrients to the soil, and their trampling can improve soil structure and conditions for microorganisms.

For the food shopping scenario to function effectively, the price of each product must be specified. Using scanner purchase data, market price assessments, and input from two focus group interviews (each with eight participants), we identified three price levels for each product to reflect realistic potential market fluctuations, such as discounts, inflation, or other influencing factors. These prices reflect real market values, enhancing the realism of the BBCE in this study. With four variants for each of the seven main food products, we created a BBCE design containing 28 products in each food shopping scenario for each meal context. Consistent with previous BBCE studies (e.g. Caputo & Lusk, 2022), an orthogonal fractional factorial design with 81 food shopping tasks (food basket choice questions) was produced for each meal, ensuring that the price levels are uncorrelated across shopping tasks. To minimize cognitive fatigue, the 81 shopping tasks were divided into 9 blocks, with each respondent completing 9 shopping tasks. Focus group interviews confirmed that respondents could process 9 shopping tasks within a reasonable time frame, and no negative reactions were observed during the focus group interviews. Each shopping task was identical except for the prices, which varied across questions (see Table A1 in the

Appendix for the price ranges). An example of one of the shopping tasks for burgers is shown in Figure 6 (in Danish). The focus group interviews also confirmed that the ingredient lists for each dish, as well as the pictorial presentation of the ingredients, were understandable to respondents who may not necessarily have expertise or prior knowledge related to the topic.

Which of the following food items would you buy to prepare burgers for dinner for your household? Remember, the items you choose will count toward your weekly food budget, which you previously indicated to be approximately (XXX) DKK/week. Imagine that you already have some additional ingredients (such as dressing, cheese, bacon, etc.) at home.

Hypothetical food shopping scenario descriptions: The hypothetical food shopping scenario centred on preparing a dinner meal. The scenario begins by informing respondents that farmers can adopt the soil health improving practices described earlier. Although some farmers already use these practices, there are currently no labelling mechanisms indicating soil health considerations on food products in Denmark. Before participating in the BBCE, respondents were asked to choose one of the three meals, i.e. burgers, chicken with vegetables, or spaghetti Bolognese, that they had prepared for dinner in their household within the past year. If they had prepared more than one of these meals, they were asked to select the one they had prepared most recently. If they had not prepared any of the three, they were randomly assigned to one of the meals. Depending on the selected meal, respondents were directed to the corresponding shopping scenario in the BBCE. Respondents were also asked to provide their weekly food budget, which they were reminded of during the BBCE. The subsequent scenario description then focuses on their selected meal. Next, respondents were told to imagine that they are in a grocery store shopping for ingredients to prepare their selected meal for dinner for their household. They were also instructed to imagine that the store carries only the foods typically used to make that meal.

However, each food item is available in four different variants, corresponding to the four soil-health improving practices described earlier, and all the food items are produced in Denmark. They were then presented with the first food-basket choice question where they were asked:

“Which of the following food items would you buy to prepare (meal) for dinner for your household? Remember, the items you choose will count toward your weekly food budget, which you previously indicated to be approximately [XXX] DKK/week. Imagine that you already have some additional ingredients (such as dressing, cheese, bacon, oil, salt etc.) at home.”

FIGURE 6. AN EXAMPLE OF A FOOD BASKET SHOPPING SITUATION.

The BBCE online supermarket software allows respondents to see the types and total number of food products selected, as well as the total price, similar to online shopping systems used in real market settings. During focus group interviews, participants indicated that there should not be too much information provided before the first shopping task, as they preferred to gain experience by answering the first question before proceeding to subsequent ones. Therefore, we moved some of the explanatory

text about the shopping experiment to appear after the first shopping task. At that point, respondents were presented with the following text:

“In the following questions, you will be presented with several shopping situations that are very similar to each other. However, you should consider them as completely independent. For example, you can think of them as shopping trips spread out over different times during the coming year. You are asked to indicate which products you would buy in each situation. The same products will be available in each shopping situation, but the prices will vary from one situation to the next – just like in real stores, where prices also fluctuate, for example depending on whether a particular item is on sale or not. It is important that, as far as possible, you make your choices in the same way as you would if you were actually shopping in a real grocery store. So if you think some of the items are too expensive compared to what you would actually be willing to pay, you always have the option to not buy them. You can also choose not to buy anything at all.”

Respondents then completed the remaining eight food basket choice questions.

Data collection: The sample frame for the data collection included Danish citizens aged 18 to 70 years. In preparation for the main data collection, four key steps were undertaken: First, the questionnaire was tested through two focus group interviews to assess its content and ensure it was understandable to respondents. The outcome of this step revealed the need for a few changes, for example, removing questions deemed irrelevant and reducing the amount of information provided in the BBCE related to food shopping. Second, once the questionnaire had been validated through the focus groups, it was implemented online using a Python-based open-source software called oTree, hosted on the UCloud server (a cloud-based supercomputer) administered by the University of Southern Denmark (<https://docs.cloud.sdu.dk/>). Third, a random – and thus, representative – sample of 60,000 individuals was drawn from the Danish Civil Registration System (CPR) via the Danish Health Data Authority. Because this process involved handling personal data, permission was obtained from the University of Copenhagen’s legal department. Invitation letters with personalized links to the online questionnaire were sent via e-Boks – a secure digital mailbox mandatory for all Danish citizens aged 15 and above. Fourth, a pilot study was conducted with 2,500 respondents to evaluate the technical functionality of the BBCE and obtain initial survey response rate. The results of the pilot study indicated that the setup worked as expected and that a 10% response rate could be achieved.

TABLE 19. SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC DISTRIBUTIONS (IN PERCENTAGES) AND REPRESENTATIVITY OF SAMPLES.

Variable	Burgers	Chicken with vegetable	Spaghetti Bolognese	Danish population	Significance (<i>Chi-square</i> test)
Gender					(NS) (*), (*)
Female	48.27	59.9	54.65	50.2	
Male	50.06	39.8	44.64	49.8	
Other	0.67	0.28	0.71	-	
Age					(*), (*), (*)
Under 35	18.1	11.7	16.7		
35-54	38.0	29.6	35.4	36.0	
Over 54	43.9	58.7	47.9	31.0	
Household size					(*), (*), (*)
1	17.9	21.8	22.1	18	
2 or more	82.1	78.2	77.9	82	
Education					(*), (*), (*)
Primary school	7.1	4.4	5.2	26	
Upper secondary or Vocational	27.3	21.7	24.4	42	
Higher education	65.6	73.9	70.4	32	
Yearly gross income^a in DKK²					(*), (*), (*)
Under 200.000	5.2	6.3	7.4	15	
200.000-399.999	16.6	19.9	19.4	35	
400.000-599.999	21.5	21.9	22.3	18	
600.000 and above	45.9	41.4	41.7	31	

Note: The last column reports tests for sample representativity of the Danish population. The three sets of parentheses in the last column correspond to the three samples from the three meals, meaning that each sample's distribution is tested against the distribution of the Danish population using the chi-square test. (NS) indicates no significant difference, while (*) indicates that the difference between the sample distribution and the Danish population distribution of the socio-demographic variable is statistically significant at the 1% level or lower. ^a Around 10% of the respondents answered "I don't know" or "I do not want to answer" to the question about their yearly gross income. Hence, the percentage distribution reported for the samples here do not sum to 100. The chi-square test is based only the income distribution of those who have answered the question.

The main data collection took place between April and June 2025. A total of 5,386 fully completed responses were obtained after sending one reminder, resulting in an overall response rate of 10%, which aligns with the findings from the pilot study. These responses were distributed across the three meal types as follows: 1,794 for burgers,

² DKK is Danish kroner. 100DKK ~ 13,4EUR.

1,792 for chicken with vegetables, and 2108 for spaghetti Bolognese. Because data collection was conducted in three waves to achieve roughly equal sample sizes, the spaghetti Bolognese meal received a disproportionately larger number of responses. To test the robustness of our analysis, we tried randomly removing around 300 respondents from this sample, but the results did not change markedly, so we chose to retain the full sample. In addition, in the econometric analysis described below, we removed anomalous responses in which participants made random or inconsistent choices – for example, selecting burger patties without also selecting burger buns, which violated the survey design requiring respondents to choose at least one type of bun to form a burger meal. The sample characteristics across the three meals are shown in Table 19.

Although we obtained a representative sample from the Danish Health Data Authority, our final sample is only representative of the Danish population in terms of gender for the burger sample. This suggests the presence of a self-selection. Because respondents were not randomly assigned to the three meal contexts – rather, they chose a meal based on their prior experience – we do not expect to observe balance in the three meal samples across characteristics.

Econometric analysis: We analyse our data using a conceptual framework for multi-product consumer choice, based on Neill and Lahne (2022), Palma and Hess (2022), and the literature cited therein. The decision of what and how much to choose is commonly framed as a discrete-continuous choice problem. Consumer choice often involves selecting among combinations of products, a complex decision that can be conceptualized using classical consumer utility maximization theory (Palma & Hess, 2022). Accordingly, a consumer n must decide which product d to purchase. The utility maximization problem can thus be expressed as:

$$\text{Max}_{x_n} u_0(x_{n0}) + \sum_{d=1}^D u_d(x_{nd}) + \sum_{d=1}^{D-1} \sum_{l=d+1}^D u_{dl}(x_{nd}, x_{nl}) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{subject to budget constraint: } x_{n0}p_{n0} + \sum_{d=1}^D x_{nd}p_{nd} = G_n \quad (2)$$

Where n represents consumers, with $n = 1, \dots, N$, d indexes alternative products, with $d = 1, \dots, D$, x_{n0} represents the amount of an outside or numeraire good consumed, x_{nd} is the quantity consumed of alternative d , x_{nl} is the quantity consumed of alternative l , p_{nd} is the price of alternative d , and G_n is the consumer's total budget. Since we focus on consumer demand for food, the inside good in our analysis refers to d , that is, the

consumption of food (e.g., ingredients for a burger, chicken, or spaghetti Bolognese dish). The outside good includes any goods consumed other than the inside good (e.g., transport, leisure, housing) (Palma & Hess, 2022).

The utility maximization problem in Equation (1) can be broken down into three parts for ease of understanding: the utility of the outside good $u_0(x_{n0})$, the utility of the inside good $u_d(x_{nd})$, and the utility of combinations of the inside goods. We refer the reader to Palma and Hess (2022) for a detailed econometric specification. Based on Equation 1 above, analysts are interested in estimating three key parameters: the base utility for alternative d, the satiation parameter for the same alternative, and the interaction parameters, which indicate substitution or complementary effects. The base utility is defined as the marginal utility at zero consumption, i.e., the utility associated with the initial unit of consumption of selected ingredients. This is also referred to as the scale of utility for a product, in our case, alternative d. The satiation parameter represents the utility obtained from subsequent consumption of a product, with higher values indicate greater consumption of alternative d. The interaction parameter captures complementarity and substitution effects. A positive value indicates a complementary relationship, i.e. that consumption of one alternative increases the consumption of the other. A negative value indicates a substitution effect, i.e., that consumption of one alternative reduces the consumption of the other. We use the extended multiple discrete continuous extreme value model to properly estimate these three key parameters (see Palma & Hess, 2022 for a detailed presentation of this model).

Due to the complexity of the model and the large number of parameters than can be estimated in the extended Multiple Discrete-Continuous Extreme Value model, Palma and Hess (2022) provide guiding principles to support model identification and improve performance. First, they introduce a version of the model that does not require a budget constraint in the estimation. They argue that food expenditure may represent only a small fraction of total expenditure, with the outside good accounting for the majority. Therefore, a model that does not rely on a budget constraint may be more appropriate than one that does. Second, Palma and Hess (2022) suggest that model identification and convergence can be improved by limiting the number of interaction parameters, i.e., the parameters which represent substitution and complementarity effects. This can be achieved by defining a single parameter for a group of similar products or by fixing some interaction parameters, e.g., those considered less relevant for substitution and complementarity, to zero.

In this study, we estimate the interaction parameters for within-product interactions defined by the different food labels (e.g., soil health-labelled, organic, and soil health- and organic-labelled beef burger patties) to investigate the role of the soil health label

in influencing substitution and complementarity effects. The interaction parameters for products not belonging to the same food group (e.g., soil health-labelled beef burger patties versus soil health-labelled burger buns) are fixed to zero. Furthermore, to reduce dimensionality, we aggregate products within the same food group. For example, burgers can be prepared with beef patties, chicken breast, or plant-based patties, which are therefore collapsed into a single product. We tested several model specifications in which varying numbers of products with similar functions (e.g., burger patties or vegetables) were collapsed. Ultimately, we selected models that were not overly restrictive in terms of the number of interaction parameters and in which only protein components were collapsed (i.e., the different patties for burgers, chicken breast and plant-based mince for the chicken with vegetable dish, and meat and plant-based mince for spaghetti Bolognese) to ensure consistency across meal contexts.

Finally, because the interaction parameters capture only cross-utility effects and not price sensitivity (Caputo & Lusk, 2022; Richards et al., 2018), we also calculate price elasticities to assess how the demand for soil health-labelled products respond to changes in their own prices and the prices of other product variations. This allows us to better understand the extent to which demand for foods carrying a soil health label is influenced by price changes.

4.7.3 Survey results

We present results from both descriptive and parametric analyses. The descriptive analysis examines the choice frequency of food ingredients, specifically conventional, soil health-labelled, organic, and those labelled with both the soil health and the organic label.

Descriptive analysis: The choice frequencies for ingredients in burgers, chicken with vegetables, and spaghetti Bolognese are shown in Figures 7, 8 and 9, respectively. These frequencies are calculated as the percentage of times a product is chosen, i.e., the total number of times it is selected divided by the total number of times it is available. As shown in the figures, in most cases, products labelled with both the soil health and the organic farming label were chosen more frequently than the others. This is particularly true for plant-based ingredients, suggesting that respondents may have recognized their direct association with soils, as their growth depends on soils in general and soil health in particular. The soil health label without the organic label did not attract more choices compared to conventional farming, with choice frequencies being almost the same or even lower than for conventional options. However, in the case of the chicken meal, this label was chosen more frequently for five out of seven ingredients.

FIGURE 7. CHOICE FREQUENCIES OF INGREDIENTS FOR BURGERS.

FIGURE 8. CHOICE FREQUENCIES OF INGREDIENTS FOR CHICKEN WITH VEGETABLES.

FIGURE 9. CHOICE FREQUENCIES OF INGREDIENTS FOR SPAGHETTI BOLOGNESE.

Parametric analysis: Overall, with only a few exceptions, baseline utilities tend to increase in order from conventional products, to soil health labelled, organic labelled, and finally to both soil health and organic farming labelled. Notably, the difference in utility between conventional and soil health labelled product versions is minimal, suggesting that respondents make only weak distinctions between these two categories at the point of zero consumption; that is, the utility associated with placing the very first unit of either product version in the basket (i.e., initial consumption) is similar.

TABLE 20. BASELINE UTILITY (MARGINAL UTILITY AT ZERO CONSUMPTION) FOR MEAL INGREDIENTS

Burger		Chicken with vegetables		Spaghetti Bolognese	
Ingredient	Estimate	Ingredient	Estimate	Ingredient	Estimate
Beef burger patties		Chicken breast		Minced beef	
Conventional	3.337 (0.017)***	Conventional	3.324 (0.018)***	Conventional	3.662 (0.012)***
Soil health	3.405 (0.015)***	Soil health-labelled	3.688 (0.015)***	Soil health-labelled	3.855 (0.013)***
Organic	3.586 (0.015)***	Organic	3.997 (0.016)***	Organic	4.056 (0.014)***
Soil health + organic	3.757 (0.016)***	Soil health + organic	4.229 (0.017)***	Soil health + organic	4.117 (0.018)***
Chicken breast		Plant-based mince		Minced chicken	
Conventional	2.865 (0.019)***	Conventional	2.654 (0.030)***	Conventional	2.996 (0.019)***
Soil health	3.147 (0.020)***	Soil health-labelled	3.019 (0.023)***	Soil health-labelled	3.452 (0.021)***
Organic	3.428 (0.022)***	Organic	3.161 (0.022)***	Organic	3.753 (0.027)***
Soil health + organic	3.694 (0.023)***	Soil health + organic	3.423 (0.022)***	Soil health + organic	3.990 (0.029)***
Plant-based patties		Potatoes		Plant-based mince	
Conventional	2.622 (0.029)***	Conventional	2.095 (0.024)***	Conventional	2.814 (0.022)***
Soil health	2.851 (0.025)***	Soil health-labelled	2.317 (0.019)***	Soil health-labelled	3.042 (0.019)***
Organic	2.983 (0.023)***	Organic	2.579 (0.019)***	Organic	3.212 (0.020)***
Soil health + organic	3.324 (0.021)***	Soil health + organic	2.929 (0.019)***	Soil health + organic	3.479 (0.021)***
Burger buns		Lettuce		Pasta	
Conventional	2.839 (0.019)***	Conventional	1.529 (0.028)***	Conventional	2.241 (0.019)***
Soil health	2.890 (0.018)***	Soil health	1.756 (0.022)***	Soil health	2.276 (0.018)***
Organic	3.018 (0.017)***	Organic	1.989 (0.019)***	Organic	2.447 (0.018)***
Soil health + organic	3.324 (0.018)***	Soil health + organic	2.446 (0.021)***	Soil health + organic	2.821 (0.016)***
Lettuce		Onion		Potatoes	
Conventional	2.055 (0.024)***	Conventional	1.838 (0.026)***	Conventional	2.134 (0.019)***
Soil health	2.041 (0.022)***	Soil health	2.059 (0.023)***	Soil health	2.123 (0.017)***
Organic	2.208 (0.020)***	Organic	2.270 (0.021)***	Organic	2.431 (0.017)***
Soil health + organic	2.611 (0.019)***	Soil health + organic	2.770 (0.023)***	Soil health + organic	2.667 (0.015)***

Tomatoes		Tomatoes		Chopped tomatoes	
Conventional	2.919 (0.021)***	Conventional	2.649 (0.023)***	Conventional	2.273 (0.017)***
Soil health	2.979 (0.019)***	Soil health	2.963 (0.020)***	Soil health	2.346 (0.017)***
Organic	3.190 (0.018)***	Organic	3.178 (0.019)***	Organic	2.571 (0.015)***
Soil health + organic	3.444(0.019)***	Soil health + organic	3.458 (0.021)***	Soil health + organic	2.782 (0.016)***
Cucumber		Bell peppers		Carrots	
Conventional	1.858 (0.023)***	Conventional	1.832 (0.027)***	Conventional	1.954 (0.023)***
Soil health-labelled	1.850 (0.020)***	Soil health	1.956 (0.027)***	Soil health	2.035 (0.019)***
Organic	2.107 (0.019)***	Organic	2.436 (0.023)***	Organic	2.291 (0.019)***
Soil health + organic	2.433 (0.019)***	Soil health + organic	2.664 (0.023)***	Soil health + organic	2.656 (0.017)***

Note: Standard errors in parenthesis. '***' indicates statistical significance at 1% or lower critical value.

The baseline utilities do not capture how well a product combines with others, which necessitates estimating substitution and/or complementarity effects. Tables 21, 22 and 23 present cross-utility estimates showing the interaction effects or joint effects of having two ingredients in a basket. The results confirm that the different product versions function as substitutes, as the estimated coefficients are generally negative, and most of these substitution effects are statistically significant. This aligns with expectations: ingredients within the same group (e.g., chicken breast with a soil health label and chicken breast with an organic label) typically serve the same purpose, even if they carry different labels.

TABLE 21. CROSS-UTILITY ESTIMATES FOR BURGER DISH INGREDIENTS.

Change in utility of purchasing				
Burger patties	Conventional	Soil health	Organic	Soil health + organic
Conventional	0.000	-14.159 (0.269)***	-19.644 (0.392)***	-27.881 (0.509)***
Soil health	-14.159 (0.269)***	0.000	-14.635 (0.325)***	-21.571 (0.401)***
Organic	-19.644 (0.392)***	-14.635 (0.325)***	0.000	-17.717 (0.932)***
Soil health + organic	-27.881 (0.509)***	-21.571 (0.401)***	-17.717 (0.932)***	0.000
Burger buns				
Conventional	0.000	-20.272 (0.347)**	-21.582 (0.369)***	-25.874 (0.459)***
Soil health	-20.272 (0.347)**	0.000	-17.145 (0.339)***	-28.154 (0.509)***
Organic	-21.582 (0.369)***	-17.145 (0.339)***	0.000	-23.571 (0.438)***
Soil health + organic	-25.874 (0.459)***	-28.154 (0.509)***	-23.571 (0.438)***	0.000
Lettuce				
Conventional	0.000	-13.995 (0.248)***	-10.461 (0.174)***	-22.002 (0.366)***
Soil health	-13.995 (0.248)***	0.000	-11.100 (0.224)***	-11.455 (0.233)***
Organic	-10.461 (0.174)***	-11.100 (0.224)***	0.000	-12.390 (0.207)***
Soil health + organic	-22.002 (0.366)***	-11.455 (0.233)***	-12.390 (0.207)***	0.000
Tomatoes				
Conventional	0.000	-21.739 (0.396)***	-33.255 (0.600)***	0.000
Soil health	-21.739 (0.396)***	0.000	-23.648 (0.472)***	-28.364 (0.548)***
Organic	-33.255 (0.600)***	-23.648 (0.472)***	0.000	-21.862 (0.438)***
Soil health + organic	0.000	-28.364 (0.548)***	-21.862 (0.438)***	0.000
Cucumber				
Conventional	0.000	-7.044 (0.113)***	-17.873 (0.260)***	-16.849 (0.352)***
Soil health	-7.044 (0.113)***	0.000	-7.827 (0.127)***	-9.508 (0.156)***
Organic	-17.873 (0.260)***	-7.827 (0.127)***	0.000	-5.467 (0.107)***
Soil health + organic	-16.849 (0.352)***	-9.508 (0.156)***	-5.467 (0.107)***	0.000

Note: Standard errors in parenthesis. '***' indicates statistical significance at 1% or lower critical value. The interaction parameter between conventional tomato and soil health-and-organic-labelled tomato tends toward negative infinity across model specifications, including those with reduced interaction parameters by collapsing similar ingredients. Following established guidelines, we fixed this parameter to the corresponding negative value and estimated the model. Burger patties represent an ingredient category in which beef burger patties, chicken breast, and plant-based patties are collapsed to support model identification

TABLE 22. CROSS-UTILITY ESTIMATES FOR CHICKEN WITH VEGETABLE INGREDIENTS.

	Change in utility of purchasing			
Chicken breast or plant-based mince	Conventional	Soil health	Organic	Soil health + organic
Conventional	0.000	-34.962 (1.006)***	-21.157 (0.894)***	-23.259 (0.806)***
Soil health-labelled	-34.962 (1.006)***	0.000	-15.691 (0.507)***	-35.687 (1.231)***
Organic	-21.157 (0.894)***	-15.691 (0.507)***	0.000	-41.183 (1.285)***
Soil health + organic	-23.259 (0.806)***	-35.687 (1.231)***	-41.183 (1.285)***	0.000
Potato				
Conventional	0.000	-12.269 (0.168)***	-11.709 (0.316)***	-12.406 (0.310)***
Soil health-labelled	-12.269 (0.168)***	0.000	-4.552 (0.153)***	-11.572 (0.314)***
Organic	-11.709 (0.316)***	-4.552 (0.153)***	0.000	-13.633 (0.406)***
Soil health + organic	-12.406 (0.310)***	-11.572 (0.314)***	-13.633 (0.406)***	0.000
Lettuce				
Conventional	0.000	-5.447 (0.208)***	-8.249 (0.301)***	-11.120 (0.434)***
Soil health-labelled	-5.447 (0.208)***	0.000	-5.834 (0.252)***	-7.117 (0.259)***
Organic	-8.249 (0.301)***	-5.834 (0.252)***	0.000	-7.522 (0.259)***
Soil health + organic	-11.120 (0.434)***	-7.117 (0.259)***	-7.522 (0.259)***	0.000
Onions				
Conventional	0.000	-8.716 (0.356)***	-9.573 (0.258)***	-15.929 (0.533)***
Soil health-labelled	-8.716 (0.356)***	0.000	-8.216 (0.336)***	-17.359 (0.484)***
Organic	-9.573 (0.258)***	-8.216 (0.336)***	0.000	-15.195 (0.467)***
Soil health + organic	-15.929 (0.533)***	-17.359 (0.484)***	-15.195 (0.467)***	0.000
Tomatoes				
Conventional	0.000	-26.459 (1.069)***	-17.352 (0.649)***	-25.254 (0.871)***
Soil health-labelled	-26.459 (1.069)***	0.000	-20.319 (0.808)***	-30.265 (0.923)***
Organic	-17.352 (0.649)***	-20.319 (0.808)***	0.000	-30.616 (1.357)***
Soil health + organic	-25.254 (0.871)***	-30.265 (0.923)***	-30.616 (1.357)***	0.000
Bell peppers				
Conventional	0.000	-10.769 (0.440)***	-11.267 (0.512)***	-10.565 (0.513)***
Soil health-labelled	-10.769 (0.440)***	0.000	-3.896 (0.454)***	-14.899 (0.799)***
Organic	-11.267 (0.512)***	-3.896 (0.454)***	0.000	-13.297 (0.447)***
Soil health + organic	-10.565 (0.513)***	-14.899 (0.799)***	-13.297 (0.447)***	0.000

Note: Standard errors in parenthesis. '***' indicates statistical significance at 1% or lower critical value. Chicken breast or plant-based mince represent an ingredient category where chicken breast and plant-based mince are collapsed together to support model identification.

The fact that cross-utilities vary across ingredients and labels indicates that respondents did not consistently purchase only a single product version in all shopping situations. In other words, they sometimes purchased combinations of ingredients within the same product category (e.g., beef burger patties).

TABLE 23. CROSS-UTILITY ESTIMATES FOR SPAGHETTI BOLOGNESE DISH

	Change in utility of purchasing			
Meat or plant-based mince	Conventional	Soil health	Organic	Soil health + organic
Conventional	0.000	-26.702 (1.152)***	-29.628 (0.459)***	-28.418 (0.730)***
Soil health-labelled	-26.702 (1.152)***	0.000	-23.324 (0.608)***	-45.624 (1.255)***
Organic	-29.628 (0.459)***	-23.324 (0.608)***	0.000	-26.411 (0.711)***
Soil health + organic	-28.418 (0.730)***	-45.624 (1.255)***	-26.411 (0.711)***	0.000
Pasta				
Conventional	0.000	-11.134 (0.179)***	-11.766 (0.192)***	-34.383 (0.267)***
Soil health-labelled	-11.134 (0.179)***	0.000	-10.895 (0.219)***	-15.035 (0.242)***
Organic	-11.766 (0.192)***	-10.895 (0.219)***	0.000	-18.069 (0.289)***
Soil health + organic	-34.383 (0.267)***	-15.035 (0.242)***	-18.069 (0.289)***	0.000
Onion				
Conventional	0.000	-11.945 (0.178)***	-15.819 (0.2312)***	-12.691 (0.191)***
Soil health-labelled	-11.945 (0.178)***	0.000	-10.154 (0.159)***	-6.727 (0.121)***
Organic	-15.819 (0.2312)***	-10.154 (0.159)***	0.000	-13.335 (0.191)***
Soil health + organic	-12.691 (0.191)***	-6.727 (0.121)***	-13.335 (0.191)***	0.000
Chopped tomatoes				
Conventional	0.000	-11.715 (0.195)***	-10.753 (0.179)***	-13.466 (0.235)***
Soil health-labelled	-11.715 (0.195)***	0.000	-11.630 (0.199)***	-14.987 (0.258)***
Organic	-10.753 (0.179)***	-11.630 (0.199)***	0.000	-13.296 (0.258)***
Soil health + organic	-13.466 (0.235)***	-14.987 (0.258)***	-13.296 (0.258)***	0.000
Carrots				
Conventional	0.000	-8.434 (0.165)***	-9.964 (0.244)***	-31.008 (0.388)***
Soil health-labelled	-8.434 (0.165)***	0.000	-9.986 (0.195)***	-13.934 (0.271)***
Organic	-9.964 (0.244)***	-9.986 (0.195)***	0.000	-13.234 (0.261)***
Soil health + organic	-31.008 (0.388)***	-13.934 (0.271)***	-13.234 (0.261)***	0.000

Note: Standard errors in parenthesis. '***' indicates statistical significance at 1% or lower critical value. Meat or plant-based mince represent an ingredient category where minced beef, minced chicken and plant-based mince are collapsed together to support model identification.

For example, in the burger meal, approximately 1% of choice frequencies represent combinations of ingredients within the beef burger patties category. Such purchasing behaviour may be particularly relevant for household members with varying preferences, for example, between organic and conventional products. Overall, we observe that meat, chicken breast or mince, and plant-based proteins exhibit the largest substitution effects across labels, compared to vegetables such as lettuce, bell peppers, and cucumber. This suggests that while all four version of all products in our analysis are substitutes, vegetable categories are more likely to be purchased together across labels, whereas protein categories generate stronger negative cross-utilities and are therefore less likely to be chosen together.

Caputo and Lusk (2022), citing Richards et al. (2018), noted that the cross-utility effects (such as those presented in Tables 6–8) do not indicate substitution effects in response to price changes. For example, the substitution patterns observed in Tables 6–8 may not be driven by price effects, as these results are not based on predicted consumption. Price elasticities are better suited to capture predicted consumption responses, making it necessary to estimate them in order to understand how demand for specific ingredients changes in response to price fluctuations. This prediction is especially important for understanding how a soil health label might influence demand for different food products in the market. In other words, we aim to explore whether a soil health label can serve as a viable business model by assessing the demand for food and the implications for farmers who implement soil health practices.

We estimate both own-price and cross-price elasticities in Tables 9–11 to better understand how soil health labels affect consumer demand for food products. Focusing on burger ingredients, the own-price elasticities are all negative, suggesting that when the price of an ingredient increases by 1%, demand for that product decreases by approximately 1.927% to 3.975%. Meat and plant-based burger patties are highly price elastic compared to vegetables.

In terms of cross-price elasticities, there appears to be a strong substitution effect between conventional and soil health- or organic-labelled ingredients. Specifically, a 1% increase in the price of conventional ingredients consistently leads to greater substitution (demand) for soil health-labelled ingredients compared to other alternatives. For instance, while the demand for soil health-labelled lettuce increases by 0.319%, the corresponding increases are 0.145% for organic and only 0.019% for soil health-and-organic-labelled ingredients. There is also a strong substitution effect, i.e., higher demand for conventional ingredients when the price of ingredients carrying both soil health and organic labels increases by 1%. For example, when the price of soil health-and-organic-labelled cucumbers rise by 1%, demand for conventional cucumbers increases by 0.815%, while demand for organic cucumbers increases by

0.357%. The largest cross-price elasticities are observed for lettuce (1.196%) and tomatoes (1.367%), indicating that increasing the price of lettuce and tomatoes with both the soil health and the organic labels leads to a strong shift in demand toward conventional alternatives of similar product versions. Because the prices of these ingredients with both labels were set higher by design, further price increases are more likely to strongly shift demand toward other product versions. This is also reflected in the lower cross-price elasticities for these products when the prices of other ingredients increase by 1%. By contrast, increases in the prices of soil health-labelled ingredients without the organic label lead to only modest substitution effects, as their cross-price elasticity estimates are often lower than those of other ingredients.

TABLE 24. PRICE ELASTICITIES OF DEMAND FOR INGREDIENTS OF BURGER.

A 1% increase in price of	Percentage of change in demand for			
Burger patties	Conventional	Soil health	Organic	Soil health + organic
Conventional	-2.898	0.185	0.151	0.062
Soil health	0.085	-3.089	0.069	0.069
Organic	0.078	0.088	-3.191	0.099
Soil health + organic	0.185	0.149	0.116	-3.207
Burger buns				
Conventional	-3.975	0.375	0.361	0.237
Soil health	0.118	-3.060	0.228	0.137
Organic	0.193	0.178	-2.401	0.184
Soil health + organic	0.615	0.612	0.023	-2.229
Lettuce				
Conventional	-2.142	0.319	0.145	0.019
Soil health	0.029	-2.425	0.184	0.048
Organic	0.222	0.050	-2.282	0.178
Soil health + organic	1.196	0.605	0.058	-2.005
Tomatoes				
Conventional	-2.256	0.278	0.107	0.011
Soil health	0.084	-2.543	0.135	0.058
Organic	0.189	0.061	-2.617	0.184
Soil health + organic	1.367	0.411	0.068	-2.515
Cucumber				
Conventional	-2.166	0.332	0.148	0.011
Soil health	0.052	-2.044	0.128	0.039
Organic	0.201	0.091	-1.962	0.118
Soil health + organic	0.815	0.357	0.055	-1.927

The results for the chicken with vegetables and pasta Bolognese meals broadly mirror those for burgers. Notably, an increase in the price of conventional ingredients leads to higher demand for soil health-labelled alternatives. For example, a 1% increase in

the price of chicken breast or plant-based mince raises demand for the soil health-labelled option by 0.233%, compared to 0.120% for the organic option and 0.041% for the soil health-and-organic option. Additionally, price increases for ingredients carrying both soil health and organic labels result in higher demand for other ingredients, especially conventional ones. Price changes for soil health-labelled ingredients alone are still associated with moderate substitution effects, although the effect is slightly stronger in the case of spaghetti Bolognese.

TABLE 25. PRICE ELASTICITIES OF DEMAND FOR INGREDIENTS OF CHICKEN

A 1% increase in price of	Percentage of change in demand for			
Chicken breast or plant-based ground mince	Conventional	Soil health	Organic	Soil health + organic
Conventional	-2.400	0.233	0.120	0.041
Soil health	0.084	-2.397	0.099	0.079
Organic	0.139	0.025	-2.604	0.111
Soil health + organic	0.309	0.064	0.001	-2.563
Potatoes				
Conventional	-2.139	0.136	0.095	0.012
Soil health	0.035	-2.030	0.074	0.072
Organic	0.076	0.006	-1.866	0.142
Soil health + organic	0.550	0.111	0.007	-1.764
Lettuce				
Conventional	-2.714	0.123	0.058	0.019
Soil health	0.136	-2.696	0.001	0.060
Organic	0.339	0.143	-3.034	0.188
Soil health + organic	1.027	0.442	0.054	-1.972
Onion				
Conventional	-4.322	0.095	0.208	0.047
Soil health-labelled	0.436	-5.349	0.275	0.073
Organic	0.190	0.520	-2.040	0.107
Soil health + organic	1.638	0.330	0.007	-1.820
Tomatoes				
Conventional	-2.583	0.189	0.089	0.043
Soil health	0.068	-2.294	0.133	0.053
Organic	0.178	0.069	-2.330	0.146
Soil health + organic	0.639	0.456	0.110	-2.286
Bell pepper				
Conventional	-2.351	0.230	0.189	0.032
Soil health	0.054	-3.117	0.034	0.029
Organic	0.156	0.088	-1.985	0.159
Soil health + organic	1.509	0.521	0.226	-4.774

TABLE 26. PRICE ELASTICITIES OF DEMAND FOR INGREDIENTS OF CHICKEN

A 1% increase in price of	Percentage of change in demand for			
Meat or plant-based mince	Conventional	Soil health	Organic	Soil health + organic
Conventional	-3.028	0.405	0.193	0.197
Soil health	0.107	-3.672	0.137	0.098
Organic	0.174	0.145	-4.101	0.204
Soil health + organic	0.172	0.176	0.066	-4.819
Pasta				
Conventional	-2.167	0.388	0.160	0.025
Soil health	0.029	-2.557	0.191	0.092
Organic	0.366	0.244	-2.587	0.049
Soil health + organic	2.307	1.181	0.311	-2.613
Potatoes				
Conventional	-2.282	0.341	0.220	0.042
Soil health	0.033	-2.613	0.193	0.077
Organic	0.208	0.131	-2.255	0.057
Soil health + organic	1.380	0.662	0.177	-2.542
Chopped tomatoes				
Conventional	-4.064	0.872	0.393	0.204
Soil health	0.018	-2.442	0.166	0.061
Organic	0.385	0.078	-2.443	0.273
Soil health + organic	0.762	0.342	0.049	-2.215
Carrots				
Conventional	-2.717	0.333	0.147	0.027
Soil health	0.059	-2.803	0.160	0.049
Organic	0.292	0.143	-2.649	0.205
Soil health + organic	1.911	1.230	0.118	-2.343

4.7.4 Market potential

Our results suggest that respondents have higher baseline utilities for products carrying both soil health and organic farming labels. These products also show stronger negative cross-utilities, meaning that when chosen, they are less frequently purchased together with other product versions in the same category. Such substitution effects are more pronounced for meat and chicken-based products than for vegetables such as lettuce, bell peppers, and cucumber. Our price elasticity estimates indicate that all products, including soil health-labelled versions, have negative own-price elasticities, suggesting that respondents, as expected, are price sensitive and that demand for soil health-labelled products decreases when their price increases. Cross-price elasticities reveal that higher prices on conventional food products increase demand for soil health-labelled versions, whereas dual-labelled ingredients with both soil health and organic labels are less responsive to changes in the prices of other products. When the price of items with both labels rises, demand

shifts toward conventional and, to a lesser extent, organic product versions. In contrast, price increases for soil health-labelled ingredients alone induce only modest substitution toward other versions.

Our results have several implications for using soil health labels as a business model to enhance ecosystem services and promote sustainable agriculture. First, the finding that soil health-labelled ingredients are more appealing to respondents at the baseline level, and that they serve as substitutes for conventional, unlabelled food products, suggests that soil health labels can be applied to food products in market places. This indicates a potential role for such labels in shaping consumer choices. As a result, policies should support and create the conditions for voluntary or mandatory labelling schemes to facilitate the adoption and marketing of soil health labels. Second, although products with both soil health and organic labels are overall preferred, respondents are more likely to switch to other product versions when the prices of these dual-labelled products rise. Since these products were already priced higher than the other alternatives, this demand shift is expected, and further price increases are likely to reduce demand. Therefore, appropriate pricing mechanisms may be necessary, including incentives for organic farmers to adopt soil health-improving practices, in order to maintain market potential without further price increases. Third, because soil health-labelled products without the organic label induce only a moderate shift in demand toward other ingredients (i.e. lower cross-price elasticities), respondents may reduce or postpone consumption of these products without necessarily substituting them with conventional alternatives. However, given that soil health-labelled ingredients are highly price elastic with respect to their own price, creating and maintaining market potential requires appropriate pricing mechanisms to preserve market share and increase consumption of these ingredients.

Overall, our results can inform policymakers on how to sustain demand for soil health-labelled products by introducing, for example, subsidies for agricultural practices that improve soil health. Such subsidies are crucial for maintaining the market competitiveness of products derived from these practices, thereby encouraging consumer adoption of soil health labels on foods and creating the economic security farmers need to invest in soil health improvements. At the same time, our results imply that the price sensitivity of soil health-labelled products should be considered when policymakers design taxes on agricultural practices and products more generally.

Appendix

Table A1. Price levels of food products in DKK (Low, Medium, High)

Burgers				
Ingredients	Conventional	Soil health	Organic	Soil health + organic
Beef burger patties (500g)	25, 43, 60	33, 49, 65	40, 55, 70	48, 61, 75
Chicken breast (500g)	20, 30, 40	35, 55, 80	50, 85, 125	65, 115, 170
Plant-based burger patties (500g)	30,40,50	35,45,55	40,50,60	45,55,65
Burger buns (300g)	10, 16, 21	13,18,25	15,21,28	18,25,33
Lettuce (1 piece)	5,9,12	6,9,13	6,10,14	7,11,15
Tomatoes (500g)	12,22,32	16,26,35	20,30,38	24,34,40
Cucumber (1 piece)	4,7,10	4,9,13	5,11,17	6,13,20
Chicken with vegetables				
Chicken breast (500g)	20,30,40	35,55,80	50,85,125	65,115,170
Plant-based mince (500g)	30,45,60	35,56,77	40,67,95	45,78,112
Potatoes (500g)	6,16,25	7,18,28	8,19,30	9,21,33
Lettuce (1 piece)	5,9,12	6,9,13	6,10,14	7,11,15
Onions (1kg)	5,9,12	6,10,13	7,11,15	8,12,16
Tomatos (500g)	12,22,32	16,26,35	20,30,38	24,34,40
Bell peppers (1 piece)	5,8,11	8,10,13	10,13,15	13,15,17
Spaghetti Bolognese				
Minced beef (500g)	30,45,60	50,60,70	70,75,8	90,95,100
Minced chicken (500g)	25,43,58	55,75,90	85,110,130	110,140,170
Plant-based mince (500g)	30,45,60	35,56,77	40,67,95	45,78,112
Pasta (500g)	5,7,10	7,8,11	8,10,12	9,11,13
Onions (1kg)	5,9,12	6,10,13	7,11,15	8,12,16
Chopped tomatoes (400g in can)	6,8,10	7,12,15	8,13,18	9,15,22
Carrots (500g)	5,8,10	6, 9, 11	7, 10, 12	9, 11, 13

4.8 Italy: “Sustainability District of the Sandy Soil Area of the Po Delta in the Emilia-Romagna Region” (IDECO)

4.8.1 Introduction and case study description

The case study "Sustainability District of the Sandy Soil Area of the Po Delta in the Emilia-Romagna Region" aims to foster local development, competitiveness, business collaboration in the sandy soil area, and the dissemination of a culture of agri-environmental sustainability among consumers. Collaboration between businesses aims to maintain an active dialogue with local institutions regarding threats to the fertility and health of sandy soils. The creation of a Food District represents an innovative business model for the health of sandy soils in the Emilia-Romagna Region. The "Food District" strategy is identified in Regional Council Resolution No. 1816 of October 28, 2019. The document identifies various methodologies for territorial aggregation. Our case study focuses on the "Sustainability District" typology, i.e., "local production systems characterized by the presence of cultivation, livestock farming, processing, food preparation, and agro-industrial activities carried out using organic methods or in compliance with environmental sustainability criteria, in accordance with current European, national, and regional legislation."

The case study's operational area encompasses several municipalities in the province of Ferrara: Mesola, Goro, Codigoro, Lagosanto, Comacchio, and Ostellato; the municipalities cover a usable agricultural area of approximately 18,600 hectares. Part of the area falls within the Emilia-Romagna Po Delta Park, which was recognized as a Biosphere Reserve under the UNESCO MaB Programme in 2015. The operational area highlights the potential for promoting the products and businesses associated with it, which share the presence of sandy soils, a distinctive element compared to all other areas of the region (Figures 10-11). This area has always been characterized by a strong agricultural and rural-tourist vocation.

FIGURE 10. NATIONAL TERRITORIAL FRAMEWORK OF THE CASE STUDY “EMILIA-ROMAGNA REGION SAND AREA”.

FIGURE 11. PILOT CASE AREA, PROVINCE OF FERRARA (EMILIA-ROMANA REGION)

The main crops grown in the sandy area are potatoes, carrots, tomatoes, durum wheat, common wheat, and fruit nurseries. In these areas, cultivated soil is often located more than 2 meters below sea level. The soil is classified as sandy because its sand content exceeds 60%. Sandy soils are poorly structured, light, and loose, with limited water retention and high permeability, as well as low organic matter content. These characteristics require careful soil management to preserve its physical, chemical, and microbiological properties, allowing farms operating in the area to continue to produce high-quality, environmentally and economically sustainable crops well into the future.

The sandy soils in the study area are characterized by two critical issues:

- salinization and salt ingression, which lead to reduced yields (Figure 12);
- low organic matter content (Figure 13).

Salt ingressión is caused by denser, salty seawater coming into contact with coastal aquifers; this phenomenon is favoured by the lowering of the freshwater level underground due to excessive use of groundwater for irrigation and by pumping for reclamation purposes ("salt wedge").

FIGURE 12. SOIL MAPPING OF THE EMILIA-ROMAGNA REGION WITH DETAILS OF SAND CONTENT IN THE 0-30 CM LAYER OF THE SOILS IN THE PILOT AREA IN THE PROVINCE OF FERRARA. SOURCE: MOKA GEOPORTAL, EMILIA-ROMAGNA REGION.

FIGURE 13. SOIL MAPPING OF THE EMILIA-ROMAGNA REGION WITH DETAILS OF ORGANIC MATTER CONTENT IN THE 0-30 CM LAYER OF SOILS IN THE PILOT AREA IN THE PROVINCE OF FERRARA. SOURCE: MOKA EMILIA-ROMAGNA REGION GEOPORTAL.

The Sustainable Sand District represents the business model hypothesized for the case study, most suitable for testing integrated soil management approaches aimed at greater adaptation and resilience to ongoing climate change.

4.8.2 Method

The survey questionnaire was addressed to farmers (farms and agricultural cooperatives), land managers such as local authorities, the Po Delta Park of the Emilia-Romagna Region, the Land Reclamation Consortium, environmental associations, foundations, and non-profit organizations. The objective was to understand the stakeholders' attitudes toward sandy soil protection and address common challenges through adoption and participation in innovative business models. Stakeholders were also asked questions about the possibility of applying other business models, such as carbon farming and the application of best practices for business competitiveness, and participation in research projects, taking into account environmental, social, and economic factors.

Approximately 60 stakeholders working in the sandy area were involved. Specifically, the following categories were interviewed:

- **agricultural companies and cooperatives** operating on sandy soils and participating in the PIL (Political Innovation Lab);
- **land managers** such as local authorities; specifically, the questionnaire was distributed to the departments of environment, agriculture, and land-use and cultural planning, land reclamation consortia for irrigation management, the Emilia-Romagna Po Delta Park, agricultural trade associations, and environmental associations;
- **technicians and freelancers** such as local geologists and agronomists.

The questionnaire was created using Google Forms and divided into 7 sections. Stakeholders were asked to express their opinions by assigning a score on a scale from 1 (completely disagree) to 5 (completely agree). The questionnaire sections are as follows:

SECTION 1 - General data: category, municipality, hectares cultivated, production type, gender, age, and education of the respondent;

SECTION 2 - Business models for sandy soil health: Users were asked to express their preferences regarding the application of different business models (e.g., carbon farming, sustainability districts, research projects, collective actions), their advantages, disadvantages, and implementation methods;

SECTION 3 - Best practices for sandy soil management: Users were asked to express their preferences regarding the application of different best practices (e.g., minimum

tillage, no tillage, cover crops) for soil health, their advantages, disadvantages, and implementation methods;

SECTION 4 – innovation, research, training: users had to express their willingness to participate in innovative research and training projects, in order to improve soil health;

SECTION 5 – Investments: This section aims to collect information regarding investments in soil health protection in the pilot area.

SECTION 6 – Social Context: The objective is to define the types of human relationships existing in the rural context of the NOVASOIL pilot area that influence sustainable soil management.

SECTION 7 – Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services: The objective is to define the level of biodiversity and ecosystem services provided by sandy soil.

Before being distributed to the identified stakeholders, the questionnaire was validated by the team of experts from the Istituto Delta Ecologia Applicata, composed of agronomists, biologists, economists, and biodiversity experts. The questionnaire was then sent to the partner, the University of Ferrara, for sharing.

Given the identified target, a database was created consisting of email addresses and telephone numbers of all stakeholders. Specifically, for each entity, people employed at various levels were involved. In local authorities, the questionnaire was sent to managers and technicians in the environmental, territorial planning, landscape, urban planning, and local culture sectors. In agricultural businesses and cooperatives, the questionnaire was sent to managers and agrotechnicians. Agricultural trade associations operating at the regional and local levels also participated. Freelance professionals active in the six municipalities involved in the pilot area, with knowledge of local dynamics, were also involved. Furthermore, to gain a more comprehensive overview of the propensity to adopt innovative business models, the governing bodies of the Province of Ferrara, specifically those in the territorial planning sector, were also involved.

Each stakeholder received the link to the questionnaire via email, along with a presentation letter about the NOVASOIL project, outlining the overall objective of the project and the questionnaire. Fifteen days after the first mailing, the questionnaire was sent again to any remaining stakeholders. Finally, to maximize participation, the stakeholders in the pilot area were contacted by telephone and supported in completing the questionnaire.

4.8.3 Survey results

The questionnaire highlighted important considerations regarding the propensity of local stakeholders to adopt innovative business models for soil management.

The survey was conducted with 60 users, of whom 25 showed immediate interest in completing the questionnaire. Specifically:

- agricultural companies and cooperatives already involved in other NOVASOIL activities, such as political Innovation Lab and interviews, agricultural associations, and a non-profit foundation actively responded to the questionnaire, demonstrating interest in the topic of soil health through the application of innovative business models;
- the Land Reclamation Consortium and the Po Delta Park of the Emilia-Romagna Region completed the questionnaire, expressing their views on the application of business models on regional sandy soils;
- local authorities in the pilot area – the Departments of Environment, Agriculture, and Land Planning – did not respond to the questionnaire and were contacted by telephone; This highlighted their difficulty in responding due to a lack of technical expertise in soil health and their discomfort with the impossibility of assigning expert personnel to the topic. They also complained about the difficulty of working on these issues in collaboration with the relevant higher-level bodies (Province of Ferrara and Emilia Romagna Region).

The 43% of respondents fall into the "farmers" category, followed by the Park Authority and land reclamation consortia; the majority of respondents are male (80%) and aged between 56 and 65. The primary production area is horticulture (36%), while agricultural land varies from a few hectares to hundreds of hectares, demonstrating how both small and large-scale agricultural businesses show interest in managing sandy soil to preserve its health and fertility.

The main findings and considerations for each section of the questionnaire are described below.

SECTION 2 - Business models for sandy soil health

56% of respondents stated that creating sustainable food districts and adhering to quality systems (e.g., organic farming, integrated production) to address sandy soil issues is the best innovative business model for managing soil health. The creation of a temporary consortium (ATI), the implementation of carbon farming practices, and corporate digitalization, on the other hand, were less likely to have impact.

When asked whether creating a business model based on collaboration and sharing among sand soil operators was simple, almost all respondents responded negatively,

highlighting the significant difficulty in communicating among the various stakeholders operating and managing sand soil.

43% of respondents stated that increasing funding for the creation and support of innovative business models for soil management is important for maintaining soil health.

SECTION 3 - Best practices for sandy soil management

The application of best practices for sandy soil management is viewed positively by more than 50% of respondents, both for maintaining and improving soil health and fertility and as a means of increasing farm income. Furthermore, it is stated that participating in soil fertility maintenance through the application of best practices leads to collective territorial wealth. The best practices found to have the greatest impact on maintaining the health and fertility of sandy soil were the use of cover crops (75%) and prudent water management (80%).

SECTION 4 - Innovation, research, training

In the areas of innovation and research, farmers and land managers agree that an innovative farm more easily addresses the problems associated with sandy soil (loss of organic matter and salinization). Participation in research projects on soil health and fertility is also essential for solving common problems associated with sand cultivation (80%). 80% of stakeholders believe that training their employees and all other workers is essential to apply innovative soil management methods.

SECTION 5 – Investments

The majority of stakeholders (90%) believe that investing in soil health today means ensuring a better future for their children and future generations. Respondents believe that sharing investments (e.g., purchasing agricultural machinery, software/management systems, specialized consulting services) with other local stakeholders is the best way to solve sandy soil problems; only 20% believe individual investments are appropriate to address the problems.

SECTION 6 – Social scope

The results of the responses confirm that collaboration and communication among local stakeholders is very difficult in the pilot area; nevertheless, 90% of respondents believe collaboration between farms, government bodies, and agricultural associations is essential for better resolution of environmental issues related to sandy soil.

SECTION 7 – Biodiversity and ecosystem services

The adoption of innovative business models for soil health, such as the creation of a Sustainable Food District, would enable the implementation of the seven ecosystem services investigated:

- **Ecosystem Service 1 - Producing food and biomass**
- **Ecosystem Service 6 - serving as a source of raw materials for human activities**

In the sand district, fruit and vegetable and nursery production is of great importance; sandy soil favours the development and growth of certain crops that prefer well-drained soils, but presents limitations for other plant species that prefer more structured soils; sustainable soil management and the application of innovative business models are essential to ensure the quantity and quality of production;

- **Ecosystem Service 2 - Absorbing, conserving, and filtering water**

Sandy soils are characterized by poor water retention capacity; good soil and water management in the sand district is essential to counter common problems such as water scarcity in the summer months and the threat of salt wedge/salinization of groundwater;

- **Ecosystem Service 3 - Laying the foundation for life and biodiversity, including habitats, species, and genetics**

In sandy soils, microbial diversity can be limited by low organic matter, water retention, and nutrient mobility, but sustainable management practices adopted at a large territorial scale (district) could preserve and enhance existing biodiversity;

- **Ecosystem Service 4 - Serving as a carbon sink**

Sandy soils are generally low in organic matter, so the use of carbon-related practices helps preserve soil carbon stocks and prevent further soil depletion;

- **Ecosystem Service 5 - Providing a physical platform and cultural services for people and their activities**
- **Ecosystem Service 7 - Establishing an archive of geological, geomorphological, and archaeological heritage**

The Po Delta sands area is characterized by unique landscapes, where the promiscuity and fluidity between natural marine and lagoon landscapes and human activities such as agriculture and tourism can be observed. Maintaining the sandy soil not only allows for the preservation of agricultural activity and the production of quality food, but also for the preservation of a socio-cultural identity, capable of maintaining the area's competitiveness through agritourism and nature tourism.

4.8.4 Market potential estimation

The study revealed that most stakeholders operating in the Emilia-Romagna Region's sandy soils believe joining sustainable food districts is effective in addressing the common issues associated with sandy soils.

Joining a district can represent a truly innovative business model for a farm, capable of generating added value and greater competitiveness on national and international markets, while also enabling sustainable soil management while preserving healthy, high-quality produce. Adopting shared best practices at the regional, not just company, scale allows for long-term production costs reduction.

Products from sustainable districts are more readily recognized in national and global markets, which are increasingly seeking healthy, geographically traced products capable of reducing environmental impact in order to mitigate and adapt to ongoing climate change. A 2021 study conducted by Junior Enterprise at Bocconi University (Milan) in collaboration with Accenture, a global multinational strategic consulting firm, highlighted how supplier selection criteria for large-scale retail trade have become increasingly stringent in recent years. 55% percent of respondents said they consider their environmental performance, from factors such as product recyclability to the sustainability of packaging, ingredients, and the processing and distribution process itself. Furthermore, 80% said they require sustainability certifications from their suppliers, a goal proposed by the "Emilia-Romagna Region sand area sustainability district" business model.

Membership in the District also provides reputational benefits, as the company's image is strengthened through membership in a structure, such as the district, that is recognized at an institutional and regulatory level (Resolution of the Emilia-Romagna Regional Council no. 1816 of October 28, 2019). Member companies, through the use of best practices, position themselves as innovative and responsible businesses, a crucial element in agri-food marketing and communication strategies. Many of the companies interviewed already adhere to certified quality systems recognized by the markets (some examples: organic farming, the SQNPI mark – National Quality System for Integrated Production, GlobalGAP, QVI – Italian Nursery Quality). Uniting these companies in a District provides visibility and assurance, increasing recognition by the markets and consumers.

From a financial standpoint, sustainable food district members have easier access to dedicated regional and national funds. In 2024, the Emilia-Romagna Region allocated €300,000 to support organic districts, with the goal of promoting good soil management practices and preserving soil fertility. At the national level, MASAF – the Ministry of Agriculture, Food Sovereignty and Forestry – launched a call for proposals in 2024 for the creation of Food Districts where eligible activities reflect the needs of

operators and administrators in the Emilian sands' rural areas in terms of soil management, research, innovation, and quality. The aforementioned call for proposals aims to:

- encourage producer participation in quality schemes;
- develop research and development projects in the agricultural and agri-food sectors;
- invest in knowledge systems and innovation sharing and dissemination systems;
- invest in knowledge-building and innovation-sharing systems;
- promote professional training and skills acquisition actions.

Adherence to the business model, based on low-impact management practices that increase soil carbon stock, allows farmers to generate new sources of income through emerging markets, such as access to the agricultural carbon credit market and payments for ecosystem services provided.

Last but not least, the creation of the Sand District offers participants additional territorial and socio-cultural value. Through sustainable management methods, businesses contribute to land protection, strengthening their ties with the local community. The enhancement of the ecosystem services generated by sandy soil (landscape, biodiversity, territorial identity) translates into tourism attractiveness and new non-agricultural economic opportunities, enabling local businesses to earn a complementary income to that earned from agricultural production.

5. General discussion

Business model potential matrix

The following Table 27 summarises the results of the presented studies in the form of a market potential matrix to identify promising business models. High potential demand that is met by high potential supply hints at a high market potential. On the other hand, low or medium potential on either of the two sides limits a business models potential, as far as it can be judged by the studies' results (not all case studies investigated both the supply and demand side).

TABLE 27. BUSINESS MODEL POTENTIAL MATRIX.

Partner	Soil health business model	Consumer acceptance	Farmer adoption	Potential value
TUM	AECS	Medium to High	High	High
TUM	Carbon farming	Low	Low	Low
TUM	Value chain	Medium to High	Medium	Medium
ZALF	Soil health and biodiversity certificates	Medium to High	High	Medium to high
WU	Carbon farming + carbon credit trade	n.a.	Medium	Low
WU	Carbon farming + value chain payments	n.a.	Medium	High
WU	Carbon farming + CAP payments	n.a.	Low	Low
UCPH	Soil health label	Medium	n.a.	High
UNIFE/UNIPI	Area based-payment (AECS)	Low	n.a.	Low
UNIFE/UNIPI	Result-based payment	High	n.a.	High
UNIFE/UNIPI	Hybrid	Medium	n.a.	Medium
METK	Low-carbon seed	Low	Low-Medium	Medium
NBU	Agrotourism	High	n.a.	High
IDECO	Sustainable food district	n.a.	Medium-High	High

Note: n.a. = not applicable, as not in all case studies both the demand and supply side were studied.

5.1 Germany: Carbon farming (TUM)

Based on the preferences of both farmers and consumers, AECS (Agri-Environmental Climate Schemes) and value chain approaches emerge as the most promising business models for enhancing soil organic carbon (SOC) and delivering climate benefits. In contrast, GHG certificate models currently face significant barriers to widespread acceptance.

From the farmers' perspective, flexibility, simplicity, and familiarity are critical factors influencing their willingness to participate in environmental schemes. AECS are favoured because they are well-established, provide reliable payments, and involve action-based measures that many farmers already understand and implement. Similarly, value chain approaches, especially those that can be terminated at any time, offer a level of autonomy that aligns with farmers' strong preference for avoiding long-term contractual commitments and additional bureaucracy. Farmers are generally reluctant to adopt measures that limit their decision-making freedom or impose a high administrative burden, particularly when market conditions are volatile.

When comparing average willingness to pay (WTP) and willingness to accept (WTA), both AECS and value chain models, particularly in their improved forms, prove economically viable. From an ecological standpoint, the improved versions of these models, which include results-based payments and longer-term commitments, are also preferable because they ensure verified carbon sequestration and better align with emerging EU regulations (e.g., CRCF Regulation (EU/2024/3012)).

Consumers, for their part, are generally supportive of climate mitigation efforts and are open to paying for CO₂ offset initiatives. However, their preferences hinge on two key conditions: short-term commitments and guaranteed environmental outcomes. They express strong aversion to long-term payment obligations (e.g., 10-20 years) and are more likely to support business models where target achievement is assured. Depending on the monitoring character, consumer potential of the business models is either medium (for action-based monitoring) or high (for result based monitoring). Result-based AECS and improved value chain models meet consumers expectations more effectively than GHG certificate models.

In contrast, GHG certificate models face scepticism from both stakeholders. Farmers are deterred by the requirement for long-term, results-based contracts and uncertainty around the future prices of CO₂ certificates. Many are hesitant to invest in new practices and technologies when market fluctuations could undermine profitability. While policy tools like minimum price guarantees could theoretically address this issue, they carry the risk of oversupply and may lead to ecological backsliding once contracts expire. These factors contribute to a high WTA among

farmers, making GHG certificate models economically and practically less attractive at this stage.

In conclusion, both AECS and the value chain approach offer a promising path forward for promoting soil carbon sequestration. They are better aligned with the preferences and risk tolerances of farmers, meet key consumer expectations, and, if adapted with results-based elements, can deliver measurable and reliable climate benefits. By contrast, GHG certificate models, while conceptually robust, require further policy support, risk mitigation strategies, and trust-building measures to become a feasible and widely accepted model.

5.2 Germany: AgoraNatura (ZALF)

Our study provides a novel contribution to the ongoing debate on how to enhance private funding for environmental improvements in agriculture. We examined private consumers' WTP for soil health and biodiversity certificates which are determined by bundling and blending. Moreover, we made use of an existing online marketplace acting as a facilitator and intermediary of such funding.

The insights of our research for leveraging private investment are manifold. First, our findings align with existing studies indicating that private consumers in Germany show a willingness to contribute financially to soil health and biodiversity on farmland. This trend may indirectly reflect public support for the EU's Soil Strategy and Biodiversity Strategy. Our results also encourage decision-makers to continue recognising soil health and biodiversity on farmland as priority in policy initiatives.

Second, policymakers may acknowledge that bundling can increase private investment. Therefore, when designing incentive schemes within current policy initiatives (e.g. the EU's Roadmap towards Nature Credits) bundling environmental improvements under single certificates should be considered. However, the heterogeneity in preferences for bundled improvements implies that while bundling responds to public demand, policy design should ensure a variety of bundle types to fully harness funding potential.

Third, blending public and private funding offers opportunities to enhance investment. Nevertheless, public spending must be carefully balanced to prevent crowding out of private funding. Our results underline that excessive public subsidies may crowd out private willingness to pay. Experiences from UK ecosystem markets and European peatland initiatives provide valuable insights here. Specifically,

mechanisms such as trigger funds, similar to those tested in our study, could successfully encourage private funding while limiting crowding-out effects.

Lastly, our results provide evidence that online marketplaces for soil health and biodiversity certificates, such as AgoraNatura, may be a useful business model to attract private funding.

5.3 Netherlands: Carbon credit (WU)

The Dutch case study identified three distinct farmer perspectives: *pro-environmental entrepreneurs*, *traditional food providers*, and *carbon farming pragmatics*. Each group holds different attitudes towards incentives for improving soil health. While *pro-environmental entrepreneurs* and *carbon farming pragmatics* may be more open to new incentives such as value chain payments or carbon farming contracts, *traditional food providers* appear more difficult to engage through these contracts. Since soil health, carbon storage, and agricultural productivity are closely connected, emphasising these links could help motivate farmers with more conservative views.

Although some farmers responded positively to value chain contracts and carbon credit trading, several aspects of these incentives require further consideration before they are widely promoted. For value chain contracts, fairness in negotiating agreements with actors who may have greater market influence is important. It is also necessary to consider public expectations regarding products that claim to be more sustainable. In the case of carbon credit trade, questions remain about whether soil health measures can deliver the intended long term carbon storage.

The study also shows that the incentives provided by public payment schemes (such as AECS and eco-schemes) are seen as insufficient by all farmers in the sample. Improving these schemes could increase their acceptance and effectiveness. Overall, the findings demonstrate that farmers have diverse views on soil health incentives. A single contract solution will not meet the needs of all farmers. Tailored approaches that reflect different beliefs, production systems, and market conditions are essential for designing effective and inclusive strategies.

5.4 Italy: Italian consumers (UNIFE, UNIPI)

The findings of the mixed logit model offer significant insights into the preferences of Italian consumers regarding conservation agricultural initiatives. The payment per

hectare signifies substantial price sensitivity, indicating that participants are less inclined to support programs requiring greater payments. This aligns with established economic behaviour and past findings that individuals generally prefer lower-cost options when contributing to environmental programs (Blasch & Farsi, 2014). Research revealed that a significant number of consumers are willing to pay a little premium price for ecological products; however, their willingness to pay declines as the premium rises (Biswas, 2016; Kucher et al., 2019). Like many European customers, Italians seem to be willing to support environmental initiatives, but only to a certain extent, particularly when the cost is viewed as excessive or unjustified. Besides, there is a considerable possibility for greater consumer awareness and vendor promotional activities due to the low level of consumer awareness of ecological agriculture products (Hao et al., 2022). Similarly, the contract duration shows a clear aversion to long-term commitments, suggesting that longer program durations reduce the likelihood of program selection. The negative effect of program duration suggests a public preference for shorter commitments, likely due to risk aversion or uncertainty about long-term obligations. In a comprehensive analysis of attributes utilized in discrete choice experiments (DCE) for agri-environmental contracts, Raina et al. (2021) discovered that contract duration was a significant component in 17 of the 34 selected studies.

On the other hand, attributes that demonstrate environmental effectiveness have a favourable effect on decision-making. An increase in soil organic matter has a large positive impact, suggesting that consumers value tangible environmental benefits highly. This aligns with global soil health initiatives that prioritise organic matter as a key indicator of soil functionality. Soil organic matter is not only a key indicator of fertility and productivity, but it also plays a critical role in carbon sequestration, water retention, and biodiversity (Celestina et al., 2019; EIP-AGRI, 2015). People accord priority to ecological agriculture because it has numerous positive effects on the environment, such as improved soil-building techniques that support soil flora and fauna, long-term sustainability of agro-ecosystems, enhanced biodiversity, better water infiltration, and a lower risk of groundwater pollution (Manco, 2023).

For payment type, the result indicates that respondents show a stronger preference for performance-based or mixed payment schemes rather than fixed-rate. The previous research stated that flexible and adaptive contractual solutions are favoured over a fixed payment type of contract. The best contract design under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) Pillar 2 measures combines action-based and result-based components in a medium-term agreement (Kelemen et al., 2023). Traditional action-orientated agri-environmental schemes have faced extensive criticism for various reasons, including ineffective targeting, insufficient payment differentiation, short-term focus, and inadequate monitoring (Moxey & White, 2014). In contrast, result-

orientated schemes are advocated primarily for their potential to enhance outcomes and reduce costs by permitting greater flexibility and innovation compared to action-orientated schemes (Simpson et al., 2023).

The values of marginal willingness to pay (MWTP) highlight these findings. Consumers are prepared to spend roughly €120.37 more per hectare for initiatives that improve soil organic matter. The World Economic Forum (2023) mentioned that at least 65% of customers wish to spend wisely to have more sustainable and healthful lives. In response to this, many food manufacturers are implementing several measures to guarantee environmental sustainability and meet the growing demands of consumers. For instance, Nestlé has partnered with 500,000 farmers to hasten the shift to regenerative farming methods, which improve soil quality, restore natural water cycles, and absorb carbon (World Economic Forum, 2023). Consumers are also showing their willingness to pay €29.36 more per hectare for result-based payments. This result suggests that consumers value performance-linked incentives that reward actual environmental outcomes. Hybrid agri-environmental payment schemes seem to provide the optimal payment solution, considering both fiscal limitations and the necessity for programs to engage significant farmer participation to achieve environmental efficiency (OECD, 2022). The potential of result-orientated agri-environmental schemes is garnering heightened interest in Europe; researchers generally believe that result-orientated strategies will yield superior ecological, economic, and social outcomes compared to action-orientated approaches (Burton & Schwarz, 2013). While MWTP for contract duration indicates that consumers are unwilling to pay more for longer program durations, they would pay €11.59 less for each additional year of contract duration. It is well documented in behavioural environmental research, which indicates that uncertainty regarding future rewards or costs diminishes the willingness to engage in long-term programs (Buttenheim et al., 2023). These estimations emphasize the importance of environmental results and program design in influencing public support.

Empirical evidence indicates that Italian consumers are inclined to support conservation agriculture, contingent upon the initiatives being cost-effective, flexible, and outcome focused. Their preferences favour short-term, quantifiable activities that distinctly exhibit environmental impact, especially enhancements in soil organic matter. These findings could have significant implications for the formulation of future agri-environmental policies. Integrating consumer-desired attributes, such as performance-based incentives and shorter contracts, can improve the acceptance and effectiveness of soil conservation initiatives.

5.5 Estonia: Seed centre (METK)

The findings of this study shed light on Estonian farmers' willingness to pay for carbon-labelled and environmentally labelled seeds, revealing a mix of economic, behavioural, and systemic influences. While policy momentum from initiatives like the European Green Deal (European Commission, 2020) and Estonia's CAP Strategic Plan 2023-2027 (RT I, 27.03.2025) highlight the importance of sustainable practices in agriculture, price remains the dominant factor guiding farmers' seed purchasing decisions. The challenge, therefore, lies in aligning environmental goals with farmers' financial realities and practical needs.

Market incentives and price sensitivity

Farmers in this study were most willing to pay more for carbon-labelled seeds when those seeds conferred a clear market advantage or price premium. This underscores that sustainability alone is not a sufficient incentive – unless tied directly to improved revenue, reputation, or reduced risk. Introducing environmental labelling into the seed sector must therefore be accompanied by mechanisms that translate sustainability into tangible business benefits, such as access to premium markets or preferential treatment in procurement schemes. This aligns with broader literature on sustainable agriculture that emphasizes the importance of value-added strategies for incentivizing sustainable input use (e.g., Singh et al., 2013). Adding a sustainability label may also enhance the company's ESG value, potentially improving conditions for investment and stakeholder confidence (Sandberg et. al, 2023). Yet, price sensitivity remains a core barrier. While consumers and downstream actors increasingly demand green products (CBI, 2022), farmers face tight margins. This is especially true in Estonia, where climate risks and farm size diversity make investment decisions cautious.

Behavioural dimensions: values, beliefs, and the value-action gap

This study confirms the presence of a value-action gap: respondents who strongly agreed that farmers should support sustainable seed producers were, paradoxically, less likely to pay more themselves. This phenomenon reflects a tension between normative environmental values and individual economic behaviour – widely observed in environmental psychology and behavioural economics. Similarly, respondents who believed that technology alone can solve environmental problems – without requiring lifestyle or practice change – were less likely to pay more for carbon-labelled seed. This reflects what Abson et al. (2017) term “shallow leverage points,” where optimism about innovation replaces the need for immediate behavioural change. The observed gender differences add nuance to the discussion: male respondents were more likely to pay a premium when market benefits were present

but less inclined when motivations involved indirect environmental gains, such as ESG improvements or carbon credit compensation. These results suggest that sustainability messaging must be targeted by gender, education level, and farm type.

Structural barriers and business model challenges

There are several fundamental challenges in transitioning seed production to soil-sustainable practices. These include questions around how to introduce new soil management technologies – such as reduced tillage, cover crops, or organic amendments – that ensure soils maintain their ecological functions, such as carbon storage, biodiversity support, and water regulation (Bender et al., 1999; Abawi & Widmer, 2000). Moreover, farmers must also secure financing to make these transitions viable. The design of future business models must consider both seed quality and productivity alongside soil health. This requires integrating local soil data, weather information, and crop requirements into decision-making and aligning them with consumer and market expectations. The entire supply chain – from production to marketing – should be considered to ensure a functioning system where soil-health benefits translate into product value. Although innovative cultivation technologies (e.g. direct drilling, catch crops) and their impacts on seed productivity and soil functions have been studied (Singh et al., 2013), there is limited integration of these findings into business modelling in seed systems. More research is needed to identify which technologies provide both agronomic and ecological value in specific contexts.

Policy landscape and research gaps

The Estonian CAP Strategic Plan 2023-2027 provides several direct and indirect measures for soil protection. These include permanent grasslands on slopes to mitigate erosion, peatland protection, crop rotation, legume cultivation, winter soil cover, and soil sampling (RT I, 27.03.2025). However, carbon certification and carbon-labelled seeds are not yet common practice in Estonia's seed production sector, as confirmed by this study's survey data.

Policy should focus on incentivizing participation in carbon programs, encouraging adoption of soil-friendly practices through subsidies, and integrating carbon and biodiversity metrics into existing CAP measures. As Liu et al. (2016) suggest, long-term effects of carbon labelling and behavioural barriers among conventional tillage users must also be addressed through tailored outreach and support. Despite green thinking becoming more widespread – including among processors and consumers – the market still signals that price is the deciding factor in seed purchasing (CBI, 2022). Therefore, a sustainability label cannot stand alone; it must be embedded in a larger system of business value and social trust.

The way forward: Differentiated strategies and soil-centred innovation

In conclusion, our findings suggest that soil-health-promoting measures must be embedded into all agricultural sectors, including seed production. These measures should not be introduced uniformly but rather tailored to the production characteristics of different crops, regions, and farm types. Not all sustainable practices are equally effective in every context, and the most suitable technologies for seed production – ones that balance seed quality, soil conservation, and economic feasibility – should be a priority for future research. The vision is to develop business models where seeds produced with sustainable soil management practices offer added value, allowing producers to earn additional income while also improving ecological outcomes. This strategy has the potential to create a win-win situation: enhancing soil health and biodiversity while increasing the economic resilience of farms.

5.6 Bulgaria: Agrotourism (NBU)

The results presented in the matrix highlight the market potential of BG CS, which is primarily linked to its strong focus on agro-ecological wine production practices that protect soil from erosion. This potential is evident across several key areas. In terms of channels, there are opportunities to expand the popularity of such wines through wine tourism and related activities, including tastings, restaurants, and hotel partnerships, while also targeting niche markets that value sustainable production. Strengthening customer relationships can be achieved by certifying wines that guarantee soil protection practices, as well as by fostering collective initiatives such as associations of wineries producing comparable quantities of wine. From a cost structure perspective, participation in joint procurement of materials and supplies offers the chance to optimize expenses and increase efficiency. Among the most important key resources is the certification of both grapes and wine produced under soil erosion protection standards, which serves as a mark of quality and sustainability. Finally, the policy framework supports the implementation of inter-row grassing, alongside investments in new technologies and experimental approaches, in order to further enhance and establish effective soil erosion protection practices. Together, these elements explain the indicated market potential and position BG CS as a promising example of how ecological practices can create both environmental and economic value.

5.7 Denmark: Soil health label (UCPH)

Results suggest that soil health labels on food products can increase consumers' utility when combined with organic labels. Labelling food products with only the soil health label leads to relatively small utility differentiation compared to conventional products without labels. The utility of dual-labelled food products – those carrying both soil health and organic labels – is also reflected in their cross-utility effects, as they are less frequently purchased together with other product versions in the same category.

The market potential of soil health labels depends on changes in both their own and other products' prices. Overall, food products carrying soil health labels, whether combined with organic labels or not, have negative own-price elasticities, indicating that price increases reduce demand for such products. However, when the price of dual-labelled products rises, demand is likely to shift toward conventional products and, to a lesser extent, organic-labelled products. This suggests that while dual-labelled products are highly preferred and competitive at the current prices considered in the study, further price increases would reduce their market share.

The results carry several implications. Soil health labels can play a role in soil health business models, but their success requires integration with established labels that are already well recognized and accepted by consumers. In our case, pairing soil health labels with organic labels enhances consumer utility. Such integrated labelling could also have significant market potential in the food sector if supported by appropriate pricing strategies or policy mechanisms. For example, subsidizing farmers to adopt soil health-enhancing practices could reduce food production costs, prevent price increases for soil health-labelled products, and in turn encourage consumer adoption through increased purchases. Moreover, our findings imply that policymakers should carefully consider the price sensitivity of food products before introducing taxes on agricultural practices. Such taxes could raise food prices, discourage adoption of soil health labels, and negatively affect consumer demand for soil health labelled products.

5.8 Italy: “Sustainable Po Delta Sand District of the Emilia-Romagna Region” (IDECO)

Based on the preferences of farmers and land managers in the sands area, the most successful innovative business model for soil health among those proposed in the survey was the creation of a territorial Sustainable Food District, coupled with adherence to quality systems (organic farming and integrated production). Local

operators consider these choices to be successful ways to address existing issues in the pilot area, such as saltwater intrusion and organic matter deficiency. The creation of temporary consortiums, the implementation of carbon farming practices, and corporate digitalization, on the other hand, appear to have less impact on soil protection.

To improve business competitiveness from both an environmental and economic-social perspective, the importance of training sand area operators has emerged. Disseminating knowledge and sharing ideas helps address issues related to sandy soil.

Farmers and land managers agree on the importance of increasing funding to support new business models for soil management. Financial support is also essential for participating in research projects aimed at improving business performance, both environmentally and economically.

Another key finding from the survey is the objective difficulty in communicating among the various stakeholders operating and managing the sands, despite the District being considered the winning business model for the area.

One problem identified is the fragility and inadequacy of local administrations, which have expressed concern about the lack of competent and experienced internal personnel in soil protection.

For the sands of the Emilia-Romagna Region, it is desirable, in the future, to implement business and development models that involve the territorial aggregation of public-private entities in order to address environmental challenges, primarily maintaining soil health and fertility.

At the regional and national levels, it is important to incentivize policies and financial plans that support the creation of "sustainable food districts" and the implementation of good soil management practices. Attention should be paid not only to farmers but also to public bodies, given their role in soil governance, such as monitoring and controlling health and fertility.

6. Conclusions

The general discussion of market potential in Deliverable 2.3 underscores the complexity of scaling up soil-health-promoting business models. The evidence reveals both promising avenues for expansion and structural barriers that constrain adoption. This section synthesizes key insights with reference to the three focal dimensions of Task 2.3.

6.1 Consumer acceptance and willingness-to-pay

Price sensitivity remains a major constraint. Although stated preferences suggest support for sustainability, actual purchasing behaviour is limited when premiums are too high. Upscaling therefore requires strategies that either reduce cost premiums (e.g., through economies of scale) or enhance perceived value (e.g., by combining soil health with health or quality attributes, or established labels). Public campaigns and retailer prioritization can further stimulate demand by embedding soil health within broader sustainability narratives.

The cross-country case studies consistently demonstrate that consumer acceptance is shaped less by the type of business model and more by its design attributes. Short contract durations and credible monitoring of outcomes are decisive. In Germany and Denmark, consumers showed greater WTP for result-based schemes that provide certainty about carbon sequestration or soil health improvements. Conversely, long-term obligations of 10-20 years sharply reduced demand, even when environmental benefits were higher.

Other contexts reinforce these dynamics. The Italian consumer study revealed relatively high WTP for food products associated with soil health improvements, particularly when linked to visible quality attributes such as freshness, naturalness, and local origin. However, WTP declined significantly when premiums exceeded moderate levels, highlighting the importance of affordability and trust in certification. Similarly, in the Bulgarian case of agrotourism, consumers valued the combination of soil-friendly practices with cultural and experiential benefits. Here, willingness to support sustainable farming was enhanced when it was embedded in a broader package of services, suggesting that bundling soil health with leisure or lifestyle experiences may increase market potential.

In Estonia, where the case centred on seed production and quality, buyer preferences reflected an emphasis on reliability and long-term benefits. While WTP for certified seed was positive, actual acceptance was strongly conditioned by assurances of performance and transparency in certification schemes. This underscores that even in

markets where buyers are indirectly connected to soil health (e.g., through inputs rather than food products), credible information remains a critical driver of demand.

The Netherlands study, focusing on carbon credits and offsetting, showed that consumers were generally open to paying for ecosystem services, but preferences were highly segmented. Some groups placed strong value on pro-environmental identity and were willing to invest in offsetting schemes, while others expressed scepticism about the credibility of certificates. This mirrors broader concerns about greenwashing and highlights the need for robust governance of voluntary carbon markets.

Taken together, the evidence indicates that across countries, consumer support depends heavily on three conditions: (1) short-term, flexible commitments, which make participation feasible; (2) trustworthy certification and monitoring, which provide assurance of real environmental outcomes; and (3) added value or co-benefits, whether in the form of product quality (Italy), cultural experience (Bulgaria), or identity alignment (Netherlands). Price sensitivity remains a universal constraint: although many consumers are willing to signal support for sustainability, actual purchasing behaviour diminishes when cost premiums are perceived as excessive. Upscaling therefore requires strategies that either lower premiums through scaling effects or increase perceived value by integrating soil health with broader consumer benefits.

6.2 Farmer adoption, profitability, and drivers of large-scale uptake

The analysis of the case studies shows that farmers primarily adopt innovative and climate-friendly business models when these provide economic benefits, flexibility, and low risks. In Germany, Agri-Environmental Climate Schemes (AECS) and value chain approaches receive the highest acceptance, as they are familiar, simple to implement, and linked to reliable payments. Farmers favour flexible, short-term contracts and tend to avoid long-term, results-based models typical of GHG certificate model, which is met with scepticism due to uncertain CO₂ certificate prices, high monitoring costs, and long contract durations.

The Dutch case study on Carbon credits confirms that while many farmers – particularly “carbon farming enthusiasts” – are open to collective models, more demanding measures such as afforestation or peatland rewetting see little uptake. Traditional food-oriented farmers are primarily driven by short-term profitability and can only be engaged when clear financial returns are evident. Farmer organizations, such as ZLTO, play an important bridging role by pooling knowledge and reducing costs.

The Estonian Seed Centre model highlights that farmers are willing to pay for CO₂- or eco-certified seeds only if such inputs deliver tangible market advantages. Higher education and income foster openness, while purely environmental arguments remain insufficient. Most farmers maintain a pragmatic stance, expecting that additional costs be offset by suppliers or through agronomic benefits.

In Bulgaria, the Agro-tourism case illustrates that integrated models (e.g., combining viticulture with tourism) become attractive when they offer income diversification alongside ecological benefits. Linking local products to regional value creation plays a decisive role in motivating farmers to engage over the long term.

Finally, the Italian Sandy Soil District case demonstrates that farmers in structurally challenging regions demand a strong connection between ecological improvements and economic competitiveness. Sustainable soil management is accepted only when it enhances yield stability and market opportunities.

In summary, large-scale adoption is driven above all by economic security, flexible contractual arrangements, collective organizational structures, and measurable co-benefits. Environmental awareness alone is not sufficient; the key lies in linking sustainability with profitability. To accelerate the large-scale uptake of soil health-promoting business models, policies should aim to combine economic incentives with flexibility and long-term stability. Hybrid schemes that mix fixed payments with performance-based bonuses can reduce risks for farmers while rewarding tangible environmental outcomes, especially when contract durations remain manageable. Collective and cooperative structures deserve strong support, as they enable farmers to share costs, pool knowledge, and enhance their bargaining power in both input and output markets. Ensuring price stability for carbon credits through transparent market mechanisms or minimum price guarantees can further reduce uncertainties that currently discourage participation. Moreover, policies should promote integrated income strategies, such as agro-tourism, eco-certified seeds, or regional branding, which link ecological practices to new revenue streams. Above all, environmental goals must be framed not only as societal benefits but also as a pathway to greater competitiveness, yield stability, and resilience. Only by demonstrating that sustainability and profitability can reinforce each other will farmers engage in these models at scale.

6.3 Societal benefits of upscaling

The potential societal benefits of scaling up soil-health-promoting models are considerable. Improved soil organic carbon sequestration contributes directly to

climate neutrality targets, while healthier soils enhance water retention, biodiversity, and long-term productivity. Upscaling can also stimulate new markets for carbon certificates, eco-labels, and sustainability-oriented tourism, creating value beyond the farm level.

However, not all business models deliver equivalent societal value. Basic AECS and value chain models, although popular, may lack permanence and additionality, thereby undermining long-term environmental outcomes. Improved and results-based schemes appear more credible, as they reward verifiable outcomes and align with emerging EU regulatory frameworks for carbon removals. Policy support is essential to strengthen these mechanisms and prevent market failures, such as oversupply of low-quality certificates.

Moreover, the demand-supply imbalance observed in several scenarios, where consumer WTP exceeded farmer WTA, suggests latent potential for expanding soil-friendly markets. Yet structural limitations, such as land availability and adoption reluctance, may cap the achievable scale. Policymakers therefore need to design instruments that not only incentivize adoption but also secure permanence and ecological integrity. Hybrid payment systems, combining fixed cost coverage with performance-based rewards, could reconcile farmer needs with societal goals.

6.4 Overarching conclusions and policy recommendations

The assessment of market potential reveals that while there is substantial interest among consumers and scope for profitability among farmers, the conditions for successful upscaling are stringent. The most promising avenues lie in improved AECS and value chain approaches, where both consumer demand and farmer supply are viable. GHG certificate models, despite its ecological potential, faces greater barriers unless contract designs and price stability are improved.

To unlock the societal benefits of soil-health business models, several steps are recommended:

- Strengthen monitoring and certification to ensure credibility and build consumer trust.
- Design flexible, hybrid contracts that balance short-term farmer needs with long-term environmental goals.
- Support knowledge exchange and advisory services to reduce uncertainty and foster peer learning among farmers.
- Promote consumer awareness and labelling schemes that clearly communicate soil health benefits and justify premiums.

- Ensure policy coherence between CAP, carbon markets, and emerging EU soil strategies to avoid fragmented incentives.

In conclusion, upscaling soil-health-promoting business models is feasible but conditional. It requires aligning farmer adoption drivers with consumer acceptance mechanisms, supported by robust governance and policy frameworks. If these conditions are met, the societal returns – in terms of climate mitigation, ecosystem resilience, and sustainable food systems – are likely to be substantial.

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